

**“Enterprise Risk Management and Board Decision Making:
Context of Laos Construction and Tourism Industry”**

By

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Declaration

I hereby declare that the research work conducted in this thesis is entirely my own work. I am not using any author's work without permission and this work has not been submitted to any other institution. I also confirm that the research and papers used have been properly referenced.

Acknowledgement

First and foremost, I want to thank my parents for their continuous support and motivation. Their financial and moral support was integral for me to complete this thesis journey. I want to thank my close friends who gave me constant emotional support. I would like to thank my supervisor Dr. Andrew Armitrage for his insights and motivation to improve my work.

List of Abbreviation

ERM _____ Enterprise Risk Management

CG _____ Corporate Governance

GDP _____ Gross Domestic Product

LAK _____ Laos Currency

ISO _____ International Organization for
Standardization

CFO _____ Chief Financial Officer

VRIN _____ Valuable, Rare, Inimitable and Non

BOD _____ Board of Directors

IBM _____ International Business Machines

COSO _____ Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the
Treadway Commission

CEO _____ Chief Executive Officer

SEC _____ socio-economic classification

NYSE _____ New York Stock Exchange

NERI _____ National Economic Research Institute

Abstract

The business world has persistently felt the need of a robust risk management approach and culture across organizations because of several external and internal threats that a business is prone to face. The risk management systems of businesses were exposed with the occurrence of financial crisis 2008, and since then businesses are trying to improve their risk planning, identification and management with improved strategies and systems. Accounting and corporate governance scandals are another problem that has raised the awareness and need of pursuing enterprise risk management with improved focus. Moreover, the business environment around the world is becoming increasingly competitive and external market forces are pushing increasing pressure on businesses which is a serious challenge for their growth and sustainability. These problems are indicating a wider scope of the study under investigation i.e., effective implementation of ERM for improving board decision making.

This is a cross-sectional study and qualitative method has been used in this study for collecting and analysing data under which semi-structured interview technique has been employed for gathering primary data from the relevant board members of selected tourism and construction companies in Laos. Thematic analysis method has been used for analysing the data as part of which coding was established against the collected data. A gap exists in the literature regarding the standard implementation of ERM concept across developed and underdeveloped business world i.e., the adoption and implementation of ERM in the business environment of an underdeveloped country such as Laos is not clear. Lack of empirical evidence about the use of ERM as a strategic risk management tool across Laos (being an underdeveloped country) also exhibits a gap that is attempted to be fulfilled in this study. A key contribution intended by this study is the creation of awareness about the significant role of ERM for construction and tourism sector companies of Laos. Construction and tourism industries are two top performing industries of Laos, and this study intends to contribute towards the economic and strategic development of these industries by proposing a suitable and reliable ERM framework using which they can improve their board decision making.

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1. Chapter1 Introduction

Since the beginning of the 1990s, there has been a growing interest in the idea of enterprise risk management (ERM) due to the diverse array of financial and non-financial risks that are faced by organisations all over the world (Arena et al., 2010; Leoni and Florio, 2017). Experts are of the opinion that ERM has a direct impact on the performance of an organisation as a result of the numerous unanticipated risks that can arise (Soileau and Callahan, 2017; Hassan and Zou, 2017). Whereas, it has been claimed by some researchers that the relationship between firm performance and ERM can be impacted by a few intrinsic factors (Wang et al., 2010; Ali and Khan, 2017). In the wake of these developments, significant number of studies have discussed the importance of ERM practices for businesses such as, (Flouris and Yilmaz, 2017; Leoni and Florio, 2017; Eckles et al., 2014). There are number of ways in which the widely accepted definition has defined 'ERM', "as the process which assists organizations in identifying and managing risks systematically for the purpose of seizing the opportunities of fulfilling their organizational objectives". In addition to this, it is meant to uncover probable occurrences that may have an effect on the company, manage risks in accordance with the risk tolerance of the organisation, and provide reasonable assurance on the accomplishment of the organization's goals (COSO 2009, p.2).

The COSO book titled "Enterprise Risk Management Integrated Framework" served as the basis for this particular concept of ERM. Because of its applicability to a diverse range of fields, including the construction industry, this explanation has been used as the basis for the conceptualization of the proposed research project. Because of this, ERM must be utilised by all levels of the firm and utilised in the formulation of strategy in order to guarantee that organisational goals are attained in more than one area that overlaps with other categories.

"ERM" is an umbrella term that encompasses a wide number of risk management idioms, including enterprise-wide risk management, business risk management, strategic risk management, holistic risk management, and many more (Manab et al.,

2010; Yazid and Daud, 2019). According to the principle of risk management, an organization's accounting costs can be lowered in order to boost its overall performance. In actuality, ERM is predicated on gaining a competitive advantage, in accordance with the philosophy of risk management (Stulz, 1996). According to the findings of several researchers, ERM not only enables businesses to reduce their financial expenditures but also boosts their levels of production and gives them an advantage over their rivals (Tse and Krause, 2016).

1.1 Corporate/Industry Problems

There are several corporate levels and industry-related problems or issues that indicate the need to employ and integrate ERM effectively in the policy framework of the firms. This aspect naturally makes the board of directors influential i.e., due to their direct involvement and responsibility towards strategic decision making. The international economic crisis faced by the world during 2007-2009 has significantly enhanced the responsibility of the Board of Directors regarding the ERM process (McKinsey and Company, 2014). This means that, corporate boards are exposed to weaknesses and are vulnerable to risks from external environments, which can be countered with the use of ERM. This vulnerability urges the need to integrate ERM across the decision-making process as well. Companies have started to give more importance to ERM since it is being considered useful for resolving risks related to strategic planning (Kee, 2016). Therefore, there is an indication that the concept of ERM can be beneficial for solving industry problems.

The accounting frauds and discrepancies have been occurring across the global business arena such as, the 2011 UBS rogue trader scandal of £1.3billion Kwaku Adoboli from the Swiss bank happened due to its lack of awareness about the flaws of internal controls. This indicated that risk management process has reinforced the importance of effective ERM in firms (Edwards, 2011).

Such corporate scandals pose challenges for boards in terms of their decision making. Firms worldwide face similar issues and problems related to risks no matter what industry they belong to. Unexpectedly, many management leaders worldwide believe that implementation of ERM is not as effective as explained in theory (N.C. State University, 2015). This understanding can mean that for a developing country like Laos, the use of ERM for decision making will be no exception, however, it gives a reason to conduct this study for determining precise picture. According to 60% of Asian, European, African, Middle Eastern and Australian organisations, the ERM is a study, repeatable and organised process compared to 29% of American firms that follow this definition (Deloitte, 2018).

This global consideration of ERM as a strategic tool makes it imperative to evaluate how it contributes to the decision-making process, which is its ultimate objective. The percentage of organisations using the ERM process as a competitive benefit needs to improve. Almost 70% of firms outside the U.S. formally assign risk management responsibilities to their board members, and only 46% of U.S. organisations give this responsibility to the board. Only 20% of firms integrate ERM processes with strategies, while almost 80% of organisations have not yet integrated ERM training for the board executives (Jankensgard, 2018). Across business sectors, ERM implementation is lacking in the United States as compared to other developed countries around the world. These statistics indicate that despite general awareness about the importance of ERM across firms globally, optimal benefits are still not being extracted. Therefore, integration of ERM process can still be improved across organizations for achieving better risk management (COSO, 2018).

Organisations need to be aware, for ERM process to become a strategic tool, it needs to be integrated across organizational levels to identify and evaluate risks. Top management and board members need to re-evaluate the leadership style and structure for ensuring presence of assistance towards ERM integration (Beasely and Hancock, 2016). This understanding indicates, to drive sound decision making under the ERM framework, certain pre-requisites are to be adhered.

However, organisations also consider the ERM process as a tool for managing risks rather than a part of value creation and strategy making. When the organisations understand the importance of ERM and integrate it across their culture, they can then strategically benefit from it. As per Olivia, (2018) when organizations realises the importance of taking risks in generating benefits, the need to integrate the ERM process withing their strategic planning becomes imperative (Olivia, 2018). To effectively use strategic risk management, organisations need to consider ERM process as a systemic process that embeds risk evaluation, monitoring and identification steps. To ensure the presence of strategic perspective, organizations need to develop effective leadership and accountability across their respective boards (Jankensgard and Alviniussen, 2015). It is therefore evident that the adoption and functioning of ERM across requires the support of effective board leadership.

An executive board member can also be appointed, specifically for handling risk management activities and coordinating the activities of board members (Bogodistov and Wohlgemuth, 2017). It is therefore reflected, that a central role is to be played by the organisational leadership for facilitating the positive impact of ERM on the board decision making. Renowned organisations, including Lehman Brothers, Tokyo Electric and British Petroleum, were unable to systematically recognise and deal with potential risks in their firms. This inability pointed out the vulnerability of businesses towards risks and has indicated the need of implementing ERM across corporate boards for improving decision making, instead of relying on non-systematic risk management approaches.

1.2 Research Rationale

Researchers have noticed a rise in the number of companies looking to benefit from ERM in the last several years. The rising uncertainty in business decisions necessitates that organisations pay attention to the implementation of ERM (COSO 2004). COSO as a professional body has emphasized that organizations need to shift their focus towards ERM with clarity for extracting optimal benefits out of ERM.

For example, organizations need to decide whether they are looking for confirmation and compliance, or else merely trying to implement better risk management (Gatzert and Martin, 2015). As organizations consider the increasingly demanding business environment, they often conclude that there is a need to change the direction towards an ERM program for anticipating, adapting, and applying changes. This will redirect their resources and efforts towards risks and prospects, enhancing their performance and operationality (COSO, 2016).

It has been demonstrated that ERM is an effective tool for assisting businesses in better quantifying the impact of major risks and opportunities on expected results, estimating the volatility of expected results as a result of these risks and opportunities, and proactively selecting and implementing risk responses that assist management in driving bets. According to the findings of the research conducted, prosperous businesses have a high percentage of ERM integrated (Kahneman, 2014; Lynch, 2012; Mikes and Kaplan, 2015). With the help of these observations, the authors present a compelling argument for why businesses should extend their ERM discussions beyond a first review. Companies are able to accomplish this goal by increasing the impact of enterprise risk management (ERM) on decision-making and by treating risk as a relevant component in the process of formulating strategies and managing performance (Aljami, 2018).

Moreover, emerging consensus states that managing a firm is more critical than departments and traditional risks, including strategic risks and competitor actions, require decision making to be risk-averse and informed (Harwood, 2016). Therefore, in the context of this study, evaluation of ERM impact on decision making in the context of Laos is not just a problem but also an opportunity to improve the performance of corporate boards. Both academic institutions and businesses might benefit from using Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) in their strategic planning (ERM). The essential subject matter of this PhD thesis is a perfect illustration of the significance of the work. If enterprise risk management is incorporated into strategic business planning, the board

of directors will be better prepared to deal with major risk situations (Pierce and Goldstein, 2018).

The primary forces that drive value, as well as the challenges and opportunities most pertinent to realising that potential. They also have an effect on the outcomes that are anticipated to occur. It seems sense to foresee a divergence from the plan's performance, but does it make sense to do so both now and in the future (European Central Bank, 2018; Fraser, 2014). These questions can only be addressed, when the effective and smooth implementation of ERM has been achieved and is ultimately informing board decisions. The board's leadership is willing to make such decisions, however, whether this is occurring and to what extent it is happening in Laos needs to be investigated. Importantly, whether firms in Laos consider ERM as a strategic planning tool is also not known, due to a lack of evidence. The lack of evidence gives a strong rationale for conducting this study and presenting concrete empirical evidence and theoretical understanding.

The motivation behind pursuing the two industries in this study is the fact that tourism and construction industries are top performing industries in Laos. Both industries are riding high on success and given their performance trend, it will be interesting and of value to study their risk management integration. Especially, in the context of their board of directors, the use of ERM as strategic planning tool for informing decisions, will make sense because in terms of performance these industries are leaders in Laos. In addition, any objectivity and factual finding obtained from these industries, can be used as a benchmark for other industries. The reason behind using these industries is to provide feedback for practice instead of conducting a comparative analysis. Moreover, in terms of resources and opportunities, these industries are in a better position to integrate and practice ERM, and to understand about the ERM framework and its benefits.

Studies have indicated, even though ERM is an efficient process of managing potential risk, its implementation is not standardized yet (Mensah and Gottwald, 2016; Bromiley et al, 2015). The percentage of firms adopting ERM in developing countries is not encouraging due to lack of awareness and guidance about implementation and monitoring of systematic risk management (Saeidi et al, 2020). This signifies the need to conduct a study about ERM in Laos.

Therefore, it is important to learn about the ERM process, its implementation, its risks and the challenges associated with its integration. The scope of this study includes the approval and integration of ERM in Laos' business sector. ERM is a relevant concept among board members, because of its need for improved governance and risk averse decisions in the favor of business objectives. Notable business scandals and collapses across the globe have given rise to the importance of ERM and the need to implement ERM framework for managing the governance related decision making of organizational boards (NC State University, 2019). Developing understanding about different facets of the ERM processes has therefore become essential for organizations today. The ERM process deals with operational risks associated with business functions i.e., finance, marketing, information, reporting, accounting, and management (Malik et al, 2020).

Organisations continuously face risks in different ways, and are required to look for strategies that can assist in creating value whilst managing the risks (Zungu et al, 2018). The academic research provides vital support to organisations to aid their understanding of effective ERM processes giving a strong rationale for undertaking this research investigation.

1.3 Research Aim

This study aims to expand knowledge, understanding and awareness about the usability of enterprise risk management for corporate boards' decision making. This study intends to identify the literature gap, regarding the use of enterprise risk management approach across corporate boards of developing countries. Given the pressure of

making strategic and financially beneficial decisions on corporate boards, this study can potentially be important for board members across Laos because it can assist in improving the decision-making culture. This study holds significance, because it intends to encourage adoption and improvement of risk management as a culture across corporate boards.

In addition, this student intends to contribute by proposing the factors that can assist in developing and implementing ERM as a system across corporate boards. The term framework in this chapter is referring to a guided structure and support mechanism which can be used by the organizations for achieving bigger and productive outcomes. For example, in the research aim presented below, the term framework is referring to a support structure that can be used by the board of directors for improving their decision making and achieving enhanced performance related results which includes minimization of risks.

- *“This study aims to propose an ERM framework for improving board decision-making in the construction/tourism industry of Laos”.*

1.4 Objectives

For achieving the formulated and established research aim adequately, this study has produced the below-presented objectives that will allow the researcher to break down the research process in distinct yet interlinked phases. These objectives indicate the scope this study intends to cover and address to achieve the research aim. Three key dimensions have been developed as a result, which embeds key variables and factors which the preceding chapters will undertake:

1. To evaluate the importance of ERM for organisational decision making.
2. To examine the challenges in the implementation of ERM.

3. To propose a strategy that how corporate boards better implement ERM in their decision making.

1.5 Questions

After developing the above-presented research aim and objectives, two key research questions are relevant to be addressed for reflecting what this study intends to achieve. Research questions presented below will enable the researcher to adequately address the research aim:

1. Which components are essential to include in the ERM framework for decision making?
2. What kind of challenges undermines the usability and implementation of ERM as a decision-making tool?

In the above presented research questions, the term ERM framework is referring to the structure and the components that actually forms the guiding structure for board of directors. These questions are exhibiting some pre-requisite factors that needs to be present in the ERM framework, for making it the desired guiding structure which can be used by board of directors.

1.6 The Context of Laos

Laos is a less developed country, however, it was one of the largest growing financial estates of the Pacific and East Asia region with a \$1410 GNI per capita in 2015, and 13th most rapidly growing economy internationally. It had an average GDP growth rate of 8% during recent years (World Bank, 2017). In 2017, the GDP growth reached 7.8%, while the per capita income reached \$2,270. Despite the flooding disasters in mid-2018,

the financial growth stood firm at 6.7% (Zinhua, 2018). The gradual growth of manufacturing, construction and power industries led to consistent economic progress during the first half of 2018. Laos is taking action to gain macro-economic consistency, by improving domestic profit collection, managing expenses and improving debt management for the public. Development is balanced with the settlement of public obligations and enhancement of capital expenses.

The fiscal consolidation of Laos was expected to decrease the public debt during 2019, however, it had limited impact on the GDP ratio. Laos PDR has faced socio-economic challenges such as, poverty and healthcare. The improving literacy level has been a positive sign in the midst of challenges. Laos has gradually made significant progress by meeting the challenges, which has allowed the country to improve its ranking in terms of 'Ease of Doing Business' (The World Bank, 2019a).

Building was included in this nation's industrial sector, which contributed significantly to the 31.53 percent increase in GDP that it experienced in 2018. 2020 (International Trade Administration) The building of new roads, water systems, and electrical grids is well under way in Laos at the moment. As the population of the country increases, there will be an increased demand for various transportation projects. In the central business district of Vientiane, numerous development projects, including the China-Laos Railway and an expressway, as well as office complexes and shopping malls, are now underway. The building of Laos's infrastructure has attracted the participation of a great number of corporations from China, Vietnam, and Thailand. When it comes to building new infrastructure, the government of Laos draws funding from a variety of sources, including both domestic and foreign contributors as well as international financial institutions (The Nation, 2020). Construction is also taking place on the country's aviation infrastructure, which includes the country's airport. The Wattay International Airport in Vientiane has recently finished the construction of two new terminals, one for domestic flights and one for international flights. Laos has set a goal to provide electricity to 90 percent of the country's population by the year 2020, and it hopes to have its electrical infrastructure fully connected by then.

Because of this, Laos will need to shell out money and invest in the recruitment of specialists in the fields of power management and electricity distribution (Asian Development Bank, 2020a). According to a recent research conducted by the World Travel and Tourism Council of the United Nations, tourism in Laos has resulted in the creation of 114,000 new jobs. This trend is expected to touch almost 30 percent of the country's labour force by the year 2028, when it is projected that 121,000 new employment will be created. In Laos, an increase in the country's per capita income can be attributed, in part, to the creation of more than 385,000 jobs in the tourism industry and industries closely associated to it (The Nation, 2020). It can be observed from the background discussion that, construction and tourism are key contributing industries in the economic development of Laos.

1.6.1 Significance of Tourism and Construction Industries

Travel and Tourism is one of the financially beneficial sectors and is responsible for creating jobs, enhancing exports, and generating prosperity for many countries. The annual analysis of the global impact of Travel and Tourism showed that in 2017, total GDP is 10.4%, job creation is 313 million and a 9.9% increase in the employment rate. Travel and tourism directly contributed to almost 115.7 billion LAK, a total 4.2% of GDP in 2017 and rise in the forecast by 4.7% in 2018 (Fong et al., 2020), as presented in the figure below:

LAOS: DIRECT CONTRIBUTION OF TRAVEL & TOURISM TO GDP

Source: WTTC, (2018)

Figure 1: The direct contribution of Travel and Tourism to GDP is expected to grow by 4.2% pa to LAK 8,018.1bn (3.5% of GDP) by 2028.

LAOS: TOTAL CONTRIBUTION OF TRAVEL & TOURISM TO GDP

Figure 2: LAOS Total Contribution of travel and Tourism to GDP

(Source: WTTC, 2018).

Travel and Tourism contributed Lak 16,764 billion to GDP in 2017 and is forecasted to increase by 4.8% p.a. to 28,000 billion LAK by 2028. This sector provided almost 114,000 jobs that are nearly 3.5% of employment in 2017. The investment of the travel and tourism industry was LAK4, 629.6 billion, which is 10.5% of the total investment in

2017. It is expected to increase in 2018 by 5.7% and 5.6% to almost LAK8, 430.6 billion (10% of total) in the next ten years (Asian Development Bank, 2019).

Travel and tourism directly contributed to 4.2% of GDP (LAK5, 115.7 billion), expected to rise by LAK5, 309.1 billion (3.8%). This aspect mainly deals with the financial profits generated by the sectors such as travel agencies, passenger transportations, hotels and airlines. It is expected that travel and tourism will contribute an almost 4.2% increase in GDP to LAK 8, 018.1 billion until 2028. The tourism and travel sector created 114,000 job opportunities in 2017 (3.5% of employment scale) which was expected to decline in 2018 by 0.6% (Asian Development Bank, 2020). This includes jobs for workers in hotels, travel agencies, transportation services, and airlines. An example would include the restaurant and entertainment industries' operations aided by tourists.

Tourism Industry Laos

Tourism and eco-tourism are working to increase job opportunities and promote a clean and green environment. The growth of regional tourism is growing rapidly. The World Bank Group is planning on discovering ways to attract many tourists, aid SMEs in fulfilling the market demands, and increase Laos' brand image by initiating talks with Green Growth Development Policy Financing (PDF) (The World Bank, 2019). International Finance Corporation (IFC) is also continuously aiding the private sector to enhance its service level in tourism. The number of visitors visiting Laos increased by just under 20% per year, and the increase in the number of visitors in the last ten years reached 4.7 million tourists, which generated around US\$725 million foreign exchange profits (The World Bank, 2019a). This sector has created considerable job opportunities for the country in the last decade i.e., 3.7% of the tourists visit for a holiday whilst the rest come for doing adventure or seeing nature.

The tourist industry is based on nature-friendly practices, and is expected to create opportunities for people in rural areas, especially for women and ethnic groups, and will

also preserve the country's natural habitat. The Tourism Research and Administrative Division's deputy director in Laos, described the organisation's efforts in researching the problems and solutions in tourism industry. The official personnel stated that some of the reasons behind a decline includes low-quality services and treatment offered to the tourists (Khanal et al., 2017). The government launched a program named 'Visit Laos Year' in 2018, and its primary purpose was to promote tourism and attract more visitors. It allowed the visitors to experience different local activities and carnivals in various places around the country (Laotian Times, 2017). Since the country is filled with breathtaking nature, attractive temples and rich history, people mainly considered tourism a big part of the economy of this land-locked country.

However, the share of tourism in the country's GDP was \$2 billion or almost 13.7% in the year 2017. This was significantly less than Thailand with 20.6% GDP or \$82.5 billion, or Cambodia with 28.3% GDP or \$5.5 billion (Asian Development Bank, 2021).

The World Travel and Tourism Council's most recent report of 2017 stated that Laos was in the 118th position in the ranking according to GDP (The World Bank, 2020). However, there are some other challenges that have been faced by Laos. For example, the percentage of visitors visiting the country for tourism purposes decreased by almost 2% in 2018 as compared to the percentage in 2016. The National Economic Research Institute of Laos (NERI) declared that, this percentage in Europe decreased by 27%, in South Korea declined by 2%, and almost 11% fewer visitors visited Thailand (World Bank Group, 2018). Laos has to face various challenges, some of these include increased expenses of general services, decreased number of attractive products for tourists and limited marketing options. They have played a significant role in restricting the tourists visiting the country in good numbers.

These numbers have been disappointing for the economic development of Laos because their major reliance is on tourism industry. Laos has made efforts recently to increase yearly financial growth by focusing on the development of tourism industry. Laos aims to keep on expanding this growth in different sectors of the country, including

tourism. This aim is being pursued by the government seriously and as part of this, Laos has launched a 'Visit Laos' program, which has brought significant changes in the tourism industry of the country. The objective was to attract 5.2 million tourists and expects its revenue to be almost equal to \$910 million in the year 2018 (Nikkei Asia, 2018). Some of the actions taken by the government are based on the coordination of private sector, and different government sectors and their promotion of the program 'Visit Laos' Year through various media platforms.

The visit of Deputy Prime Minister of Laos to Vang Vieng, which is considered one of the most attractive spots for international tourists is a prime example of focus being given to tourism industry. In this visit, Deputy Prime Minister motivated the local authorities to enhance the attractiveness of Vang Vieng as a tourist destination. Deputy Prime Minister also urged them to coordinate with various commercial and industrial sectors to avoid excessive industrial expansion, which can hamper the tourism industry (Kang, 2018).

One of the problems identified was the lack of reliable communication, between public and private sectors and the ineffective communication of governmental departments. The government have realised this problem and has started to cooperate with Asian Development Bank to publish a Destination Management Plan (Asian Development Bank, 2021). This plan focused on hospitality abilities, promotion and marketing, accountable tourism and training of tour guides. This development enhanced the communication opportunities between the private sectors, public government and non-governmental sectors, which had not been seen before. The government is very determined to make other significant changes as well. For example, many plans have been created to launch E-visa (electronic visa) services by the end of the year or the start of the next year as an effort to accommodate more international customers (World Bank Group, 2018).

The government of Laos devised plan to offer visas easily for people who want to come for tourism purposes and then gradually extend it for entrepreneurs or businesspeople

who wish to expand their business in Laos (Government of Lao PDR, 2019). The Laos government expects to see the results of its efforts in the next few years as an increase in the number of tourists to reach 7.5 million by 2025 (Kang, 2018).

Such positive advancements by Laos government have enacted a positive response from other countries. The World Travel and Tourism Council experts, state that the growing tourism industry is expected to increase job opportunities offered by the sector by almost 0.3%, which is 384,500 jobs by the year 2018 to nearly 428,000 jobs by the year 2028. It also states that, the tourism industry's contribution to the country's GDP is forecasted to grow in the year 2018 and subsequently during the next ten years as well. The experts stated that, such information should be forecasted in an authentic way, since the country has major reliance on tourism industry. For now, it is evident that the Laos government recognises the difficulties that are preventing it from realising the country's total tourism potential and that it is heading in the right direction (Kang, 2018).

Construction Industry Laos

Construction is one of the major economic sectors for Laos. Studies have shown that the financial crisis faced by the South Asian countries from the year 2000 has caused many detrimental effects on the economic growth and has also lowered the living standards of Laos (Vangkeomany, 2010). The capital of Laos is peaceful and not as flashy or attractive as compared to the hustling, bustling and high buildings of other Southeast Asian capitals such as Singapore, Kuala Lumpur and Bangkok. However, this city is losing its dullness and raising its reputation as the booming economic centre by hosting summits for high-class leaders such as Chinese President Xi Jinping, U.S. President Barack Obama and others in the year 2016 (Roughneen, 2016).

The country's capital city has many cranes towering over the people every day, and the construction sounds are dimming out the hustling and heavy traffic on the roads. According to the Asian Development Bank, this rapid construction spree is due to 7-8% of the country's financial growth in the last few years, which has doubled since 2006.

Despite this, Lao's economy is still the smallest, according to the Association of Southeast Asian Nations, which is almost less than 12\$ billion (McKinsey and Company, 2014).

Most of the growth of the economy is fueled by hydropower exports and mining. The government considers Laos the "Battery of Southeast Asia", and for a good reason. It has coordinated with many international companies, including Thai and Chinese, working to construct massive dams in the Mekong River and promised them energy supplies in return. Even though the construction of this dam has caused problems for countries such as Vietnam and Cambodia that depend on this river for tourism, fishing and agricultural purposes, the primary concern of Laos is creating job opportunities. The dam-building and mining sectors of the country only employ almost 25,000 people (Olarn et al, 2018).

The government is aiming to grow these sectors. Even though the government has established tax-free zones and other benefits for international companies such as Nikon and Toyota of Japan have their factories in the country, it still has not attracted many labourers. The government has made significant investments to aid the business finances and stimulate the country's financial situation, and therefore is expecting to see almost 10% growth in the construction industry by the end of the year (OECD, 2018).

This trend is being promoted by many interconnected factors such as real estate, infrastructure development, and investment in various services (Vientiane Times, 2019). The Director-General of the Centre of Macroeconomic Policy and Economic Restructuring belonging to the National Institute for Economic Research explained to Vientiane Times in an interview on Tuesday that the growth in the construction sector is enhancing rapidly. However, some problems need to be addressed, such as servicing debts to businesses and managing loans if the government wants to expand the construction industry. The government knows about the chronic debt problem and has given eight solutions to the construction companies, enhancing the industry.

These measures are critical for increasing the growth of construction companies in the future. In the previous years, the private sector faced many problems while managing State-projects due to the heavy debts. The contractors were not being paid back, and the companies were under obligation by the bank. Also, the banks were unable to loan them money to continue the state projects.

Such issues delayed the projects and also made the strategies fail. The growth of the construction sector greatly depended on bank loans. Because of this, financial stimulus initiatives were released as a solution to such long-term and short-term problems (World Bank Group, 2018a). In the previous year, an increase in the service and energy departments, such as shopping complexes, led to increased 8.9% growth in the construction department. Statistics state that the construction sector's growth increased by 13.6% or 3.4% from 2013-17 (Asian News Network, 2019). The Loa government is motivated and determined that such impressive growth will continue this year since many construction schemes are underway, such as constructing and developing the Siphandon new city, Vang Vieng-Vientiane expressway China-Laos railway and so on.

The deputy Prime Minister and Minister of Finance stated at the current session of the National Assembly that these projects would have great importance in enhancing the macro-economy. Also, new hydropower projects are being initiated. With the help of the tourism industry and real estate, the construction industry will grow by leaps and bounds. Real estate is also expected to enhance alongside the construction industry in the financial sector. The Finance Minister of Laos also motivated the local and official authorities to pay special heed to the tourism industry. It will act as the backbone for the construction sector. Since Laos could not meet its international tourism target last year, the government needs to pay more attention during the China-Laos Year 2019 (World Bank Group, 2020).

1.7 Chapter Summary

The chapter is based on the problem statement, research aims, objectives, research questions, and the context of Laos's tourism and construction industry. It has been identified from the chapter that the construction and tourism industry of Laos is unable to implement ERM effectively. This is because of less awareness about the significance of ERM processes and lack of guidance related to implementing and monitoring risk management in organisations. Therefore, it is crucial to learn about the ERM process, its implementation, its risks, and the challenges associated with its integration. This study deals with the approval and integration of ERM in Laos' business sector, especially in the case of the Tourism and Construction sector. Due to this, the study aims to expand the knowledge, understanding, and awareness about the usability of enterprise risk management for corporate boards concerning their decision making. This study will identify the literature gap regarding the use of enterprise risk management approach across corporate boards of developing countries.

Chapter2 Literature Review

The literature review chapter will mainly consist of your distinct and interconnected themes i.e., ERM, Risk Management & Culture, Decision Making, ERM Theories & Models. This chapter will revolve around the aforementioned four themes and will discuss these in detail by using sub-themes that are highly relevant and meaningful. The theoretical framework of this study will be informed by these themes of literature review i.e., the components of framework will be driven by the literature review findings. These four pillars of literature review are strictly in line with the research objectives and questions outlined in the first chapter. For example, the scope and context defined by research objectives will be reflected across these four themes and will provide a meaningful direction for the development of theoretical framework and data collection tools. The knowledge and information presented under these four themes will establish the pathway and boundaries of the data collection and analysis process as well i.e., keeping the rest of the study aligned.

2.1 Understanding the Concept and Dynamics of ERM

According to Jankensgard (2018), ERM (Enterprise Risk Management) is defined as the usage of high level and frequent analytical techniques responsible for evaluating risks that may be harmful to the whole organisation's IT infrastructure and information assets. The primary use of ERM is to assess the high-level risks that may enrisk the critical operations of the organisations as considered by the management. The insight responsible for handling the essential business functionalities related to compliance, risk, and governance is Enterprise Risk Intelligence. The implementation of ERM is not typical among organisations because they do not have the appropriate resources or technologies to incorporate it. Because of this, they are even practising ERM as a challenging task to accomplish.

Still, ERM has many benefits for organisations, such as evaluating the impact of potential risks on the whole organisation, planning to reduce risks, and better alignment of security goals and IT business (NC State University, 2017). Dealing with potential risks on a regular basis is one of the primary responsibilities of all the business leaders in the world. Typically, any risks faced by a department of an organisation are the concerned leader or manager (McShane, 2018). An example would be the Chief Operating Officer dealing with issues related to manufacturing and distribution. The Chief Technology Officer copes with all the IT (Information Technology) problems, and then the Chief Marketing Officer handles the customer relationship and sales. The treasurer deals with the cash flow and other financial management projects. All of these leaders have to deal with the risks and risks that their department deals with. This method of dealing with risks is mainly known as stove-pipe risk management or silo since every leader of different departments has to deal with the risks they face (Iswajuni et al., 2018). The management is always thinking of ways to handle risks, but the main problem they face is to choose the person who will lead the solution (Yang et al., 2018). They usually are not successful in finding people who will successfully handle the risks. Because of this, ERM is generally focused on creating risk-free strategies that have no relation to operational strategy and its implementation.

In this, the relationship between strategy and risk is not clearly defined. Because of this, the need for an Executive that will handle the risks according to ERM and lead the project successfully and responsibly (Vollmer, 2017). Mark Beasley and Bonnie Hancock wrote an article in the Journal of Accountancy about a technique that executives can adopt to deal with risks in a strategic lens way. When the CFO position presented its points regarding the issue, it was realised that they could be adopted by any executive who wishes to handle risks strategically faced by the organisations. In this way, ERM can help the company accomplish its goals (Beasley et al., 2017).

Disadvantages of Traditional Strategies for Risk Management

Even though the responsibility of risks related to the department to their leaders appears to be a good idea; however, this way of handling risks has its setbacks. There might be some severe risks that the person in charge might not notice, and the organisation's progress may be affected.

Some risks might even fall in the category of silos that might not be detected by the leaders or managers (Deloitte, 2020). Risks are always unexpected and do not follow the business plan; that is why they may attack any time. (Battaglia et al., 2016). Because of this, a risk may be hidden in some corner that the leaders might not notice until it shows itself in the form of a disastrous risk factor. An example might be that the company is not detecting any change in the market demographics; however, the reality is that the population is shifting essentially towards urban areas, and the leader has failed to notice this change (Manab and Ahmed, 2016).

Risks affect different silos in unpredictable ways. Therefore, even though a leader has recognised a risk, he might not consider it very important or hazardous towards the business' operations (Office of Rail and Road, 2020). A risk that seems to be very minimal towards one part of the organisation's operations may prove extremely disastrous towards the other operational units of the organisation. It might also detriment its collective performance. Also, in a traditional strategy for risk management, one silo might not notice the detrimental effect a risk might cause on the other operations of a business. An example may be that risk of cyber risks may lead the IT department to implement new protocols against invaders' attacks. However, the workers might find these new protocols challenging to understand, causing frustration and tension, which results in costly workarounds and detrimental performance of business operations (Bento et al., 2018).

More than often, the traditional risk management strategies have an internal lens used to identify and create contingency plans against the risks they face (Berry and Shabana, 2020). The management usually deals with problems in the department of their organisation and tend to ignore any difficulties that may be gathering outside that will severely affect the organisation. An example might be that the organisation has not considered that its opponent is creating and releasing a new product that will affect the sales of its products. Even though many leaders understand the importance of the connection between return and risk, they find it challenging to plan risk and implement it in the strategies for their organisation (Soltanizadeh et al., 2018).

An example may be that the people involved in implementing and creating the operational strategy cannot deal with the plans' risks because they were not involved with the planning process of the developed techniques. When new strategies are created, they bring unexpected risks that the traditional system cannot handle yet (Guyen, 2020).

In the past few years, the leaders of the organisations have realised that the strategies adopted for creating plans for the organisations have many flaws and that they should adopt the enterprise risk management methodology to deal with the organisations' risks better (Grant and Baden-Fuller, 2018). They have understood that knowing about risks beforehand is safer than waiting for them to escalate out of hand. Because of this, they have started to implement the ERM strategy as a part of their business plans to manage the risks that the company faces. The main goal of the ERM is to create a general and complete view of the expected risks that may hinder the achievements of the company's objectives. The 'E' in ERM indicates that this process creates the complete list of all the significant risks that might prove harmful to the organisation's success (Mark and Gallagher, 2015). It can also be said that the job of ERM is to create a basket of risks responsible for positively and negatively affecting the business's operations. The most important strategy that the leader of any organisation should have been an efficient ERM process.

The potential risks found by ERM should always be considered while making business plans for the organisation (Lubojanski and Sheedy, 2018). With increased knowledge about potential risks that a business might face, the board and management can make careful plans that will allow them to reach their business goals without actually tackling such risks. Actively thinking about risks that might occur is a valuable exercise as it allows an organisation to strategize better. Also, the management will be better prepared to face any risks that might happen in the future.

Elements of an ERM Process

Risks are always coming and going in a business; that is why they are an ongoing process. However, some people think that ERM is a never-ending process and a continuous struggle that organisations have to face.

The initial phase of the ERM process may need some collaboration with the project management. Only after the business has started to reap the ERM Process's benefits, it will realise that a fully continuous and functional risk management process is the one

that will give them the most help (Emerald Publishing Group, 2016). The significant factors of an ERM process are described in the figure below. Before delving deep into the details of these points, it is necessary to understand the diagram that has an oval shape and has different arrows connecting them. This overall makes the ERM diagram (Zhao et al., 2016). The clockwise arrows reinforce the point that ERM is an ongoing process. Once a business starts working with the ERM process, it is their responsibility to continuously assess, identify, monitor and plan against all kinds of risks that may affect the goals and objectives of the business.

Figure3

Figure 3: ERM Process

Source: Zhao et al, (2016)

It is crucial to use the strategic lens to identify, assess and manage the potential risks of the business. This is because the main objective of ERM is to inform the organisation about any potential risks that it might have to face in the future.

The first phase of the ERM process should evaluate the risks that create value for the organisation and the new plans and resources reserved for the organisation to help the business grow. To make sure that ERM knows about all the external threats and

opportunities that the company might be facing in the future, the ERM strategy must be created with a clear objective of the business. In addition, what steps it needs to take to achieve all of its long term and short-term goals (Khan et al., 2016).

2.1.1 From Traditional Risk Management to Enterprise Risk Management

A "silo-based" approach to risk management (also known as traditional risk management, or TRM) involves isolating and addressing one particular issue at a time. When companies treat different categories of risk as if they were entirely separate entities, they create what are known as silos. Therefore, each risk is handled as though it were completely independent from the others (Pagach & Warr, 2010). One of the drawbacks of this strategy is that it can result in different approaches being taken to deal with threats that are essentially the same (Lundqvist, 2013). A key deficiency lies in the fact that silo-based risk management does not take into account the interconnection of the various dangers (Wihlborg, 2009). The company is unable to adequately assess the risks it faces and the consequences of those risks due to the weak understanding of risk and the natural hedge that is not recognised, and this is a big shortcoming for two reasons. The first reason is that this is a serious shortcoming (Lundqvist, 2013). Enterprise risk management places an emphasis on taking a holistic approach to hazards and the management of risks. However, it also places an emphasis on the significance of addressing all of a company's risks at the same time. administration of potential dangers to a company (Nia, et al., 2017). It's possible that events that have nothing to do with money at all could yet have a detrimental effect on the accomplishments of an organisation.

This indicates that a wide array of dangers, as well as the connections that exist between them, need to be taken into consideration (Tavakoli et al., 2016). The economic downturn has increased attention paid to the management of corporate risks.

This method, which is also known as "enterprise risk management" (ERM), includes a wide variety of actions that are aimed at fully, strategically, and comprehensively handling all of a company's potential threats (Dafikpaku, 2011). ERM has recently

become increasingly significant for firms as a result of the growing risk as well as the requirement to restructure organisations and corporations (Martin, 2013). According to Brown, Steen, and Foreman's research, this presents an opportunity for businesses to seek out more favourable chances and accomplish more lofty objectives (2009; see also Foreman, Steen, and Foreman). The primary goal of enterprise risk management (ERM) is to assist an organization's management in coping with the unpredictability, dangers, and opportunities that come along with it (Eikenhout, 2015). An excellent illustration of this can be found in COSO (2004), which defined ERM as a "process, affected by an entity's Board of Directors (BOD) and other personnel, applied in strategy setting and across the enterprise, designed to identify potential events that may affect the entity, and manage risk to provide reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of entity objectives (COSO, 2004)". This is an excellent illustration of how ERM can work.

According to the definition provided by the Asian Risk Management Institute, Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) is "a systematic and integrated approach to risk that supports the configuration of strategy, process, and people." This enables businesses to determine, rank, and effectively manage the risks that are most important to them (Ai, Teoh, Lee, & Muthuveloo, 2017). "the discipline by which an organisation in any business analyses, manages, exploits, finances, and tracks risk from all sources with the objective of raising the value of a firm to its stakeholders on short and long periods," is how risk management is defined. An enterprise risk management (ERM) strategy strives to manage and limit risks while increasing opportunities (Society of Actuaries, 2006).

2.1.2 Challenges in ERM Implementation

The advantages and financial situation of ERM are different for different organisations since they have their business plans and goals (Beasley et al., 2018). There are many challenges for the organisations that implement the ERM process.

The process is said to be complicated and is not easily understandable. In addition, organisations need to understand all the aspects of ERM and what situations they should avoid. In addition to the managers, the Internal Auditors must be involved in the ERM planning phase since any risks arising from the implementation of ERM will severely affect the organisation's financial situation. Proper training about handling and managing risks should also be given to the Board members, and they should be taught about countermeasures that should be applied if any risk is faced at any time. Auditors should also be allowed to hold independent analyses on the progress whenever they want to avoid unnecessary risks. They should mention the contingency plans of the organisation regarding the challenges faced due to ERM implementation (Ferkoli, 2010; Schanfield, 2009). Some of the common ERM challenges are described below.:

Describing Risk: To ensure that all the organisation's employees understand the required terminologies related to the potential risks, a summarised glossary should be created when the ERM process is implemented.

A clear explanation of all the risks and associated words should be defined clearly when the ERM process is implemented so that all the employees use the exact words, and no misunderstandings can occur (Teoh et al, 2017).

The organisations can use some of the terms that include risk, residual risk, likelihood, risk management, significant risk, inherent risk, ERM, and risk assessment. Deciding on a Framework: many organisations have used many ERM frameworks in the past years until the ISO 31000:2009 was released by the International Standards Organization (ISO) in 2009. According to this, every organisation should evaluate its business lifecycle and select an ERM process (Silva et al, 2019). On the other hand, the author thinks that all the business entrepreneurs of Nigeria should adopt the ISO 2009.

Before implementing ERM, the organisation's managers should have a basic idea about ERM to implement its implementation effectively. The organisation should also defend its decision of selecting an appropriate framework for ERM if it has to. Internal auditors can only decide which one of the ERM frameworks is best for the organisation after

thoroughly reviewing all the options (Fraser et al, 2016). After the auditors have managed this task, the rest is straightforward to manage.

Risk Assessment: All risks can be successfully assessed if the likelihood, significance and proper timing of all the risks are known. Many techniques such as quantitative, semi-quantitative and qualitative analysis are used to assess risks properly. The main challenge is to find the best strategies or combination of techniques that are the most suitable for tackling risks (Ranong and Phuenngam, 2015).

Risk Evaluation: When all the risks have been dealt with in the risk assessment phase, they are appropriately evaluated. The potential risks are adequately assessed, and then they are compared with the amount of risk tolerance the organisation has, taking into consideration their business goals. The result of this exercise is that the organisation has a complete list of tolerances and risks. The organisation should put more effort towards reducing risks that have a low-risk tolerance. An essential part of the risk evaluation is that the organisation should share information about risk tolerances regarding all areas (Olivera et al, 2019). Usually, just board members are not enough to evaluate all the potential risks' tolerances. This is why the other stakeholders should also make efforts to assess the organisation's risk tolerance level.

Risk Treatment: Making the board members and management understand the options for treating risks is challenging. This is because you might not always get an appropriate reaction. The organisation may have the resources to deal with high-level risks. If many risks have a low tolerance level, the board members might even have to re-evaluate them (Fraser et al, 2017). Some of the options of risk treatment are as follows:

Accepting Risks: in this case, the organisation does nothing. It acknowledges that the risks cannot be avoided anymore and decides to accept the consequences. The board members hold a meeting to evaluate the risk tolerances to ensure that doing nothing is possible for them (Li et al, 2015).

Risk Avoidance: To avoid the risk that might happen, one should skip the activity that will lead to it. Managers usually have to transfer, share or outsource the tasks. With this, managers can hire third parties to do back-office work, payroll processing or manufacturing. Managers can also make efforts to fix the issue. For this, a team can select the appropriate solution for the risk by doing a cost-benefit analysis on the task (Khan et al, 2016). At some point, the organisation might also need experts like Actuaries.

Risk Monitoring: the organisation should always check whether their risk management process works appropriately by efficiently monitoring it. The monitoring responsibilities should be distributed among board members, business managers and internal auditors. An effective monitoring process can also be created by using specific software that ensures high performance (Deloach, 2015).

Creating Risk Awareness Among Employees: To ensure that the risk awareness protocol is properly spread among all the employees, the organisation needs to create a risk-aware culture. The chosen ERM structure can be used to make sure that all the employees from top to bottom are trained. The organisation can slowly adopt specialised risk awareness techniques, which includes control self-assessment (Olson and Wu, 2016). The whole team should be involved in such activities as decision making and implementation. All the divided responsibilities should also be appropriately documented for future reference.

Technology Set-Up: The members and policies of a team usually determine the quality of an effective ERM, not the technology. Many organisations use techniques that are different from the traditional risk management frameworks or are slightly different from the frameworks chosen by the organisation (Heong et al, 2018). Using such practices can lead to the creation of new risks. However, that does not mean that technology has no role in the implementation of the ERM process. The technology created should be tailored according to the needs of the framework and should be utilised in several ways. The risks should be recorded in a repository database.

The stakeholders should be able to voice their thoughts secretly with the help of efficient voting technology. Training and compliance monitoring can be done digitally with the Compliance software (Florio et al, 2017). Other technologies that the organisations can use for their ERM process include software for audit paperwork, monitoring risks and extracting audit data.

Involving Human Resources and Strategy into the ERM Process: Integrating human resources and strategies into the ERM process is particularly important. To ensure the success of ERM, Human resources suggest that a specific goal should be included in the employee's management plan. Otherwise, there is a high chance that the implementation plan fails. In the same way, the organisation should clearly define the objectives and vision of the business along with its strategy at the start of the exercise. This strategy will allow the ERM process to start successfully, and with this, the organisation's strategy and goals will be clearly defined (Ferkolj, 2010; Jackson, 2009). To ensure that the ERM is implemented successfully, the business strategy should have positive risk culture as an integral part, and this part should be clearly explained and described. Also, the board members should initialise the process of ERM to effectively think about ways and implementation of tackling risks. All the steps of the ERM process, including the risk strategies and its guiding principle, should be documented. The organisation should integrate the ERM process as an integral part of its strategies and plans rather than a distinct sector to enjoy its benefits fully (McKinsey and Company, 2020).

2.1.3 ERM and Strategy

According to the COSO framework (2004), the ERM process is applicable in all strategy settings. It is designed to ensure that the related entities succeed in their business goals

(p.2). This definition explains that ERM is a process used to deal with any potential risks that may create hindrances for the organisation to achieve their goals. Anderson and Frigo (2011) supported this by saying that ERM should be integrated into all business plans and strategies to show positive risks.

Even though the importance of ERM is explained, its implementation in the organisation proves to be challenging. Pagach, Branson and Beasley (2015) used the sample results from almost 645 companies from various business industries to find out the business-specific factors that influence the successful implementation of ERM. They discovered that ERM is only used as a strategic tool when a business faces risks or when the information about high-level risks is given to the board members annually. The ERM and strategy were more commonly used to manage when executives received proper ERM training as per their findings.

Moreover, Pagach et al, (2015) observed that the organisations had a management-level risk handling committee and regularly updated information about risk factors faced by the organisation. They also found that a complicated relationship between risk management and executive compensation enhances the strategic value of the ERM process. The researchers determined that public firms considered the ERM process just a value-added method, whereas private firms considered it a critical strategic tool. The audit partners, audit committee members and Chief Financial Officers of the same business of 11 different organisations were interviewed in detail by Wright, Krishnamoorthy and Cohen (2014). They called it the governance triad. They discovered that the audit members and CFOs were more involved with the strategic planning processes than the audit members. There were only two organisations recorded in which all three members of the governance trade were equally involved. In half of these organisations, the majority of the triad members were involved in the strategic planning process.

In contrast, only the CFO and audit members were involved in the strategy connection process in the other half. When the audit members and CFOs were asked about their

roles in the compliance, operational, reporting and strategic activities individually, they all declared that they had an essential role in achieving the desired objectives. The external audit members realised that their role in assessing risks concerning objectives and goals was not that important. The authors also reviewed these responses through the resource dependence and agency lens theory. They found out that according to agency theory, ERM was used for monitoring purposes only.

However, it could also balance business risks and corporate strategies according to the resource dependence theory. This empirical evidence is indicating that ERM is a potentially strong tool and approach for identifying organizational risks especially when it comes to the board activities and functioning.

On the other hand, Viscelli et al. (2016) after interviewing the ERM champions of almost 14 organisations discovered that most organisations use ERM as a means of understanding risks. When asked about the areas where ERM processes can be improved, nearly all of them stated that it should be an integral part of the strategy-making process and should be implemented effectively in the business plans over the next 3-5 years. This empirical evidence is also indicating that ERM is potentially a useful component of the risk management strategy for business firms and organizations need to pay attention towards integrating it in their risk management culture more strategically for extracting benefits.

Overall, it seemed that all of them thought the drawback of ERM was that it was first used as a risk avoidance strategy and then ultimately used as a monitoring tool for managing risks. Thus, the full extent of ERM benefits cannot be achieved due to the lack of ability to link both strategy and ERM. Interestingly, Zeghal, Ben-Amar and Boujenoui (2014) found that the corporate strategy primarily determines the role of risk management in the organisation after studying 110 non-financial Canadian companies. The risks management was further investigated in detail with the help of content analysis. It was declared that the business side of an organisation influences the risk management strategy decisions taken regarding risks and the risk level for all kinds of

individual and collective risk types. This empirical evidence also advocated the use of ERM as an integral part of risk management strategy and culture, and for this purpose this evidence indicated the importance of board's role because corporate strategy developed at the board level determines the pragmatic role of risk management in the company.

2.1.4 ERM as Corporate Framework

ERM is defined to be the process that analyses risk according to the company-wide and integrated operations. This approach allows the alignment of knowledge, people, technology, strategies, and processes to define, consider, and manage risks faced by an organisation, which hinders progress towards its objectives and goals (Wahlstrom and Liff, 2018). ERM makes sure that all risks are clearly defined and understood. After careful evaluation and monitoring, the information related to risks can be effectively used for planning against reward evaluations, capital budgeting, performance, and investments. The main goal of ERM is finding an appropriate channel that will deal with all the individual and corporate risks and organisations might face. Also, ERM makes efforts to integrate risks and risk management activities along with the business' plans and goals so that it can achieve maximum competitive advantages in the market (Deloitte, 2018a).

An organisation with many divisions and a multiple period capital budgeting system is the most suitable for the capital budgeting and enterprise risk management framework. This framework is made as a solution for the leaders and managers of an organisation in which appropriate amounts of resources are allocated to different sectors to complete their dependent and independent tasks and consider strategies for risk management to avoid losses (Yilmaz et al., 2017). After they have figured out solutions to risks, the benefits of the problem-solvers or leaders tend to increase the value of shareholders, which is, one of the goals and objectives of the organisation. In addition, an organisation

can adopt frameworks that allow return relationships, risk margins and allows dependence of various non-linear and linear structures (Giuffrida et al, 2021).

An efficient framework for optimising ERM solutions is therefore created with the help of a visual and intuitive interface developed by a decision tree model. The primary use of decision tree models is in risk management and decision-making strategies that allow contingency planning in case of unexpected risks that an organisation might face (Dyer and Wang, 2012; Glickman, Dalkiran, and Sherali, 2011). In various studies, the strengths and advantages of the decision tree are explained and documented (e.g., Reilly and Clemen, 1999).

Even though there are many fundamental uses of decision trees for making decisions regarding the risks faced by organisations in the industrial sector, it is not most commonly used in financial and risk management related decisions. This is because the size of the tree grows exponentially along with its computational complexity, especially in situations where the organisation has to deal with many sequential problems and unexpected uncertainties. This computational problem can be dealt with, with the help of an innovative form of copula analysis and dimension reduction method (Guo and Zhang, 2015; Sale and Gustafsson, 2005).

All the potential risks are explained in detail in the decision trees and the complete explanation of all the alternatives a leader might follow under such risks and its consequences are described. The statistical technique devised by Dyer and Wang (2012) is used to create a framework that deals with all the issues related to implementing the ERM model and creating a dependent decision tree framework based on copula. According to the model adopted, the nature of the decision tree in the capital budget sector is a state of nature. It deals with both individual and dependent risks that all the organisation's departments and the organisation itself collectively face (Sari et al, 2019).

The dependent tree sector deals with all the potential risks, decisions, investment options and capital constraints of the organisation's cash flow. The decision-maker of

the corporation describes his preferences related to risks used to create innovative risk management solutions and capital budget plans. The significant advantage of the organisation's risk management solutions and its effectiveness for the organisation is gained by the senior executives and board members. Executives should always make sure that their efforts to create risk management solutions bear fruit by providing valuable insight for the strategy creation process. Organisations should also realise the significance of taking risks since they always provide excellent output. Organisations adopt multiple strategies to reduce their risks and enhance their profits. For this, using the ERM process to create an appropriate strategy is crucial (Flouris and Yilmaz, 2017).

ERM is also a fundamental method for planning, solution-making and controlling the organisation. Other than this, ERM is also significant for solving all kinds of financial and non-financial issues of an organisation (Rasid et al., 2014). The top-level management in an organisation deals with the long-term planning, strategies development and reduction of costs. Because of this, they should have a vast knowledge of the ERM practices, which plays an integral part in the decision-making, strategy creation, operations and processes of an organisation (Schmit and Gatzert, 2016; Kaarboe and Meidell, 2017). Many studies suggest that adopting various techniques of ERM can lead to the success of an organisation. For example, it can effectively manage working costs, accurately determine accounting ledgers and determine accounting costs (Collier and Soin, 2013). The top-level management always needs to prepare against any potential risks by effective strategy planning and ERM implementation methods (Tse and Krause, 2016).

The competitive advantage of a firm can be acquired through a variety of approaches; however, enterprise risk management (ERM) strategies are mostly utilised to lower a number of different types of risk and assist businesses in improving their long-term CA. (Elahi 2013; Yang et al., 2018). ERM is an ordered and systematically incorporated approach that manages and deals with risks that an organisation faces. Its main goal is to achieve the organisation's goals by creating and maximising the stakeholders' value (Viscelli et al., 2018). Because of this, ERM does not deal with potential risks that are

damaging for the business but also operational, strategic and financial risks so that the enterprise value enhances. This is shown in the figure below:

Figure 4: ERM Brings Together All Risks,

Source: Beasley et al., (2004).

Assessing and managing the risks that a variety of businesses face in the process of value creation in accordance with an ERM framework or organised approach that integrates corporate strategy, resources, technological advances, and industry expertise (Hoffman, 2009).

2.1.5 Enterprise Risk Management (ERM): Development Stages

As a direct result of the ongoing financial crisis that the world is currently experiencing, "enterprise risk management" has emerged as a prominent new approach to the management of risk for organisations (ERM). It is possible for a company to engage in operations that are both strategic and comprehensive as a means of coping with unpredictability. More than ten years ago, the standard risk management strategy that the vast majority of business managers are already familiar with served as the inspiration for this cutting-edge method of risk management. As a direct consequence of the implementation of this new strategy, traditional approaches to risk management, such as individual risk management and sectorial risk management, have become obsolete. Akintoye and MacLeod (1997) made a seminal contribution to the field of risk management when they proposed that this form of risk management becomes even more limiting when the identified risk may be as precisely defined as affecting the

schedule or cost of a particular operation. In other words, this type of risk management is not very flexible.

According to Stulz, this was frequently the case in the financial industry, where the metric is a monetary statement of risk and reward associated with an investment plan. This was also the case in the past (1996). People, processes, and scopes are all taken into consideration by Barton et al. (2002) as part of their enterprise-wide risk management approach to enterprise risk management. This approach to enterprise risk management focuses on enterprise risk management (ERM).

Researchers believe that because an enterprise-wide risk management plan is integrated throughout an organisation, it is more effective at reducing costs. Therefore, enterprise risk management (ERM) is considered to be more comprehensive in its approach to minimising total risk and hazard, and as a consequence, to increase the value of an organisation by improving efficiency, lowering expenses, and lowering turnover that is unpredictable (Hoyt and Liebenberg, 2003). In some contexts, the term enterprise risk management (ERM) is used interchangeably with the terms comprehensive risk management, integrated risk management, and strategic risk management (Hoyt et al., 2008).

When taking a holistic approach to risk management, it is possible to do so in an integrated fashion; this leads to increased coordination and, as a result, improved decision making for an organisation... ERM is an abbreviation for enterprise risk management, which is a comprehensive strategy developed by Gates and Hexter (2005) for analysing the risks associated with running a business. Enterprise Resource Planning, also known as ERP, has a scope that is significantly broader than that of other management systems, which tend to focus on a single department, project, or process. As can be seen from ERM's definitions and supporting frameworks, the enterprise risk management methodology places a great deal of stringent requirements on an organisation.

According to the definition provided by Bailey et al. (2004), Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) incorporates rigorous and methodical techniques to manage risks

in their entirety. This is abundantly clear from this explanation of ERM. There is coverage of everything, from the tiniest new businesses to the largest conglomerates in the world. In addition to that, it seeks to accomplish the goals of the organisation and to increase the value that the organisation provides to its various stakeholders. Emerging Risk Management (ERM) gradually differentiated itself from Traditional Risk Management (TRM) over the course of its first decade of existence (McShane et al., 2011). Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) takes a holistic approach to managing enterprise risk and uses an integrated analysis method. This is in contrast to traditional risk management, which takes a more traditional approach (Rodriguez and Edwards, 2009).

ERM is perceived to be more of an integrated strategy than a siloed one when it comes to risk management (Gordon et al., 2009). ERM is conceived of as a kind of synthesis of various risk management approaches that are carried out separately from one another. According to ERM, there has been a significant shift in the manner in which businesses deal with risk. Instead of having each department evaluate its own risks and determining how to reduce them, the holistic approach of ERM looks at the entire organisation and identifies and assesses numerous risk variables. This allows ERM to take a more comprehensive approach to risk management (Lin et al., 2011).

The definition of risk management that is provided by COSO (2004) is as follows: Risk management is utilised by the board of directors, management, and other members of an organisation in order to determine the likelihood of events that could have an impact on the company as a whole and to manage risk in a manner that is congruent with the risk appetite of the organisation (COSO, 2004, p.3).

In 2004, for the first time, COSO defined a "Integrated framework for ERM" as an approach that was developed by an organization's directorate, management, as well as additional staff offices, and that was used to identify expected cases that could have an impact on the company's overall strategy and risk appetite, in order to provide fair authority regarding the success of the company. As evidenced by the COSO report from 2004, (p.4). A framework can be thought of as an outline or overview of interconnected aspects (activities) that serves as a guide to help an approach toward achieving a

specific goal be implemented. (COSO, 2004). In 2004, COSO defined the four types of risks that focus on the organization's internal scope as follows: strategic, operational, reporting, and compliance risks. All four of these types of risks are included in the definition. Throughout the entirety of this investigation, references will be made to the opinions offered by COSO (2004) on enterprise risk management (not only the specific risk categories described here).

According to the Global Audit Information Network of the Institute of Internal Auditors and Research Foundation, COSO (2004) is the risk management framework that is utilised by organisations the most frequently (GAIN). Risk management and the suppression of fraudulent activity are two of COSO's primary goals. The ERM Integrated Framework, which was developed by COSO, is a method of risk management that is well-known and frequently utilised. Facilitates a better understanding among executives of the connection between strategy and the performance of their companies, as well as the role that risk management plays at each stage of the process.

In May of that year, the Committee of Sponsoring Organizations for the Treadway Commission (COSO) issued an updated version of its Internal Control—Integrated Framework. The 1992 Framework was retired on December 15, 2014, marking the end of the transition period that had been in effect since it was succeeded by the 2013 Framework. In the process of revising the Internal Control—Integrated Framework, one of COSO's primary goals was to clarify internal control requirements. Other primary goals included addressing changes in business (globalisation, use and dependence on technology, and complexity), and encouraging users to apply internal control in order to monitor additional organisational objectives (COSO, 2013). To have an effective internal control system, each of the five components of internal control as well as the applicable principles need to be present and operational. Additionally, to have an effective control system, each of the five components of internal control need to collaborate with one another in an integrated manner (COSO, 2013).

The 17 COSO principles that are included in the 2013 Framework are connected to the five pillars that make up internal control. The Framework from 1992 contained an underlying assumption of these concepts, but it did not state them explicitly. According

to the 2013 Framework, each of the five components of an internal control system must be present and operational in order to demonstrate that it has been successfully developed and put into practise. By utilising the templates and guidelines provided by the Organization, clients have the ability to conduct an analysis of the organization's Internal Control over Financial Reporting (ICFR) and document their findings.

Even in light of the newly recognised need for such a system, an efficient system of internal control over financial reporting should continue to adhere to the same standards. When evaluating the ICFR in accordance with the COSO (2013) Framework, however, management and internal auditors may find weaknesses in the organization's internal control framework (ICFR). At the conclusion of June 2016, the COSO ERM-Integrated Framework was made available for scrutiny by the general public. Over a thousand business executives and risk managers from different countries contributed to the development of the document that ultimately became the final version. It is possible that the ERM's efficiency will improve even further if the proposed update to the Framework is implemented.

Risk management has emerged as a more pressing concern for board members and executives, who have advocated for improved information as a tool to assist in the process of making strategic decisions. There are a variety of modifications that can be carried out, but the ones that have been discussed here are among the most significant ones (Richtermeyer, 2016).

2.2 Understanding the Concept and Dynamics of Risk Management

A firm faces many risks that can be internal and external, i.e., economic downturn, the unpredictability of the market, competent human resources leaving the firm, changing consumer demand and new legislation or rules being formed by the government (Coleman, 2019). Many risks are related to resources such as strategies not being appropriately implemented (Vessey and Scott, 2012), representation of sunken costs (Wrigley and Clark, 1997), or not being available (Mentzer and Manuj, 2008). In the

same way, every action can lead to multiple risks such as uninformed operations and moral issues (Ferrao, 2008), wrong implementation or misunderstanding due to different situations or asymmetrical information. Because of this, the association between actions and resources is deemed hazardous such as the idea of secondary risks presented by Baker (1997).

Other than this, the people who work or do not work, including bounded rational workers (Simon 1979), or individuals with misconceptions or wrong evaluations related to the particular situation, should also be included. Behavioural risks also include demotivation among staff or unsatisfactory working conditions (Ilardi et al., 1993).

It can be concluded that making a list of all potential risks that an organisation might face due to its strategies is impossible (Wohlgemuth and Burisch, 2016). Because of this, it is identifying and managing all kinds of risks according to their effects and probability is not a practical approach. The same point is discussed in the paper written by Rau and Bromiley (2016).

That is why the portfolio theory is considered a feasible solution (McShae et al., 2012; Mikes, 2009). Another research related to strategic management reveals that classifying multiple risks according to their type to solve them is not a practical solution (Fieberg and Berger, 2016). Rather than categorising the organisation's departments into different sectors, the risks should be differentiated according to their difficulty level, and the most hazardous risks should be dealt with first.

For example, Schmit and Gatzert (2016) think that all risks against reputation and brand image should be given first priority. ERM is the answer given by Schmit and Gatzert to this strategic management concern. Hopkins (2015) in his study has classified the risk structure into four main categories: reputational, financial, marketplace-related, and infrastructural. Even though the concept itself is beneficial, its implementation is complex since it leads to many issues. According to Hopkins, the first step of this process is strategic rather than operational objectives. However, the second step is not precisely determining whether it should be related to strategy or any other department.

Even though categorising risks according to their difficulty level and solving them is helpful, the categorising process for every organisation is different and depends greatly upon their resources (Aven, 2016). The view based on resources describes that a compelling competitive advantage of an organisation depends significantly upon its diversity of resources available. Although all firms have different resources, only a few use them effectively and create a favourable competitive advantage for them in the market.

Such a company's competitive advantage is only beneficial until the idea is copied; it is no longer valid. Having VRIN (Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, Non-Substitutable)-approved resources increases the strategic value. According to the definition, the kit can be a routine, a bundle of practices, a specific ability or competence in various fields (Barney, 1991). On the other hand, ERM analyses all the potential risks related to the organisation or risks due to resources, strategies, and significant competencies that fall under the VRIN criteria (Teece, 2018). These aspects are indicating that risks can have the highest impact on the functioning of business organisations.

In the light of studies conducted in the recent past, it has been deduced that organisations should evaluate their potential risks in a systematic way. VRIN holds prime importance in this regard since they are the ones that gain profits for businesses in the market. This aspect is also reaffirmed by Spiking (2013, p.99), as he concluded that it is the business risks that benefit the businesses and return value to the organisations.

Rau and Bromiley, (2016) discovered that one business risk carries almost one hundred and twenty-eight different managerial considerations. So, mathematically, organisations have multiple one hundred and twenty-eight with an undetermined number of potential risks. For this, the view based on resources is used to eliminate any potential risks and hazards that the organisation might face at an early stage. It also provides a framework with unrealistic expectations for effective risk management. Since the firm's survival depends entirely upon the core competencies, removing risks threatening those should always be the priority (Hamel and Prahalad, 1990). From the number of risk

management methods, choosing the most effective way is made with the approach proposed, i.e., ERM.

All the risks that concern the core competencies should either be eradicated or reduced to the lowest degree. On the other hand, other risks that do not affect the core competencies but still have a high probability level should also be dealt with attention.

Link with Information Flow and Decision Making

Risk management is one of the main components of business strategy and it is implemented so that all kinds of potential risks and their effects can be reduced or finished to survive in the market (Chakabah et al, 2021). The effects of the risk management process can be easily enhanced with the help of integrated risk management procedures such as the effective implementation of ERM. The main aim of the ERM process is to create a system or functions within an organisation that helps it tackle all kinds of potential risks and their effects and increase business profits (Liebenberg and Hoyt, 2011).

So, one of the main objectives of the ERM process is enhancing and creating value. All kinds of risks and rewards are obtained due to decisions regarding organisations and their operations; the decision-makers always know first what kind of rewards they will receive.

The risk management procedure allows the management to make intelligent and effective decisions related to decision-making, strategy and planning while dealing with the organisation's daily operations (Gorzen-Mitka, 2019). The process ensures that the organisation achieves its objectives, has optimum performance and the stakeholders achieve their total value. The risk management process is valuable since it provides practical, reliable, timely and current information about the potential risks that may prevent its success (Lima et al, 2020). Flawed decisions can be made by decision-makers who are influential. Such imperfect choices can be made for various reasons, such as a reduced capacity to offer others corrective feedback in their decision-making

process or to fail to expose errors and rectify decisions. This decision-making process can also be improvised as long as group members are encouraged to debate and challenge their peers for better comprehension. All conflicts are heard and well understood. When debates and conflicts catch fire, decision-making authorities indulge in a deliberative process to distance both conflicted parties. Once made, they rightfully make decisions and submit them to higher governance hierarchies for cross-checking and approval (Yoost, 2016).

One of the tiers which play an essential role in this decision-making process is known as risk management. Downside Risks associate a decision after institutionalising how its information is presented. An executive or a risk management officer can facilitate and give such vital information to aid the decision-making procedure. (Scandizzo, 2016).

Figure 5: How to Communicate Risks Using Heat Maps

Source: Association of International Certified Professional Accountants, (2019)

2.2.1 Risk Classification

For business risks, Dey (2009) says that they can be "internal" or "external," depending on whether they arise from within the organisation or from the rest of society. Classifying risks by compartmentalization, rather than individual risks, is a recommendation from the Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of Treadway Commission (COSO 2004).

Another way to categorise "risk" is to say that it is either avoidable or unavoidable (Coyle, 2004). To maximise the wealth of its shareholders, an organization's ultimate goal is always clouded by risk and opportunity (Liu, 2011).

Consider hazards on several levels, including the corporate, division, subsidiary and/or business unit level. Multi-level risk identification is the term for this (COSO, 2004). World Economic Forum (WEF) categorises systemic risks into economic, geopolitical, environmental and sociological concerns (WEF). For the sake of this study, all of these categories are relevant and will be discussed multiple times in this report. Mehr and Hedges (1963) outlined a five-step process for building the risk management process:

- Identifying the risks of loss;
- The measurement of the exposures.
- The comparison of several risk management methods;
- deciding on the best approach; and
- Keeping tabs on the results(D'Arcy and Brogan, 2001).

Conventional risk management is based on the techniques indicated above. At this point, the primary goal of these steps is to reduce the likelihood of negative things happening. When the notion of risk management was initially coined, most businesses did not have to worry about inflation or fluctuating interest or currency rates. Financial concerns were not viewed as a big threat by business owners. During the early 1970s, a global domino effect occurred as oil prices surged and output decreased, resulting in unpredictable and unstable interest rates (D'Arcy and Brogan, 2001). Some major economic changes began to take place during this time. Insurers began using risk

management as a tool to protect themselves against financial setbacks, earnings instability, and other unpleasant surprises.

To help individuals who want to strengthen current systems and ensure regulatory compliance in the event of financial, geopolitical, or climatic instability, this tool was created (Doherty, 1985; Dickinson, 2001).

2.2.2 Leadership at the top and Risk Management Culture

The 21st-century organisations face market complexities and uncertain circumstances owing to increased dynamic internal and external forces (Deloitte, 2019). Regardless of the impacts of a riskous atmospheric devotion, advancements in distributed computing, web-based media or political change and the potential for less liberal exchanging conditions, the quantity of manners by which associations can entangle appears to expand (FSB, 2014). Picking the 'protected' choice can be a hazardous system in itself, as shown by organisations, especially IBM and Kodak. These companies, despite building up the computerised cameras, decided not to showcase it. Corporate administration codes and norms are likewise evolving. A significant amendment of the COSO Enterprise Risk Management Guidance was finished back in 2017 in the US (COSO, 2017). However, amendments to the Corporate Governance Code were delivered for discussion later in the year-end of Dec 2017 in the UK (FRC, 2017). The two cases talked of a closer connection between essential administration, and risk of executives' jobs of the board were both proposed. Significant obligation regarding ERM begins at the top (Schmid, Sabato and Aebi, 2015).

Nonetheless, every individual who matters inside an organisation should partake in the ERM cycle (Salz, 2013). Part of the board's responsibility is to oversee the organisation's technique and execution. Taking care of this high-risk sector is an essential aspect of any project. An assessment of the system's risk consequences, an

investigation of hazard potential, and a determination of the organization's location of risk are all done in this manner (Lubojanski and Sheedy, 2018).

For ERM, top executives are held to the highest standards. This group includes the Chief Risk Officer, the Chief Financial Officer, the Chief Legal Officer, and the Chief Audit Executive. The Enterprise Resource Management cycle is most effective when all of the organization's most critical administrators participate (Wisniewski and Stark, 2019).

The COSO Enterprise Risk Management structure expresses that the director of the organisation "supports the entity's risk management philosophy, promotes compliance with its risk appetite, and manages risks within their respective spheres of responsibility consistent with risk tolerances" (COSO, 2017). Consequently, recognising pioneers across different levels of the company and acquiring their help is fundamental to the fruitful execution of Enterprise Risk Management. This possibly can only happen when executing objectives are plainly expressed, and the fitting people are considered responsible for results. The COSO structure defines that the CEO "is, at last, capable and ought to accept proprietorship" over the usage of Enterprise Risk Management. Since Enterprise Risk Management, as COSO characterised it, is fundamental to running and dealing with a business, the CEO's contribution is essential to the accomplishment of Enterprise Resource Management (McConnell, 2017; Gordon et al., 2015; COSO, 2018; Li et al., 2014; Arab and Mardessi, 2018; Iswajuni et al., 2018).

Culture involving risk and managing vulnerability are fundamental pieces of corporate risk (Vashishtha and Armstrong, 2012; Smolarek and Sipa, 2015; Smolarek and Sipa, 2015; Slavecik and Kubenka, 2016; Kosmala-Wieczorek, 2017; Mitka-Gorzen, 2015; Palermo et al., 2017, Griffin and Sheedy, 2015; Banks, 2012; Palermo et al., 2017; Moeller, 2007; Lams, 2003). A number of researchers have looked into the relationship between ERM's efficiency and the culture of organisations. In an ERM geared at the accomplishment of long-term goals, Keith et al. highlighted the role of culture as an important factor (2013). If risk management is going to be effective, the culture of an

organisation needs to encourage an openness to and acceptance of uncertainty in all of its features and procedures.

Because of the operative risk culture, the value that is created as a result of ERM contributes to an improvement in the long-term viability and competitiveness of a business (KPMG, 2011; Paape and Spekle, 2012; Keith et al., 2013). A straightforward goal cannot produce the kind of atmosphere that is necessary for the success of a company. The ERM literature does not contain enough studies on the topic of risk culture in the context of risk management and the adaptation process that organisations employ for both their external and internal settings, despite the widespread belief to the contrary. This is a significant gap in the research in this area (Hindson, 2013).

It is impossible to maximise shareholder value without a supporting corporate culture, which is important to a successful ERM implementation. Moreover, a good ERM implementation is essential to maximising shareholder value (Chapman, 2007). Greater risk awareness and knowledge dissemination are two of the defining characteristics of a culture that is risk conscious (Brooks, 2010). The fact that this was acknowledged in some of the ERM literature despite the fact that it was completely ignored in other research investigations.

2.2.3 Business Ownership and its Types

Since this research is focused on business firms in a particular country that belongs to two different industries. This reflects that the business firms can have different nature of ownership which can help in interpreting and understanding the results appropriately in line with the research objectives (Goyal et al, 2019). Therefore, it becomes important to define and understand the types of business ownership that exists in the business world. Individuals can run their business with the help of three different modes: sole trader, partnership or private limited organisation. The business offering franchises or being a public company depends on how it grows. When one main person runs the business and has hired workers for help, he/ she runs a sole trader (La Porta et al., 1999). Sole traders often provide services such as photographers, hairstylists or

plumbers. The most basic model is the sole trade ownership, where a single individual manages the business operations. No legal element differentiates the owner from the business; therefore, all the functions and debts of the company are the responsibility of the owner himself (Quinn et al., 2020).

In partnership, two or more people work together as owners of the business. There are two main types of partnership, i.e., Limited and General Partnerships. In Limited Partnership, one of the owners has no personal responsibility related to the business's debts. On the other hand, in a General Partnership, all the owners have equal responsibilities in the business, similar to Sole Proprietorship).

Despite the various types, the partnership is the simpler form of business ownership where the duties are shared, has to faceless government rules and, like sole ownership, have to pay taxes only once (Liguori, 2021).

The additional advantage of being part of a partnered business is additional information and knowledge because more than one owner is present. Despite this, there are disadvantages, including splitting profits between owners and a possibility of clashes occurring between them regarding operations (Stubbs, 2019). This mode of business operations is only beneficial in starting the business procedure in which many people are included.

This business model has more potential for growth than sole ownership because of maximum resources and sharing of benefits (Marian and Belvet, 2013). Compared to the previous two modes of business, corporations have a type of ownership that has a legal element distinct from their owners. Even though the owners enjoy limited liability and responsibilities, they have to pay extra taxes on profits, including corporate income tax and personal income taxes. However, corporations can make more profit than sole owners since they have many funding methods, e.g., selling stocks. The corporations are also made to follow several government regulations, such as detailed documentation of all the business operations. Also, establishing a corporation has many

challenging jobs, such as gaining more capital resources to cover expenses or create legal documents (Vaughan and Arsneault, 2018).

Only individuals who want limited liability and are owners of mature and rapidly growing organisations can adopt this mode of ownership (Skripak, 2016). The decisions of a company are either made by the stakeholders or the Director. Even though shareholders are mostly directors of a business, isolating the decisions being made is essential. The directors make decisions for managing the company while shareholders make decisions as to the business owners. In the initial stages of a business, shareholders and directors have friendly relations, and thus, no clashes arise while making decisions.

However, in the later stages, disparities start to appear, leading to various problems in the company. Therefore, for the smooth running of the business, it is essential that the decision-making process is clearly defined in the company's constitution (Stockder, 2019).

The directors are responsible for making decisions regarding the daily operations of a company. On the other hand, the board of directors make many important decisions regarding the future of the company (Steens et al, 2020). An example is that the board of directors can change the permanent address of the company at any time they want. The directors' decision-making process rules are mentioned initially in the article of association of the company. They include many points such as voting rights and meeting regulations. Suppose the directors decide with the help of meeting with the board of directors rather than a simple written agreement. In that case, it has to follow some procedural laws mentioned in the company's article of association (Merchant and Stede, 2017). Most small businesses opt for the partnership model of ownership since using gathered resources and investment from various individuals interested in the same kind of business proves to be more efficient. Even though the initial framework of partnership is simple, it becomes complicated with the growth of the company. Also, the

framework and structure of the business significantly affect the smooth functioning of the business operations (Ward and Aronoff, 2016).

2.3 Understanding the concept of Decision-making

Decisions are an integral part of success, and sometimes decision-makers face situations that are pressurising, confusing and difficult to handle (Radzi et al, 2021). The decision-makers do not just want to make the right decisions, and they have to make the right decisions. In some cases, not deciding at the right time has worse consequences than making an incorrect decision (Anwar, 2014). According to the definition of decision-making, it is the ability to study all the possible options and then choosing the best out of them to achieve your goals.

It is mainly regarded as a part of the cognitive study since many logical and mental reasoning is needed (Ahmed et al., 2012). It can also be defined as an action that managers and professionals take to deal with a particular situation after choosing the course of the plan. Its primary purpose is to achieve the set goals and objectives (Massie, 2009).

According to Bruce and Scott (1995), the decision-making process is a learned response of a person who shows it while facing an unexpected situation or crisis. Tolliver, Gifford and Behling (1980) suggested that the decision-making style is different for different people according to their thinking patterns. A person who collects information without a solid plan is said to be 'feeling' like information evaluators. On the other hand, the people who collect information analytically are said to be 'thinking' like information evaluators. Harren (1979) has categorised the decision-making style of leaders into two main types based on how they gather and evaluate information: rational and intuitive. As a result, decision-makers are classified as people who are either always reasonable or intuitive when collecting and evaluating information.

2.3.1 Prominent Decision-Making Styles

Intuitive Decision-Making Style: intuition denotes "a vague feeling" or "sense of feeling of pattern or relationships". It is also referred to as "holistic thinking, immediate insight, seeing the answer without knowing how it was reached" (Thorne, 1990), or as "a technique of swiftly retrieving hunks and forms of knowledge moulded from previous experience" (Seal, 1990). The decision-makers are good at connecting facts by using their gut feeling, patterns and things happening around them. Intuition is defined as the abrupt realisation of helpful information (Sauter, 1999; Dijksterhuis and Ritter, 2014). The decision-makers and leaders use their intuition to connect data with facts without really knowing the reason for their existence.

According to Volz, Horr, Bolte and Zander, (2016) initiation can be explained as the "unconscious thought is a process wherein disorganised information becomes more and more organised until some kind of threshold is reached, and conclusions can be transferred to consciousness." As a result, it leads to enhanced personal and collective performance of the organisation.

According to Sauter (1999), there are many ways with which a decision-maker can create intuition. Detection: The mind shows verified pieces of information that can be used to solve the problem. Evaluation: this is influenced by the natural conflict between feelings and emotions (Sauter, 1999; Hidgetts et al., 2017). Some studies say that intuition is used in decision making by following two main steps, i.e., by using feelings to make a definitive decision; by using past experiences to make an implicit decision (Cleereman, Destrebecqz and Bierman, 2005). According to Patton (2003), the decision-makers use three primary intuition sources: the process of natural learning and experiences as you age, known as the general experience, the natural survival instincts that people show due to unexpected situations. This is not learned and is known as an innate response; the learning process involves developing new habits that can be used to improve oneself, also known as focused learning. Kuzey, Gonsel, Bayyurt and

Acikgoz (2014) discovered that intuition leads to improved performance and a high rate of organisational success.

Rational Decision-Making Style: This makes all the decision-makers and leaders liable for considering different kinds of alternative solutions and probabilities for each of their decisions (Oliveira, 2007; Spicer and Busari, 2015). According to Sharfman and Dean (1993), The term "rationality" refers to a process of making decisions that involves acquiring pertinent information and depending on the analysis of this information in order to arrive at a choice that is informed." The rational decision-making process involves the systematic study of facts and a controlled procedure, which takes a lot of time and hard work (Kremer, Mohammad and Fitzgerald, 2017). The decision-makers use rational processes to develop a suitable decision criterion, plan alternative solutions, and manage each alternative solution (Reimann, Kreft, Ehrgott and Kaufmann, 2012).

The rational decision-making method makes sure to evaluate all possible decision choices and deeply assess them to know their consequences compared to the intuitive decision-making strategy (Tetlock et al., 1993; Baird, 1989). The rational decision-making methodology makes the decision-makers study all of their available options carefully, including their risks and consequences. This process is thoughtful, carefully evaluated, and free from irrationality and superstitions, proving it to be the more enhanced decision-making style (Epstein and Pacini, 1999). It also shows more effective organisational performance and operational success (Uzelac et al., 2016; Singh, 2014; Spicer and Busari, 2015; Smolka et al., 2016).

All the decision-making process steps are based on the complete decision-making procedure (Holsapple, 1995) and knowledge management skills (Nicolas, 2004). Practically speaking, all the practitioners assess and evaluate the complete available information to reach a conclusive decision. Because of this, the rational decision-making procedure is responsible for establishing relations between the organisation's performance and knowledge management process. The intuitive decision-making

procedure is responsible for the knowledge development procedure and performance. It has been studied that a person's information processing abilities are dependent on their mental skills (Simon, 1976; Ariely, 2010) and the inherent distribution of neural matter (Tranel et al., 1994; Kahneman, 2011). According to Herbert Simon, human behaviour is primarily intentional rather than rational in business-related matters (Simon, 1976). Many scholars have approved this study, all of whom state that such intuition instructions complicate the information processing process (Tranel et al., 1994).

Based on Simon's observations, scholars (Klein et al., 2002; Klein, 1998a; Klein, 1998b; Klein, 1998) showed that most decision-makers follow their feelings and opinions to make effective decisions regarding the concerning situations. The intuitions and experiences gained by dealing with similar situations have led to rapidly making decisions regarding specific conditions. In the intuitive decision-making procedure, feelings are given more importance than rational thinking based on facts (Wray, 2017). It is a haphazard and random mode of making decisions that use the related information available (Kiyani, Khan, Mughal, Busari and Rasool, 2017). This allows freedom from extensive systematic procedures and logical calculations and gives time and energy to deal with other tasks at hand (Klein and Kahneman, 2009; Kahneman, 2003).

2.3.2 ERM and Decision-Making

The ERM process involves decision making for all the individual and collective sectors of an organisation. The risk management process especially has a vital role in the decision-making procedure since it is related to the other functions of an organisation, such as assets-liability matching, capital budgeting, etc., through dependent and shared risks and collective relations with the business framework (Mukhtar and Soliman, 2017). With the increase in the organisation's size, the complications and interactions between the various functions increase. This increase in exchange means that no department is a silo. The more complicated the corporate structure of an organisation is, the more chances there are that it will face a hazardous breakdown.

This is proved by the financial service corporation AIG during the economic catastrophe where the potential risks of the Financial Products department impacted other areas, and ultimately, the effects were felt by the top-level of the organisation's management. One of the primary goals of the ERM process is to enhance the value of organisations by helping with the decision making for all the complicated risks (cf. COSO, 2004). According to this study, the ERM process uses a decision tree based on the copula model and an optimisation framework to create a flexible structure for handling risks. ERM has dramatically grown in the last few years with the help of rating agencies such as SandP's ERM ratings since 2006 and regulatory forces such as the Sarbanes-Oxley Act, 2002 (Deloitte, 2012).

In 2013, RIMS Enterprise Risk Management surveyed more than 1000 professionals and found out that almost 20 per cent had completely incorporated ERM in their firms, while nearly 42 per cent had partially incorporated this. The total rate was 63 per cent, which was double as compared to the survey of 2009 (RIMS, 2013). The economic institutions more commonly use the ERM processes, and it is spreading.

An example will be NAIC's new monitoring policy, "Own Risk and Solvency Assessment (ORSA)," which ensures that the ERM strategy is being normalised within all the organisations. Many advantages of incorporated risk management have been explained (Grace et al., 2015; Warr and Pagach, 2011; Warr, Pagach and Beasley, 2008; Liebenberg and Hoyt, 2011; Yu, Wen and Lin, 2012). If any of the risk managers are interested, they can consult the study of Martin and Gatzert (2015). Even though the risk management process deals with the corporate level and is incorporated with other operational functions given the dependencies. However, the real test of using ERM to implement corporation decision-making process has not yet been dealt with properly (Kolb and Gatzert, 2014; Yu, Wen and Lin, 2012; Ai et al., 2012; MacMinn, 1987). The influential studies by Froot (2007, Stein and Froot (1998) and Stein, Scharfstein and Froot (1993) is used to solving this issue by integrating all the corporate operations into a single ERM decision framework.

Many studies have been implemented that connected firm value to ERM and showed unpredictable conclusions. Studies conducted by Razali and Tahir, (2011) and Liebenberg and Hoyt (2011) have explained the impact of firm value and ERM. According to Liebenberg and Hoyt (2011), there is a main positive effect between firm value and ERM, while Razali and Tahir (2011) say otherwise. The quality of risk management processes can be enhanced through the incorporated risk management that is achieved through the application of ERM.

Some studies state that ERM is responsible for identifying and evaluating different risks, incorporating all of these risks and then coordinating the risk management activities to all the functional sectors within the firm. This practice is different from the traditional practices, where each industry identifies the risks related to its departments and solves them independently (Lin et al., 2012). ERM is a procedure that works under different employers, including directors, board members and management, all responsible for managing the organisation. They work together to discover potential risks, manage them, and motivate them to achieve the organisation's objectives (Moeller, 2009). In theory, the integrated risk management approach can use many ways to enhance firm value.

They can start by identifying all the risk factors and developing an adequate risk portfolio for their organisation. Next, the organisation should classify the risks factors based on their individual needs with ERM (Lin et al., 2012). Besides this, ERM can help firms run their business operations smoothly with ample measurable risk (Sugiarti and Widjaya, 2013). Because of this, integrated ERM implementation is necessary so that the firm is ready to face any kinds of risks in the future.

Role of Dependence Modelling

An integral part of the creation of the ERM decision-making procedures is dependence modelling. Risks are mostly known as 'silos' in the traditional risk management procedures, overseeing all feasible dependencies and allowing the enhancement of the performance of the whole organisation. Oberstedt stated clearly (2013, p. 54), "The

decision to implement ERM is partly driven by the recognition that risks are interrelated and interdependent". Relying on the traditional approach of managing individual risks separately in their risk silos tends too often lead to severe and systematic errors in risk identification and assessment." Many studies have proved that ignoring dependencies cause issues with the firm's crucial strategies, leading to significant consequences if the positive dependency is high. However, many computing complexities are the main reason why these dependencies are ignored, as stated by Butler, Dyer and Wang (2015), Ai et al. (2012), Winkler and Tsetlin (2005), Straumann, McNeil and Embrechts (2002), Gollier (2011) and Evans, Ryan and Smith (1992). The primary dependency modelling is integrated with the optimised risk management and decision-making structure with the help of a measure based on copula strategy.

The Incorporated Organizational ERM Decision Framework

It is said that the firm's objective of providing maximum value to the shareholders can be achieved by the decision-makers when they find solutions to the problems faced by the organisation (Engemann, 2019). The copula dependence modelling strategy is used for allowing a large margin for risks and return relationships.

It also enables the creation of different non-linear and linear dependencies. A practical and optimised ERM decision model can be created with the help of a visual and intuitive interface by the decision tree model. Decision tree models are used to identify and analyse risks and decisions to make effective strategies in uncertain risks (Dyer and Wang, 2012; Glickman, Dalikran and Sherali, 2011; Reilly and Clemen, 1999). The advantages and sturdiness of the decision tree strategies are documented and explained in various studies, e. g, by Reilly and Clemen, 1999). even though the decision trees are an essential analysis tool in the industrial sector, they are not commonly used in economic decision making and firm's risks management processes. This is because of the rapidly growing size of the tree, its enhanced complexity, and

several resources such as sequential decisions and dependent doubts. This complex issue can be dealt with the help of the copula analysis method and a dimension reduction strategy (Salo and Gustafsson, 2005). An effective decision tree is made only when all the risk factors are explained in detail and the alternative solutions a leader might make. It also includes the results of all such decisions made against risks.

To make an effective model that will deal with all the issues the ERM implementation might bring, the statistical method of Dyer and Wang (2012) is used, which formulates a dependency tree based on copula strategy. This model allows the dependent state of nature to capture all risk dependencies of capital budgeting, reflecting the specific risks and relationships across time and business sectors. Another factor of the decision tree is cash flow which depends upon capital limitations, investment prospects, decisions and risks. The choice of the decision maker's risks is summarised with a utility function used to plan ERM and capital budgeting strategies.

Supervision of Enterprise Risks by Board Members

All the international regulators have created new revelation regulations that deal with how the board members should monitor the risk management procedures after the GFC incident (Ontario Securities Commission 2010; Securities and Exchange Commission 2010; The Conference Board 2005).

Because of this, the number of organisations adopting ERM increased exponentially across multiple industries to improve risk management strategies. Tonello (2007) described the importance of the ERM oversight role of the board members responsible for creating a detailed explanation of all the individual steps of the ERM process development and implementation. Based on the result of these studies, Dublon and Barnes (2012) discovered that the board members and management should cooperate for finding out which kind of risks holds critical importance. Moreover, considering the interdepartmental relationships, embedding the enterprise risk management culture in

the firm was also deemed necessary, i.e., for describing results of the risks and actions taken.

The organisation's performance can drastically improve if the communication between management and board members regarding risk management is enhanced (Dublon and Branes, 2008). A survey by COSO (2010a) discovered that less than 30 per cent of organisations consider their ERM execution to be repeatable, forceful and organised after collaboration with the board members. In contrast, almost 60 per cent of organisations believed their partnership with the board members was purely makeshift and with more room for improvement (Leech 2012).

ERM should be considered the crucial point of concern for all organisations since its primary goal is to develop, protect, and increase shareholders' value (Berenbeim, 2005; Barton et al., 2001). Barton et al., 2001 collected information through several interviews and concluded that the board members should regularly discuss potential risk factors and know the board members' business, market, and capabilities. In addition, they should document all the board risk observations, do training for effective ERM and create good relations between C-suite and board. Since the ineffective monitoring of board members has been a potential risk for a long time in the market, studies declare that the inclusion of board members in the ERM process is simply for show and has little impact (Barton et al. 2008b).

Also, Bates (2009) states that the implementation of ERM should start at the highest hierarchy level and then be handed down systematically. Branson (2010) and Beasley (2011) have emphasised the importance of risk monitoring and meetings among the board members and the management. Branson (2012) emphasises the role of the board members of an organisation and how important it is for proper communication between management and board members. On the other hand, Beasley (2011) tells us the importance of risk monitoring and its difference from risk management.

Branson (2010) talks about the significance of identifying potential risks and their effects which includes enhancing ERM's efficiency, managing risks effectively and dealing with core risks that can be reduced before they get out of hand. According to Branson (2010), top-level ERM monitoring is one of the main functions of the board members. On the other hand, Beasley (2011) believes that the board's primary function is to understand and monitor the potential risks and the risk management strategies. Also, to be proactively involved in the risk management procedures, the board should constantly contact the management to know about the status of ERM strategies. Beasley (2011) also states that active involvement of board members would allow them to see when the ERM strategies are effective enough to deal with financial risks and deal with the overall risks that an organisation might face. The board members can efficiently decide which risk factors can cause more detrimental effects to the organisation. Because of this, the information about risks and risk tolerance should be detailed and clear enough to remove silo reporting (Lattimore and Mylrea 2010).

Effective communication and proper integration of risk management strategies are necessary to deal with all the potential risks (Beasley, 2011). An essential responsibility of the board members should be to enhance risk monitoring to determine beforehand which potential risks can jeopardise the organisation's goals and objectives. They should also make sure that the risk managers and planners get the organisation's deserved attention.

This means that they should be notified about all the changes in strategy development and implementation procedures (Beasley, 2011; Newfrock and Kocourek, 2006). Many studies have proved that the role of board members in risk management and risk monitoring procedures is essential for all firms (Barton et al., 2008b).

Their roles also extend to providing valuable suggestions and knowledge and overseeing risk management procedures that will help in identifying and resolving risks (Dublon and Barnes, 2008). If, by any chance, a core risk is overlooked during the risk management, it will have an intense detrimental effect on the whole ERM process. This

portion of the ERM process needs the most care during research. As a consequence of this, even if the board members are the ones who are responsible for managing ERM, all of the employees should be aware of the commercial or economic risks that could lead to personal benefit or corruption in the financial sector (Tonello, 2007). The board of directors needs to be aware of the procedures that senior management uses to identify events and the parameters of those procedures. As a consequence of this, it will be able to critically evaluate the results of their actions and give more efficient risk oversight.

2.3.3 The rational model of Decision Making

Bounded rationality model

In this model, the decision-maker can obtain perfect information, determine every outcome, be aware of all alternatives, and develop a preference scale. Furthermore, as part of the stages of decision-making, decision-making will consistently result in choosing the alternatives that provide maximum solutions to the issues that require a decision. Decision-makers are often unaware of the existence of the challenge. Even when they are aware, they do not strive for possible solutions to the problem as they face cost, time and ability to process information limitations. Therefore, they use a partial alternative solution for the problems depending on their intuition, advice from others, creative ideas, and their experiences.

Thus, rationality is limited. The term bounded rationality is introduced by Herbert Simon (1997, 1982, and 2009); he described that normally the decision-makers who want to make the best decision settle on the less than the best solution. Bounded rationality involves the following:

To complete the rationality is the process of making a decision (Simon, 1979): 1) The findings will always be taken based on incomplete knowledge of the true nature of the problem to be solved. 2) The decision-makers will never find a possible alternative solution for the problem. 3) It is not possible to completely predict the outcomes of each

alternative, so the alternatives cannot be evaluated completely. 4) A criterion for choosing the alternative must be set other than optimisation or maximisation as it cannot be predicted which alternative is best. The process-oriented view 'satisficing' is primarily based on the work of Simon (1979) related to bounded rationality and admits that the rational organisational manager does not always have perfect information, and there is no need for optimal choices every time.

As per the findings of Simon (as quoted by Chase et al. (1998), "rational human behaviour is shaped by scissors whose two blades are the structure of task environments and the computational capabilities of the actor." The problem space is cut into smaller parts by these scissors, which are easy to search. The activities such as satisficing and exploring are included in bounded rationality.

Alternatives are searched and evaluated in a sequence. If the option satisfies the particular external or internal minimum stated criteria, then this is known as 'satisfice', and the research gets terminated. The identification of consistency in the task environment can make the searching process easy. Though he was acclaimed prominently for the bounded rationality theory, this still explains rational behaviour (albeit constrained). However, many researchers like Teng and Das (1999) and Huber (1981) have not differentiated the bounded and perfect rationality in their decision-making models.

2.3.4 Factors Influencing Decision Making

Decisions are mostly affected by a person's past experiences and the outcomes are what is expected from the future (Secundo et al, 2021). Because of this, decisions are considered as a procedure with specific and rationalised choosing. The decision-making process involves choosing from several choices, and each option has its considerations. Some of them include subjective and objective factors, rational regulations, etc. Other factors that influence the decision-making process are belief in particular importance, personal differences such as social status and age, levels of commitment, levels of

optimism, different biases, past experiences, etc. Such factors play an essential role in determining the decision-making procedure. High commitment, trust in individual significance (Krueger and Acevedo, 2004), social and age differences (Fischhoff, Parker, Bruin, 2007), in-built prejudices (West and Stanovich, 2008), and previous happenings (Garling, Karlsson and Juliusson, 2005) significantly affect the priorities of people.

Understanding the choices made is the first step of understanding the decisions that people have taken. Thus, the factors influencing the decision made may play an essential role in the output. Heuristics is an effective and satisfactory decision-making framework (Oppenheimer and Shah, 2008). There have been attempts to explain the decision-making process with different heuristics. To make sure that less time and energy is spent on decision making, people are always looking for solutions, and heuristics offer these services by providing instructions that can be followed to decrease the effort invested in the process. The factors affecting the decision-making process and heuristics together are essential components of critical thinking (Stanovich, Toplak and West, 2008). Some studies state that decision making is a process that can be learned, so people can gradually make better decisions and solve issues in unexpected situations (Hacker and Nokes, 2007). Previous experiences play a huge role in influencing the decisions made. Garling, Karlsson and Juliusson (2005) state that the earlier experiences broadly impact the decision-making process.

It can be understood that if a decision generates a positive outcome, people tend to reference it for future situations. Similarly, individuals do not repeat their mistakes (Friedland and Sagi, 2007). Decisions made influenced by past experiences cannot always be the right decisions.

An example can be seen in the financial sector where the decisions are made while analysing the circumstances rather than being affected by the past. Thus, this theory can have many sides (Juliusson et al., 2005). Other than previous experiences, personal prejudices also affect the decision-making process. Cognitive biases are thinking styles influenced by observations and hypotheses about situations that result in

wrong logic, faulty judgements and memory mistakes (Stanovich, Toplak and West, 2008; Pollard, Barston and Evans, 1983).

The types of cognitive prejudices include confirmation biases: people noticing situations that are suitable for them, omission biases: individuals removing any knowledge that any prove harmful to them, hindsight biases: people thinking of situations as inevitable once they have occurred; and belief biases: complete dependence on previous experiences and information while making decisions (West and Stanovich, 2008; Von Collani and Nestler, 2008; Hanlon and Marsh, 2007). Cognitive prejudices are risky since they make people decide based on their previous experiences and gain information without accepting the unknown territories or looking at the whole scenario properly.

Even though this process can be a harmful aspect of decision making, people use heuristics to make proper and effective decisions (Oppenheimer and Shah, 2008). A crucial factor that determines the effectiveness of the decision made is the leader's personality. The information about the leader, such as his family background, information and education, can play a huge role as the sub-base of the individual portion of the decision-making procedure. Even though these factors are similar in one way or another, the leaders usually are different from each other anyway. This difference is caused by the personality of the leader (Kurt, 2013).

The decisions are influenced by the in-built, psychological and moral abilities of an individual. Massie (1971) states that a rational decision can be defined as the mental ability of a person and logically followed processes. However, some subconscious and emotional parts can influence a decision unconsciously, which makes others think that this decision was made irrationally. Similarly, Onaran (1971) has stated that the psychological abilities of a person, such as associations, interpersonal interactions, comprehension, motivation, and perceptions, greatly influence the decisions being made. The perception of an individual plays a crucial part as one of the decision-making procedure's mental constituents, including evaluation and conceptualisation.

2.4 Theoretical Frames and Perspectives (Informing Framework)

2.4.1 COSO Framework

The WBCSD (World Business Council for Sustainable Development) and the COSO (Committee of Sponsoring Organisations of the Treadway Commission) together develop the final form of "Guidance for Applying Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) to Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG)-related Risks". These instructions support mainstream organisations and other businesses globally by clearing the risks and opportunities brought by ESG and have been greatly analysed by the public. The main goal of this framework is to increase the flexibility of the organisations that have to face multiple potential ESG risks that include extreme weather problems, regulations of product safety and so on. These instructions have been made to integrate Strategy and Performance with Enterprise Risk Management (ERM). The ERM process is used by firms internationally for managing all the potential risks and their effects that a business might face (World Business Council for Sustainable Development, 2019).

The Guidance to ERM process by COSO is expected to have a significant influence. The individuals who know the importance of COSO can agree that this will prove to be a practical step in speeding the businesses' transitions to a more resourceful environment," as said by the CEO and president of WBCSD, 2019.

He also added that "When organisations have a better grip on their risk management, they can make better decisions that will influence better results. He also promised that this would positively impact corporate governance internationally (WBCSD, 2019). Since the external and internal business environment has changed with time regarding the risk management done by the organisations, many risk management frameworks and standards have also changed drastically.

The ERM processes of each organisation are different from each other because of unique business goals, strategic methods and corporate frameworks (Mikes 2009a). That is why financial sectors need to be careful about changing the ERM process according to their needs, size, industry, abilities, management methodology and culture rather than using a standard risk management process. This section deals with some of the internationally successful ERM frameworks, which include New Zealand/Australia Standard 4360 – Risk Management (New Zealand 2004), ISO (International Organization for Standardisation) 31000:2009, 2009 and COSO (2013; 2004; 1992).

The creation of different US risk management strategies and guidelines, and the financial and accounting associations in the United States that were worried about false accounting reports in the 1980s united to create COSO (Committee of Sponsoring Organisations of the Treadway Commission). They released a study on internal control management in 1992 (Power, 2009). They provided a basis of the main components of the ERM framework by COSO, which explained the direct effect of a financial conception on internal control.

The ERM process is considered the best risk management template internationally, even though it strongly influences auditing and financial control (Power, 2007; Moeller, 2007; Kahn-Samed, 2005). The COSO (2004) framework was defined as a procedure that is "applied in strategy setting across the enterprise" and "designed to identify potential events that may affect the entity and manage risks to be within its risk appetite to provide reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of entity objectives" (COSO 2004, p.2). According to this definition, ERM cannot be operational in a restructured environment.

It worked well under the management of several stakeholders since it is used to protect both the firm's goals and shareholders' value (Branson, 2010). The international business community has transitioned through several changes in the strategic and functional sectors of the organisation. There has been an enhanced rise in the complicated procedures and rapid changes in external and internal environments.

Similarly, the advent of technology and improvement in business processes, performance, and decision-making processes need rapid enhancement in risk and business intelligence (McNally, 2013).

Keeping the upgrades in mind, COSO published an enhanced form of the Internal Control-Integrated. Its main goal was to create a reviewed, refreshed and modern version of the original structure and ensure its continuous implementation. The COSO framework (McNally 2013) has developed principles according to the five main parts of internal control: monitoring processes, communication and information, control actions, risk evaluation and control environment. According to this framework, the leaders can effectively manage issues, implement internal controls and cater for the decreasing resources and matters in their organisations (McNally, 2013). The figure below describes the changes in the COSO framework over the previous few years:

Figure 6: Evolution of the COSO ERM “Rubik” cube 1992–2004–2013

Source: COSO, (1992; 2004; 2013)

Despite the number of changes made in the COSO framework, it has always been questioned about its reliability and whether it depends on a traditional control method. Bonisch, (2012) has described the 2013 version of the COSO framework to be highly idealistic regarding its insight information required by individuals.

One of the main disadvantages of this framework is that it cannot deal with events simultaneously and unexpectedly (The Internal auditor, 2013). The main competition of the COSO framework is the ISO 31000:2009 that is developed for the management of risks and its effects. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is one of the world's most prominent organisations for developing standards. The ISO 31000 (2009) framework is not based on prescription instead focuses on principle. Even though it does not give a detailed structure or consistency in contrast to COSO, it still can develop ERM procedures unique for all organisations to deal with potential risks and their effects (ISO, 2009). The ISO 31000 (2009) framework describes that the risk management procedure should be completely incorporated with the decision-making procedure of the organisation. The management believes that doing this will help them reach their objectives and goals (Shortreed, 2010).

Figure 7: The ISO 31000:2009 Risk Management Process

Source: Shortreed (2009)

The figure describes that the ISO 31000 (2009) standard describes some manager risk management tasks that an organisation must adopt and implement for effective decision-making. All firms can follow the given figure, but some of the specifications must be changed according to the organisations' specifications. "Establish context deals with the preparation of an ERM task or decision. Risk assessment deals with evaluating

and identifying risks, while "Risk treatment" is the positive or negative effects and solutions of the risks on the organisation. It is reviewing and monitoring the risk controls while consultation and communication deal with consulting the shareholders regarding risk management processes. ERM is a procedure that organisations use with the primary purpose of creating value. Leech (2012) declares the main disadvantage of the ISO 31000 is that it does not explain the proper significance of the risk evaluation process and does not define the assessed and potential risks systematically. Thus, ISO does not explain the apparent connection of ERM with goals and also does not define the effect of unclear goals. In practical implementation, this is one of the significant risks of ERM since it does not represent the clear connection of the risk written on documentation and described to the board members (Leech, 2012).

2.4.1.1 Application of COSO

COSO developed a framework in 2004 as an extension of their initial framework developed in 1994 for achieving organizational objectives. The purpose of this new framework is providing organizations with guidelines regarding the right way of implementing ERM which is referred to as Enterprise Risk Management–Integrated Framework (COSO, 2004). The new COSO framework embeds eight different components of ERM that plays a key role in achieving organizational objectives (COSO, 2004). Listed at the front of cube, the eight ERM components exhibited what is required for achieving their organizational objectives. All the risks in the new COSO framework were handled in a holistic way which offered opportunities for organizations to align their corporate strategy with their risks making their response towards risks effective (Geessink, 2012). A three-dimensional matrix forms the basis of the new COSO framework and takes the shape of a cube. This cube indicates the relationship between organizational levels, objectives and ERM components. The integration and implementation of all eight components is imperative for providing effective ERM. Organization wide risk management is emphasized by the COSO framework covering four key objectives i.e., compliance, reporting, operations and strategy (Passenheim,

2010). The framework stressed that examination of risks needs to be carried out at every organizational level i.e., division, business units, subsidiary and organizational level with the intention of managing a portfolio of risks holistically across all levels (Curkovic, Scannell, Wagner & Vitek, 2013). A brief discussion on the eight components is presented below:

Internal Environment - The basis of how risk is addressed and viewed is set by the internal environment as it embeds the tone of an organization. This includes risk appetite and risk management philosophy, ethical values and integrity, and the overall environment within which organizations operate.

Objective Setting - Before potential events (that can implicate on objectives) are identified by the management, objectives must be developed. ERM ensures that a process is in place by the management for setting and supporting the objectives, are consistent with organizational risk appetite and also for aligning with the organizational mission.

Event Identification - External and internal events affecting achievement of organizational objectives must be identified, distinguishing between opportunities and risks. Management's strategy or objective-setting processes in such scenario integrate opportunities in a channelized manner.

Risk Assessment - Considering likelihood and impact, risks are examined as a basis for defining how they should be managed. In a residual and inherent basis risks are then assessed.

Risk Response - Risk responses are selected by the management i.e., reducing, sharing, avoiding or accepting risk, ultimately establishing a set of actions for aligning risks with organization's risk appetite and tolerances.

Control Activities - For helping and ensuring effectiveness of risk responses being carrier out, procedures and policies are established and implemented.

Information and Communication - Relevant information is communicated, captured and identified in a timeframe and form that enable people to conduct their responsibilities.

Moreover, a broader sense is exhibited in effective communication i.e., across the organization, flowing down and sometimes upwards.

Monitoring - The entirety of ERM is monitored, and changes made as necessary. Accomplishment of monitoring is conducted through ongoing separate evaluations, management activities, separate evaluations, or both.

Therefore, in an organization effective adoption of ERM may be used as a benchmark so that it can be followed by others in making sure risk and uncertainty free environment of workplace. Finally, makes good business sense which is a key reason why organizations are embracing it. Organizations today are installing new technology and using innovative procedures to change the way they take risks (Setapa, 2015).

2.4.2 Contingency Approach to ERM

The contingency theory explains that a firm's performance depends on several external features such as technology, organisation culture, corporate framework, and environment (Ismail et al, 2010). Also, contingency planning states that the organisation must incorporate many contingency features with itself, such as strategy planning, size of the firm, the framework adopted, and corporate environment to show better performance (Lorsch and Lawrence, 1967). Also, according to Otley (1980), the contextual factors of the organisations influence the stronger association between performance and the ERM process. Because of this, contingency planning plays a huge role in describing the elements, including organisational performance.

Some of the main contingency factors that affect the firm performance- risk management of the organisation include (1) independent meeting of board members (Beasley et al., 2005) (2) size of the organisation (Husaini et al., 2013) (3) complications (Husaini et al., 2013) (4) the uncertain environmental conditions (Tjahjadi, 2011).

ERM is now a crucial part of the general corporate governance and has provided several instructions, principles and values (Bone, 2020). Many well-known organisations, including Lehman Brothers, Tokyo Electric and BP, were unable to recognise and deal with the potential risks in their firms. Such examples of human-influenced disasters and the management and operational failures describe how complex the implementation of the ERM process is. Even though some hard-core supporters argue that following the ERM processes is the only way of avoiding potential risks (National Commission, 2011), some people say that ERM itself is the problem (Power 2009; Power 2004). In such cases, however, many sample frameworks are available in literature for risk management, including Risk Management Principles and Guidelines on Implementation, the International Standards Organization ISO 31000:2009 and risk revelation references in the UK Turnbull report (OECD, 2014).

The agencies that rate credits determine it through the firm's ERM and Standard and Poor's, and Moody's mainly focus on risk management in the insurance, economic and energy sectors (SandP, 2013; Moody's Analytics, 2010). Since ERM has such many guidelines, theories and plans, experts consider that ERM is an established principle with proven theories and tools that only need basic information and submission to be implemented effectively. However, many think otherwise. They believe that ERM still requires effort and has a lot of unexplored potentials. Many practitioners agree with this and believe that the given ERM procedures are unsatisfactory (Hancock, Branson and Beasley, 2010; Towers Perrin and CFO Research Services, 2008).

Even though some ERM structures think that managers should only deal with the potential and avoidable risks, some others believe that ERM should work with the implementation (International Standards Organization, 2009; COSO, 2004).

In contrast to this, Wohlgemut and Bogodistov, (2017) consider integration ERM into the dynamic ability framework and views based on resources, while an organisation uses the ERM resources to enhance its core values. It is a worry to know that a strategy that was supposed to solve all problems is facing problems itself. There is a chance that

slowly, the ERM process will lose its actual worth. Nowadays, the board members adopt the ERM process to deal with two main risk management issues. The first issue is hiring managers who will be self-sufficient, will not show any biases, and introduce new risk management strategies. This is also named the organisational matter related to risk management (Tufano, 1998; Stulz and Smith, 1985; Meckling and Jensen, 1976). The second issue is the correct collection of risk-related information at an appropriate time and context that will aid the organisation in making effective decisions and earning reasonable return value. This is named the informational issue of risk management.

This issue mainly arises since the top management makes operational decisions of the organisation and the information given to the workers is not easily accessible to the board members (Raviv and Harris, 1996). One of the main risk management challenges faced by the organisations today includes the organisations' weak internal abilities to create total exposures and help the economic crisis of 2007 to 2009 (Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2013).

2.4.3 Resource-based View

One of the main topics of management practice and research is Risk management (Rau and Bromiley, 2016). According to this, risk management is done to avoid losses due to returns and enhance the business's core value. The identification, evaluation and administration of potential risks and issues with internal communications, decisions and observations that manage such risks are known as risk management. The risk avoidance strategies of the organisations are completed with ERM processes, and it tends to become a crucial part of the strategy-making of the firm (Bromiley et al., 2015). There are still many discussions discussing if ERM is a theory, set of strategies and acceptable practices, or just a group of theories used in several situations.

Some other risks that the managers face include the infinite unrecognised risks and the inability of identifying such risks in time. Even though many strategies and resources are available, it is still not enough to deal with all the potential risks (Rau and Bromiley, 2016). That is why setting priorities is essential. Some experts have created suitable

frameworks (Hopkin, 2015; Schmit and Gatzert, 2016). An issue is that they are not unique for all organisations. Bromiley et al., (2015) states that integrating the ERM process with strategic planning has still not been dealt with properly. Many scholars say that management and strategy experts are the most suitable for dealing with such issues in the ERM process. This study will increase the knowledge of risk management by describing a dynamic ability and a view based on resources.

One of the most significant strategic management theories is the resource-based theory (Barney et al., 2011) or the resources-based view (Hamel and Prahalad, 1990; Wernerfelt, 1984; Barney, 1991; Barney, 2001). This theory states that there is an unequal distribution of resources between organisations and describes how some organisations have competitive advantages over others. The organisations should have VRIN resources (Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, Non-sustainable). This study proposes that these resources are the basis of an effective ERM process. The main goal of ERM is to deal with the risks collectively rather than individually (Stulz and Nocco, 2006). The change of the resource-based strategic management theory to the risk management domain will influence the experts to develop a consistent primary strategy that will implement ERM in all possible scenarios. The dynamic ability perspective is the next step of the view based on resources (Peteraf et al., 2013). The main weakness of the resources-based view was its inability to deal with unexpected situations. The dynamic ability perspective will help to overcome this challenge.

According to this, "the capacity of an organisation to purposefully create, extend, or modify its resource base" (Helfat et al., 2007, p. 1) and also gives suggestions on how to deal with unexpected and dynamic situations (Teece et al., 1997). Here, experts also state how the knowledge of dynamic ability perspective can influence the theory and implementation of the risk management process.

All changes in technology, competitors, financial situations and political stability are threats in the market. The firms should set aside special resources and strategies to deal with such situations. The experts have now used the ERM process to change the

environment of the organisations and have studied the effects on its performance (Bromiley et al., 2015). With the integration of resource-based view and dynamic ability perspective in the ERM, the knowledge and implementation strategies of the organisations have improved. The resource-based view provides methods that can be used to prioritise tasks in the firm. The environmental complexity leads to several unexpected potential risks for the business (Luhmann, 1995; Wohlgemuth and Burisch, 2016; Rau and Bromiley, 2016).

The firm cannot manage all risks and needs to deal with the most threatening ones first. The resources-based view describes which ones are the most problematic. The dynamic ability perspective deals with any unexpected future risks. Many strategies and theories are focused on identifying and monitoring risks. Some of the prominent examples are due diligence and compliance procedures (Varma and Clarke, 1999). Still, there will always be unforeseen circumstances. Many organisations deal with risks that have low probability but hazardous effects. This low probability makes all the potential risk management contingency planning useless (Rau and Bromily, 2016). The dynamic strategies help the firms deal with such events smoothly and recover instantly. Thus, a dynamic ability perspective is necessary for the ERM process to smooth the transition from risk events by providing the managers with strategies that will help them recover.

2.4.4 Theory of Risk Management

Dubin's framework (1976) states that a theory needs to consist of explicitly defined units, risks of such units and contingency strategies that will be used to recover from such risks. According to Weick (1995), there is a clear difference between theorising (Process) and theory (product).

The process cannot start without the presence of information, theory or appropriate analysis. Some experts agree with a part of it. This study deals with the three main

components of the ERM process. First is the risk management phase (steps include risk identification, assessment, management, monitoring). The second is the risk evaluation (risk probability vs potential hazardous effects), such as the ISO 31000:2009 explained by Leitch, 2010; Purdy, 2010). The risk phase includes the significant steps while dealing with risks (Hiebl and Falkner, 2015).

An example may be that ISO 31000:2009 consists of the given steps: declaring background, identifying risks, analysing risks, evaluating risks, treating risks, consultation and communication, risk assessing and rowing (Purdy, 2010).

The ERM also integrates the organisation's strategic goals and incorporates favourable chances and risks (Hopkins, 2015). Tippett and Carbone (2004) have created their risk management process. This process is descriptive and aided with related information such as declaring probability, effects, and identification values rather than writing risk analysis. Some writers do not consider the monitoring and recursive parts of the process. Other organisations (COSO in the USA or CoCo in Canada) and writers (Baker, 1997) follow the basic principle of the theory. The risks should be dealt with systematically, and that risk evaluation is a crucial part of the risk's management procedure.

The organisation can predict the risks by measuring their chances of occurring and the amount of damage it will cause (Rau and Bromiley, 2016). Some experts have added extra points regarding risk assessment. An example would be the integration of personal risk tolerance by the organizational leadership (Holzhauer et al., 2016). Tippett and Carbone (2004) suggested the detection method for assessment. According to experts, this method is necessary for dealing with unexpected risks. Similarly, Smallman and Elkington (2002) have added the importance of timely identification, while Baker (1999) throws light on the presence of secondary risks evaluation.

However, the main idea of risk evaluation is the chances of occurring and the number of hazardous effects. The third component of the risk management process consists of four major strategies. They are known as reduction, contingency, transfer, and

prevention (Smallman and Elkington, 2002). Tippett and Carbone (2004) have also described the same techniques under different names: Transference, acceptance, avoidance and mitigation. The techniques can be defined as tolerance (Retaining or acceptance), treatment (reduction or control), transferring (Contract or insurance) and termination (elimination or avoidance). Other experts have added more strategies, such as Spikin (2013), who has differentiated risks into two types: risk finance and risk control. Risk finance includes risk retention, toleration, sharing and corrective.

In comparison, risk control includes strategies for avoiding risks such as risk termination, prevention and reduction, directive, detective and corrective. Hilson (2002) has explained some circumstances in which the risks have led to positive opportunities such as enhancing performance and resources. An overview of these techniques shows that even though they have different names, they are similar in nature. The risk management strategies discussed to define the parts of risk management theory in the Western business world; since risk management procedures may be different in the Islamic world, some cultural biases may be faced (Shafque et al., 2013). Other than the substitute strategies of risk management, including dynamic risk management (Tsyplakov and Fehle, 2005), the dynamic approach (Rasmussen, 1997) and eco-centric theory (Shrivastava, 1995), these theories also understand the basis of the ERM strategy (Spikin, 2003; Rau and Bromiley, 2016).

ERM is one of the most commonly known strategies in the field of risk management nowadays. It proposes that the risks be managed collectively rather than individually (Stulz and Nocco, 2006; Bromiley et al., 2015). It also integrates both traditional and strategic risks (Obi and Ibik, 2014). In ERM, standard techniques are used when they are implemented systematically. The risk avoidance strategies are thus made following the organisation's communications and surroundings (Rau and Bromiley, 2016). The implementation is still complex.

A lot of energy and time is required to make sure the ERM is implemented through all the management levels (Beasley et al., 2005). One of the main reasons is that potential

risks are many, and systemising them is challenging (Luhmann, 1995; Wohlgemuth and Burisch, 2016; Rau and Bromiley, 2016).

The following strategies and their applications take additional time and energy in lost money or time. Even though the ERM theory is explained in detail, its implementation procedure still has missing links. Finding all of the potential risks and calculating the cost-efficiency of strategies is not possible practically (Wohlgemuth and Burisch, 2016; Rau and Bromiley, 2016).

Many factors are potential risks themselves. However, the risk management process should not deal with identifying all risks rather should concern with listing them systematically throughout the entire process of ERM (Harrington et al., 2002). Harrington et al., 2002 also states that the risks can be structured and prioritised by dealing with them systematically instead of approaching them individually, a technique which is mostly documented in many literature papers. This study also tells us about the ever-changing environment and its effects. Experts mainly deal with risks and their losses based on previous experiences, which might be inaccurate. Instead of this, they should deal with the unexpected external factors and create effective strategies to deal with them. This study also mentions the eagerness of experts in developing new risk identification strategies (Wagner and Kinatendar, 2014).

2.5 Chapter Summary

The chapter has presented arguments and knowledge from contemporary and classical literature on how ERM holds value and how it facilitates decision-making for boards across organizations. COSO framework and other relevant theories discussed in this chapter have assisted in understanding the need of ERM for making organizations effective in their decision making and overall performance. COSO is the first formal initiative towards risk management which is providing the basis of theoretical framework in this study. The relevance of ERM for board of directors have been signified in this chapter by mentioning the type of risks they usually face and how ERM can potentially provide them with a strong strategic option to improve their risk management related

decision making. This chapter is reflecting that ERM provides a system which organizational boards can use for making informed decisions and ERM can form a major part of corporate strategy as well so that a culture supportive towards ERM adoption can be established. After providing theoretical base of the study, the next chapter will present theoretical framework developed in line with the four themes presented in this chapter. Collectively this chapter is providing a guideline for the selection of research methodology because this chapter has determined what kind of data and information is required for addressing the research objectives. Moreover, while developing data collection instrument the consideration of literature review chapter findings will be essential and it will be equally important to consider the knowledge presented in this chapter while conducting data analysis.

2. Chapter3 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework to be presented in this chapter is inspired by the COSO framework, and the literature review chapter findings presented so far. COSO framework is a system developed for improving internal control in organizations and it provided basis of all the recently developed risk management related models. This study's underlying stance is that the ERM as a framework can be effective towards risk management and internal control and fundamental components of ERM framework are derived from and are rooted in COSO framework. This chapter will develop a theoretical framework that will be aligned with literature review findings and COSO components which will guide the data collection and analysis process. Ultimately, in the last chapter, a conceptual framework will be developed in the light of research findings of this study and will link different concepts together in the form of a network. This proposed conceptual framework in the last chapter will indicate a potential solution for ERM adoption and integration across selected Laos industries.

Corporate board and organisational strategy are aligned, and they are supposed to be aligned as a prerequisite of adopting ERM effectively. Any organisation's board of directors is the people who hold the responsibility of making financial decisions that affect the executives' perquisites and power, the financial health of communities, security of the workers, and the investors' capital (Molz, 1985). These people are selected or chosen and are responsible for leading the operations of the company. They also signify the profits of the stakeholders. These and many other responsibilities are assigned to the board directors by law. The board's fundamental purpose "is to ensure the company's prosperity by collectively directing the company's affairs, while meeting the appropriate interests of its shareholders and relevant stakeholders" (Institute of Directors, 2018).

The organisational board must ensure certain aspects regarding their characteristics and competencies for being able to and for being ready to capitalise on ERM in decision making (Clara et al, 2019). These aspects, if not secured, can potentially result in issues.

For example, if sufficient training of directors is not conducted, then the skills and competencies of board members may restrict their ability to embed ERM and use it properly. Moreover, suppose an appropriate framework of ERM has not been selected, and consensus has not been achieved regarding which framework is suitable. In that case, it can restrict the ability to improve decision-making. If the leadership representing the board is willing and aware of the benefits of ERM and trained appropriately, they can only select an appropriate ERM framework suitable for their business (Johanna and Anderson, 2019). However, it has been observed that the most critical factor for driving ERM adoption and ensuring that board decision making is well-informed and risk-averse is the presence of a risk management culture (Sekerci, 2015). Therefore, this framework indicates that the starting point or initial step is to develop a risk management culture across the firm because different organisational functions will have to support the effective working of ERM for the board. Therefore, the first step is to ensure that the organisational strategy and corporate board are driven by and integrated with a risk management culture.

Many studies based on ERM highlight the principal responsibilities of the board members related to the risk management activities (To et al, 2021; Bunea and Dinu, 2021; OECD, 2014a). As the expectations of the board members in managing the risk-related responsibilities have increased, they are now held accountable for the approval and administration of all the risk-related managerial processes and strategies. An example is that the audit board committee has explicit responsibilities given by the governance rules of NYSE to "discuss management's risk management and risk assessment processes". SEC enforced the proxy exposure rules in 2010 also state that the public firms should be transparent in the yearly proxy statement about the prominent roles and responsibilities of the board members (SEC, 2009; NYSE, 2004).

Since board members have higher responsibilities related to the monitoring of the risk management processes, many questions related to the understanding of the risk strategies and approval of these strategies for the risk-related management processes are asked i.e., Which firms use the ERM strategy as a solution for risk management? Which procedures are involved in the ERM strategy? and What is Internal Auditing (IA) used for in ERM? The main objective of adopting the ERM process is to deal with enterprise-level risks to ensure that all the organisation's potential risks, rather than just one sector, are identified and evaluated (Lai et al, 2017). With the increased expectations of efficient risk management from the directors, there is a lot of pressure on the senior executives to implement the ERM process effectively. In such cases, the boards can challenge the decision of implementation of ERM in the organisation.

Organisational strategy guided by the risk management culture will have to ensure that specific strategies are developed and intact, i.e., reporting standards and quality needs to meet the internationally established criteria for upholding transparency and accountability (Murayev et al, 2016).

A corporate governance system built on good practices is another strategy required for successfully integrating ERM across board decision making. Some of the main important factors that determine whether an organisation should implement ERM include governance and organisational characteristics, including industry and size factors. Many organisations that implement the ERM process have different results when they include other financial and organisational features. Some studies describe the direct influence of the ERM process in organisations, and they mainly prioritise the COSO system (Radaelli, 2020).

Even though many firms use some aspects of this framework, no organisation will implement the procedure thoroughly. Documents that describe the experience of organisations that implemented ERM showed that they were in different forms and different effects even if they belonged to the same industry. Various organisations use different versions of the ERM process according to their requirements. Since there is no

definitive knowledge of what ERM strategies firms use in their operations, conducting specific research about the efficiency of these methods is very difficult (Martin et al, 2019). The exact information about factors that influence the ERM, and its efficiency is also minimal. The most significant achievement of a business in terms of its governance and performance management is its success in integrating systematic risk management into its day-to-day decision-making (Stulz, 2016). The picture below is a depiction of how risk management driven by ERM engages and works across an organisational system:

Figure 8: ERM and Organizational System

Source: Gelman et al, (2018)

Incorporating ERM is getting more critical, but since ERM processes are not entirely integrated with the business, they do not have a powerful impact (Lam, 2016). This is where the ERM processes are really tested. With the proper implementation, both models support and aid the monitoring process. This is to make sure that the organisation achieves its objectives and enhances its value. The senior management and the directors have two varying roles. The responsibility of the senior management is

to plan and manage employees, procedures, strategies, technologies and documentation, which are essential for reaching the organisation's goals. The directors are responsible for establishing restrictions, approving strategy and monitoring implementation processes. There are many limitations related to risks set by the board members.

In an organisation, the ERM process is responsible for organising management processes and identifying potential risks and solutions. There are three ways how ERM manages this, which include controlling the environment and risk appetite (Lyons, 2015).

Moreover, the frameworks are known to facilitate the processes in governance, if their implementation is properly done. The task of these frameworks is to assist the firm in attaining the objectives and enhance the value (Jankensgard, 2019). It is critical for the board to oversee execution by establishing boundaries and approving strategic decisions. The management needs to make sure that reporting, people, processes and strategy is aligned to attain the mission on the basis of established values. It aims to play a critical role because risks can be evacuated due to such boundaries formed by the management. ERM develops a sense of discipline in the management and allows them to perceive risks and opportunities regarding how they can manage the firms. It also contributes this change in three ways, the first is to control the environment, the second is to manage risk appetite and the third is to manage philosophy (Gatzert and Martin, 2015).

3.1 Theory of Risk Management

The risk management philosophy is one of the three parts of the ERM process. It is the method that determines how the firms take notice of risks in all of their operations, including strategy planning, application, and daily activities. It also informs about the significance of risk management in all of the functions. All organisations adopt the risk management philosophy. The features of risk philosophy include its development state, whether explicit and implicit and how fast employers understand and embrace it (Cohen et al, 2017).

3.2 Risk Appetite

Risk appetite describes the organisation's risk management philosophy and affects the culture and operations management of the firm.

The risk appetite is documented in a risk appetite statement that exhibits the firm's risks and the economic and operational factors that the organisation should adhere to, i.e., to operate smoothly (Farrell and Gallagher, 2019). The statement should be moulded according to the organisation's requirements but not so much that it is continuously changing. Frequent change in the risk appetite decreases the value of it. Risk appetite is a significant factor for organisations that use monitoring processes to balance value protection and value creation.

3.3 Control Environment

Both models have control environments containing a total of five values that are responsible for efficient monitoring. These values include ethical and moral values, individuality and control of the board of directors, report lines created by the management, the concern of the organisation towards its hard-working employees and the answerability of the organisation. A good business depends upon competent people and has a controlled environment that facilitates this (Lechner and Gatzert, 2018).

According to the COSO framework (2004), ERM is defined as a procedure “applied in strategy setting” designed to provide reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of entity objectives” (p. 2). According to this definition, ERM manages the risks that a strategy might face during implementation while trying to reach the goals of the company. Anderson and Frigo (2011) also think that ERM is only effective when it is used during the strategy implementation. Despite these theories, it has been discovered that coordinating the ERM and strategic process is very hard for organizations. Pagach, Branson and Beasley (2015) collected sample data from 645 firms of different industries to collect specific factors that value the ERM process. It was discovered that ERM is

used as a strategic device when the organization includes it in its risk appetite statement during the strategic planning process and when the annual management report citing potential risks is provided to the board members.

They also discovered that ERM is better implemented and integrated with the ERM process when the firm creates a committee at the management level, proper training related to ERM is given, and the shareholders are involved during the whole planning and implementation process. It was also stated that the organization's value is increased when there is transparent cooperation between the risk management process and executive compensation. Larger organizations implement ERM as a strategic device, while public firms implement it to enhance value.

The researchers also interviewed the audit partners, committee members and CFOs that worked in the same firms form a total of eleven organizations (Cohen, Krishnamoorthy, and Wright, 2014). Trade strategy was mentioned to be critical by the two firms' members, whereas remaining mentioned strategy to be critical. It was also noted that the CFO and audit committee members noted strategy to be ore important aspect. They were also inquired about the individual role in mentioning the risks of four objective, i.e., compliance, reporting, operational and strategic risk as presented in COSO (2004) framework for ERM, the probability of them to mention a critical role of strategic risk was higher as compared to other three risks.

Moreover, the weakness in the role was perceived by external auditors in terms of risks for strategic objectives. It was also reviewed by auditors that resource dependence theory and agency theory can be applied in the case of ERM. They explored that as per ERM, they are playing the monitoring role as per agency theory, and they aim to balance the corporate strategy to evade risks related to business. ERM champions were also interviewed by Viscelli et al. (2016) in various firms, and they found that there is a strategic need to evaluate risks, for which ERM is widely being used. Yet, the area which is commonly cited in the interviews given by employees is the further

improvements in the processes of ERM when discussed the three to five years goals for ERM. All in all, the interviewee indicated that strategic impact of ERM is majorly indicated by limited factors, and resource development is the core for these processes. However, it also emerges as a tool that helps in monitoring the agency theory. This results in the limited extent of its impact, and a failure in linking ERM with the strategy. The COSO framework (2004) is now defined as a method “applied in strategy setting across the enterprise” and “designed to identify potential events that may affect the entity and manage risks to be within its risk appetite to provide reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of entity objectives”. This basic idea has been instilled in the above-developed framework, i.e., to enable the board and organizational culture strong enough that they can identify risks effectively in the form of a mechanism and keep the board informed about the potential risks. “Strategic” was included in the list of factors of ERM, and therefore ‘objective setting’ was determined as one of the main objectives of the ERM process. According to the COSO framework (2004), internal control is also ERM’s part. Therefore, the aspect of strategy holds importance in this framework incorporated and embedded in the above-presented model. Internal control has also been integrated into the above-formulated framework as part of the organizational culture. It functions as part of the overall firm culture and improves gradually, ultimately having the impact of strong ERM board decision making. The role of leadership style is crucial when it comes to board decision making because it will direct or guide the way board members are behaving and adopting ERM i.e., wrong choice of leadership behaviours and style can deter the process of improving board decision making.

The five main parts of the internal control have basic principles developed by the COSO framework. They include risk evaluation, control environment, control activities, monitoring activities and communication and information. (McNally, 2013). This is the reason why the internal control system has been linked with the organizational risk culture. Organizational culture has great significance in the implementation and efficiency of the ERM. If the CEO or board members do not give enough consideration to the ERM process, its implementation to gain strategic value becomes hard. There is not much information about the organizational culture in the ERM process.

According to studies, transformational leadership is an effective strategy that can be used in both private and public sector firms (Hatmaker and Hassan, 2014). Transformational leadership coordinates with employees to change things. They are responsible for creating a goal for their workers and achieve it through motivation and hard work.

They are supposed to be a role model whose actions would be followed by employees. They create new paths and change the organizational culture in contrast to managers who follow the rule book to lead their teams. The primary responsibilities of such leaders also include developing a vision that the organization would follow, work to implement these changes and make sure that it becomes an integral part of the organization (Ulrich and Tichy, 1984).

The concept of transformation leadership was given by Burns (1978). This concept pinpointed how efficient leaders can bring change and improvement in the culture of an organization. Brass (1985) also presented his theory based on Burn's (1978) concept, but both of these were slightly different. Burns (1978) stated that transformational leadership increases the standards and inspiration of both workers and leaders. Hich et al., 2018 says that a transformational leader increases his skills while motivating his followers to work hard and show inspirational results. Such leaders encourage their followers to do their best and guide them in becoming excellent leaders themselves. (Kroyak et al., 2015). To achieve this, two main things need to be kept in mind. First is fulfilling all the requirements of the employees, and second is to set objectives for leaders, workers, teams and firms (Fisher et al., 2017).

Burns (1978) stated that all managers in any firm could be transformational leaders. Bass (1985) noted that an excellent transformational leader is determined by his impact on his workers, which includes the workers trusting him, following his opinions, and being loyal and respectful towards him. They are also motivated by him in achieving their goals. Three main points can transform the viewpoint of workers i.e., 1) By drawing the attention of workers towards the importance and results of their tasks, 2) By

motivating employees to prioritize the organizational benefits over their interests, and 3) By assisting the employees in fulfilling their requirements. The effect of transformational leadership is not only dependent upon his charisma (Fruhen, Mearns and Temminck, 2015). There are many other characteristics of a leader that attracts followers. Even though charisma plays a considerable role, other features also play a substantial role (Lindholm, 2018).

Some of the main features of a transformation leader include identifying priorities, having explicit beliefs and values, influencing agreements among shareholders, maintaining the state of urgency and readying people to act on it. These features make the shareholders understand the importance of change and thinking of ways to implement such changes.

Below presented is the theoretical framework of this study which is encompassing the concepts from literature review and COSO system:

Figure 9: Theoretical Framework

Source: Bikky,(2019)

4. Chapter4 Research Methodology

4.1 Paradigm of Inquiry (Interpretivism)

The main components of a paradigm include ontology, methodology, and epistemology. This chapter will provide an explanation of these terminologies along with exploring the relationship that exists between them. The nature of knowledge is subjective when it comes to the interpretivism paradigm (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). This will help the researcher focus on the personal knowledge and information possessed by the potential sample respondents. Truth is context-dependent, and this is what counts as the trustor is considered as truth. This shows that the particular context of Laos is to be explored with the help of interpretivism, and the fact will be regarded as applicable and determined in the context of Laos. This also indicates that while collecting data, the intention and focus should be laid on the context-specific activities or strategies. The current interpretative research aims to understand the experience of the individuals and personnels for which it has been carried out in a natural setting where participants are functioning. This also indicates the high relevance of phenomenology for carrying out and addressing the established research objectives in Laos. The study will state the assumptions of the interpretive research as it is an effort to understand the human experience, which will explain the relevance of phenomenology. The research process is also affected by the assumptions that have been made regarding the multiplicity of realities. This may be seen in several forms such as an unclear research question that gradually evolves with the research through the investigative progress (Mertens, 2009).

The tools that are generally used for the collection of qualitative data under the qualitative approach include interviews and observations (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005). Using such an approach will provide an interpretation of reality which is subjective, the events are observed while staying in the natural environment. Interpretivism is interested in collecting qualitative data with the help of tools such as participant observation and interviews (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005).

This approach adopts a subjective interpretation of reality. It tends to analyze things by allowing them to stay in their natural environment, which provides a strong rationale for using this data collection method in the respective study. Unlike the positivism approach, interpretivism is known to dig deeper into the social process through which the questions to why and how can be understood. Since the research problem under consideration is significantly related to the individual knowledge of the board of directors, there is a severe need to explore how respective directors view the issue and why they are inclined towards a certain perspective.

This will be made possible with the application of the interpretivism paradigm of inquiry because it supports the extraction of subjective and multiple realities. Interpretivism helps to integrate the human interest into a study since it involves interpretation by the researchers. This study intends to engage, extract, and evaluate the opinion of board directors working in Laos firms, representing the human interest of this study. According to Myers (2008) “interpretive researchers believe that the access to reality, which can be both natural or socially constructed, is only through social constructions such as language, consciousness, shared meanings, and instruments”. However, in the context of this study, interpretivism will be given preference as compared to constructivism. Interpretivism is “is often associated with the position of idealism under philosophy and is used to create a group of diverse approaches. Such different approaches include phenomenology, hermeneutics and social constructivism, which reject the objectivist view relating to the meaning present within the world free from human consciousness”.

This interpretive view will enable the researcher to focus and give preference to the individual thinking and viewpoints of the board directors as fundamental human interests of this study. Although research philosophies tend to vary from a number of angles, the main difference is seen. Research philosophies may vary on a number of domains but are seen to mainly varying on the research goals set out and the process to be followed for achieving these goals (Gummesson, 2000). This requires the researcher to carefully take into account the goals set out in the research through which the approach research methodology to be applied can be determined.

Common perception present between researchers is that the interpretive/constructivist paradigm mainly makes use of the qualitative research methods (Glesne and Peshkin, 1992; Willis, 2007; Nind and Todd, 2011). This perspective gives an indicating that phenomenology is suitable for implementation in this study. Interpretivism is commonly seen to prefer the qualitative methods of research such as ethnography and case studies (Willis, 2007, P.90). Using the qualitative approach provides rich data which can be used by the interpretivists to understand the texts completely. Thomas (2003) has also made claims that are consistent with such findings such as claiming that the qualitative method is followed because it helps present such a world in which one can understand reality in its true image of complex and ever-changing socially constructed reality. According to McQueen (2002), the interpretivism approach involves researchers seeking methods through which they can understand the relationship that exists between human beings and their environment along with the role played by other people as being part of the social fabric. For this reason, interpretivism cannot use methods that grant precise or objective information.

McQueen (2002) has described interpretivism as the process of viewing the world through a number of perspectives of different people since each person has their own view regarding the world. This brief description of the nature of the interpretivism paradigm is reflecting that participant selection will be critical for addressing the established research objectives in this study. Researchers that defend interpretivism claim that qualitative methods provide more approachable means through which one can access a reality. Therefore, this study intends to investigate the reality of ERM implementation and its impact on onboard decision-making by closely interacting with board members and collecting qualitative data via an interview.

The key aim that is pursued by the researcher while using the interpretive paradigm is gaining deep insight or in-depth information regarding the research topic that is being explored. A reason for which the qualitative approach allows the researcher to achieve in-depth data of high quality is following the process of deep attentiveness and empathetic understanding (Punch, 2009).

These arguments clarify how relevant and imperative the interpretivism paradigm is for effectively completing this research study. In-depth and rich insights are precisely what is required in this study because the understanding and the viewpoint of every selected board director can vary. Crotty (1998) claimed that an individual may construct different meanings from the same scenario and the truth is formed as a result of a consensus that is acquired between the co-constructors. Knowledge is known to possess the trait of being historically stated and culturally derived. Ideologies are accepted in the interpretive paradigm rather than being accepted.

This means that the contextual situation of ERM within Laos firms and the ideologies possessed by respective board directors will not be questioned, and instead, the answers to questions 'how' and 'why' will be addressed. Crotty (1998, p.42) also claimed that knowledge and meaningful reality are constructed through interaction that takes place between humans and the world which is transferred in the social context. For this reason, only those individuals can be understood in the social world that is actually participating in it (Cohen, et al, 2007). The interpretive theory is being generated from data rather than preceding it, for which it is the view as grounded (Cohen, et al, 2007, p.22). For this reason, the research questions aimed to be answered are broad. Cohen et al, (2007, p.8) used an approach that is characterized by an individual case in which a relativistic social world is embedded. Interpretivism refutes the existence of value-free knowledge. Researchers tend to assert their belief then they decide the particular domain they wish to research along with the process of studying and interpreting data (Edge and Richards, 1998, p.336).

4.2 Ontology

The domain of ontology is concerned with understanding what makes up reality. They need to take up a certain position regarding perceptions around what things are and how they work. In this study, ontological assumptions provided by the interpretivism paradigm will enable the researcher to articulate and analyse the reality of the impact generated by ERM onboard decision making in the specific context of Laos.

While questioning reality, the interpretivists have put forward the claim that it is socially constructed (Mertens, 2009; Creswell, 2003). A number cannot be assigned to intangible realities as they depend on the number of people creating them. For this reason, the reality is dependent on the mind and is a personal or social construct. If a researcher believes a particular concept or event, then it is their reality, a way in which they try to make sense of the world. This means that the researcher will have to take and accept an inevitable reality related to the application of ERM in the light of literature review constructs.

The previous argument made clearly shows how reality is being limited to context, individuals, space, time, groups, situations etc. for which it cannot be generalized as a shared reality. Making such assumptions clearly opposes the assumptions made by positivists as they claim that a tangible external reality exists which can be accepted. The assumptions made validate the concepts of reality from all cultures present. Individual, as well as group-shared realities, are seen to exist in today's time. The question worth asking here is that how these realities are to be shaped into the research process for understanding the scenario present. Multiple and socially constructed realities are embedded by the interpretivism paradigm. This also indicates the suitability of interpretivism for researching the chosen topic of ERM and board decision making. Relativism is the ontological position taken up in the paradigm of interpretivism. Assumptions made in relativism are that reality is subjective for which the perspective can vary from one person to another (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). The perception of reality of a person is being mediated with their senses and without consciousness, the world would appear to be meaningless. A person would be enlightened by the truth when he interacts with objects that are already carrying meaning (Crotty, 1998).

Reality is known to be individually constructed for which the number of realities can be correlated with the number of individuals. Languages do not play a passive role but rather work actively for shaping reality (Frowe, 2001). From this, it can be said that truth is being constructed through the interaction that takes place between language and the realities that are present in this world.

Subjectivism is the epistemology that is used under the interpretive paradigm which is based on the real-world phenomenon. Grix (2004, p.83) also claimed that the world is not independent of the knowledge that a person holds. In the words of Crotty (1998, p.43) through the personification of a tree, “One needs to remember that humans themselves have created it as a tree by giving it a name and then attributed it to associations that a person makes with trees.” A tree will not be called a tree if a person does not exist to call it a tree. For this reason, meaning is not discovered but rather constructed through the interaction that takes place between the world and consciousness. Consciousness does not exist independently but rather depends on something else (Crotty, 1998, p.44). One can only experience the world through molding and countering it (Heron and Reason, 1997, p.3). Intentionality refers to the interaction between consciousness and phenomena that will be used during data collection in this study so that the construction of reality can be made meaningful.

4.3 Epistemology

The process that would be used for the acquisition of knowledge is defined under epistemology (Bryman, 2001). The knowledge specified is acceptable under certain paradigms. An example can be taken of the epistemology of normative design in which the social world can investigate in the form of natural science. Epistemology is the study of how we can assert the viewpoint or carry out the study to stress our perspective, contributing to reality (Punch, 2013). The interpretive form of epistemology involves the acquisition of knowledge by investigating phenomena in a number of ways due to the difference from the natural science of social context. A number of interpretations can be drawn through the investigation of social phenomena. This is precisely the case with investigating the role of ERM in improving board decision making in the specific context of Laos. The social context of different firms operating in Laos will have to be considered by applying epistemological assumptions. Constructivists believe that knowledge is subjective because it is socially constructed and mind-dependent.

In this study, it is believed that the use and influence of ERM will vary from one board to another because the knowledge and understanding of each board will be different, hence signifying its socially constructed nature. Interpretivism calls for the acquisition of knowledge through human experience, where the statement of true or false is seen to be context-dependent, historical, and culture-bound with somewhat scope to be universal.

Applying learning within this domain, it can be said that the community stories, claims of spirituality, belief systems, and earth connections tend to find space as legitimate knowledge. Therefore, it will be interesting to determine and evaluate the subjective knowledge produced by different board directors in line with the literature review findings that represent a distinct context-dependent set of factors.

Choosing epistemology in the context of business research as a branch of philosophy is seen to be primarily concerned with the sources of knowledge. Epistemology in specific is seen to be concerned with nature, sources, limitations, and possibilities of knowledge in the field of study. There is no grand method of theory present that has a universal or general claim to authoritative knowledge relating to making sense of social reality (Richardson, 1997: 121). The researcher generally took part in practical activities through which data can be generated and interpreted in order to create meaning from what the participants know and do. A range of tools and techniques are present are applied for this purpose such as life history work, narrative inquiry to study, and ethnography which according to Hammersley (2006) shows “first-hand what people do and say in particular contexts”. The practice of the researcher underpinned with an epistemological stance in order to complete this task and provide a philosophical ground for deciding that types of knowledge that are possible. This will also make it possible to understand what kind of information is both adequate and legitimate (Maynard, 1994). The table is given below highlights a range of epistemologies that show how knowledge can be generated. Such stances are generally expressed in qualitative research methodologies and methods that researchers employ.

<i>Objectivism</i>	<i>Constructivism</i>	<i>Subjectivism</i>
Meaning and meaningful reality exists as such apart from the operation of any consciousness. In this epistemology, of what it means to know, understanding and values are considered objectified in the people researchers study. Using appropriate methods researchers can discover objective truth.	Constructivism rejects the objectivist view of human knowledge. Truth or meaning is constructed not discovered. People may construct meaning in different ways, even in relation to the same phenomena. There can be no unmediated grasp of the social world that exists independently of the researcher and all claims to knowledge take place within a particular conceptual framework.	Evident in structuralist, post-structuralist and postmodernist thinking. Meaning does not emerge from the interaction between the object and the subject; it is imposed on the object by the subject.

Table 1: Three Epistemologies

Source: Crotty, (1998)

There are certain parallels present between these epistemologies and each had a unique feature that will hold concern for the qualitative researcher. However, there are several ways through which these concerns present can be addressed. The least area where researchers have to take a decision is how to regard a particular knowledge as acceptable. It is necessary for social scientists to understand the context and actions in which people live as it helps to make sense of the discourse that they construct. Riemer et al, (2012) pointed out that qualitative research does not need to carry a fixed epistemological implication. It is up to the researcher to decide what type of knowledge they want to gather about the social world where the epistemological assumptions, methods, and values can be intertwined.

The approach suggested puts emphasis on studying the attitudes, ideas, motives, and intentions of the participant regarding how they perceive the social world whether or not they are online (Foster, 1996). The participants can be enabled to engage, as individuals or groups, in activities, being a member of the virtual community online. A researcher can also join the participants in such communities in order to see how they are acknowledging the social world present around them and observe the participation of co-construction online.

Researchers can immerse themselves through participation by gaining deep insight into the private lives, conversations, and social worlds which can be broadened and democratized, rather than just being a plain explanation of the human experience. The online experience of users can be understood through dialogic and reflexive encounters through which greater sense can be made of the scenario. This becomes part of the interpretive act itself which plays role in helping the participants to develop their viewpoint through sharing their experiences. Such a process can be enhanced by taking into account both temporal and contextual dimensions of the participant's experience (Illingworth, 2006). The hermeneutical position is reflected through the adoption of such procedure. Both time and space are provided for carrying out clarification of constructs that are not understood properly and clarifying the conditions in which understanding has taken place to better understand the meaning. The process of conversation and interaction can be negotiated mutually through the act of interpretation rather than waiting around for it to be discovered.

Taking up such point of review, the construction of knowledge, researchers and participants work in collaboration to create an understanding of the situation where the participants work and live (Thomas, 2013) The physical, visual, and embodied ways of knowing in the face-to-face qualitative research tends to provide a legitimate mean for identifying and explaining the epistemological stance adopted by the researcher (O'Leary, 2010).

4.4 Methodology

Phenomenology is defined as the methodology or the precise approach to be used for carrying out a study or research. Langdrige (2007) stated that there are a number of phenomenologies that overlap in both methodology and philosophy and the facts tend to reveal themselves over time as phenomenology develops over the years. Phenomenology in principles has been defined as the people's perception of the world or perception regarding things as they appear to be. It is often defined in relation to the study of phenomena through human experience in the lives of a person (Von Eckartsberg in Valle 1998).

The methodology defines a set of tasks that are to be followed for collection and analysis of data followed by reporting the findings. The findings provided are a collection of descriptions and meaning for individuals that relate with the lived experience or the collective experience of concepts (Creswell, 2007). Such illustration generally appears in the form of statements or written phrases that show meaning which the participant attributes to a certain experience (Smith, et al, 2009).

From this, it can be said that phenomenology tends to reduce the experiences of a subject to a description of its overall perception that is written down. The role of a qualitative researcher is to identify a phenomenon such as an 'object' from the human experience which can be given a voice (Creswell, 2007). The approach devised under phenomenology itself aims to identify a particular phenomenon that is perceived by the participants in the particular situation provided (Kafle, 2011). This can be translated into the process of gathering deep information and perception through the use of qualitative data in the human sphere through interviews, participant observation, and discussions (Gill, 2014). In the setting of the current study, the board members can be labeled as the actors of the situation and the phenomenology seems to benefit for collecting information relating to the perception of ERM in the firm.

Phenomenology aims to carry out a study of experience through the perspective of the individual, usual ways of perceiving, and 'bracketing' assumptions that are taken for granted. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches are based on the paradigms of subjectivity and personal knowledge which emphasize the importance of interpretation and unique perspective. They tend to play a decisive role in understanding the experience subjectively while gaining insights into the actions and motivation of people while sorting through the clutter of conventional wisdom and taken-for-granted assumptions. One challenge that is faced by researchers while opting for this particular phenomenological approach is that a large amount of data is collected such as jottings, tape recordings, interview data, etc. which need to be analyzed in detail by the researcher.

No clear categories are present in which the data can be categorized, for which the researcher usually has to follow the complicated process in order to find the right answers. A number of links may be potentially created between the observations and discussions. Applying thematic analysis can potentially play a critical role in such type of study.

An important stage is when the data is highly disorganized, such as in the form of unstructured notes, personal texts, or interview transcripts, that need to be given order in order to make sense of the scenario present. The first step is to go through the data and make sense of what is being said through which the key themes can be identified along with issues present. Aggregation can then be carried out of such themes and issues through the help of a mind-map or post-it notes. The resulting list is then further used to interrogate the data and further summarize them such as through participants saying. Points that are left out need to be added through this process. This can help gain a detailed understanding of the process (Hycner, 1985).

Carrying out a review of themes across participants would be easier in the case where physical documents are present in small-scale projects with interviews conducted. However, all researchers are not carried out on a small scale for which an alternative approach is to enter the data into a database using headings to be compared and contrasted, through which identifying relationships between factors and themes would be easier. Phenomenological studies tend to make detailed comments about individual situations that are not feasible for direct generalization for which it is claimed for survey research (Barua, et al, 2015).

If the research wishes to develop general theories, which apply to situations beyond case studies or participants, from phenomenological findings then it needs to be done in a transparent manner to carry validity. This would enable to study of the findings in detail linking with the theory and understanding how he has arrived at the particular interpretations that have been presented. The researcher may not appear 'in person' in

the research, although it may be rare in the case of public domain reports (Moustakas, 1999).

4.4.1 Van Manen Perspective and Hermeneutic Phenomenology

The phenomenology used in qualitative educational research is seen to be significantly misunderstood for a number of reasons. One of the main factors leading to such misunderstanding is that scholars and researchers working in the field tend to copy the dense writing style of philosophical forerunners in phenomenologies such as Husserl, Brentano, Heidegger, Hegel, and Merleau-Ponty (Van Manen, 2002). Human science, which was perceived as rigorous previously, is now willing to adopt a soft and reflective approach in order to bring a variety of meanings to life's phenomena through meditative awareness (Van Manen, 1997). The purpose of human science notions such as subjectivity, objectivity, method, understanding, description, analysis, interpretation, etc. is always understood in a rational perspective. Phenomenology is an example of such a rational perspective.

One of the most commonly agreed-upon definitions for phenomenology is that it is a theoretical viewpoint that advocates the study of the experience of individuals because human behavior is determined by the person's experience rather than being objective and physically describing the external reality (Cohen et al, 2007). It can be described as a methodology aimed at driving meaning for individuals through verbal or written language (Langdrige, 2008; Byale and Brinkmann, 2008). It is a result of sober reflection on the human lived experience, in the sense that reflecting on experience must be thoughtful. It also needs to be free from suppositional, theoretical, and prejudicial intoxications. However, it is also driven by the fascination that will lead to wonder and inquiry leading to a fascination with a meaning.

Four ways have been mentioned by Van Manen through which literature can enhance research. Out of these, the last point mentions the ability of literature to transcend to specific plots and characters that speak about the universality of the human condition.

This makes the transcendental structure of lives available for analysis as well as criticism.

Literature also provides a gateway to researchers through which they can consider ways of doing things that have not occurred to them but have been covered by others in their own research. In the words of Van Manen (1997) “allowing us to set out limits and further transcend these limits of our interpretive sensibilities.” One can access such discourse through literature which will enable one to reflect more deeply on the way researchers have worked on the topic and make sense of the lived experience.

Phenomenology plays a role in informing, transforming, performing, and reforming the relation that exists between being and practice. Explanation of each component is; Inform, plays role in providing thoughtful advice and consultation, Reform, Texts tend to make demand through which own research approach may change, Transform, contains practical value by reaching in the depth of our being, Perform, Reflection of the practice or tactics that are adopted. Researchers in the study would be able to reflect on the essential themes that emerge from an engagement with the description of lived experiences that have been presented in a poetic manner.

Phenomenological themes are seen to relate with structures of existence that hold meaning for the research. Carrying out reflection will help to understand the themes and experiential structure that have made up the experience. The creation of themes provides the researcher with greater control over the research and makes it easier to determine the appropriate written expression. Generally, three approaches are commonly used for isolating thematic aspects of a phenomenon from text which include the holistic approach, the selective approach, and the detailed approach.

The process of engaging in phenomenological research has always been defined as bringing something to speech. This thoughtful process of bringing to speech is most commonly seen to be a writing activity. Writing allows giving form to what is made through thematic analysis and also communicating the essence. The art of writing refers

to the application of language and thought to the phenomenon in the aspect of lived experience to show itself as it is. It is the art of creating and communicating the phenomenological-ontological understanding of the lived experience.

If one wishes to use the hermeneutic type of phenomenology as a research methodology then they has to apply reading of texts and transcripts of spoken accounts of personal experience through which particular themes can be isolated (Van Manen, 1997). These themes separated are described as the interpretations of the lived experience shared. Applying in the context of hermeneutic phenomenology requires the examination of the text in order to discover themes and then reflect before further propagation through writing. After singling out a theme, it is rewritten with the interpretation of its meaning of the lived experience. One may make mistakes in identifying experiences in qualitative research when he is new to hermeneutic phenomenology as a method of analysis. It is difficult to determine whether the person has identified the right theme and whether he has accurately defined the experience of the individual. This makes phenomenology a difficult methodology to apply as it is difficult to get it right due to the complexity seen associated. Smith et al, (2009) have also labeled the phenomenological view to be complex.

4.4.2 Transcendental Phenomenology Advocated by Moustakas

Transcendental phenomenology is another philosophical approach to qualitative research developed by Husserl which aims to understand the human experience (Moustakas, 1994). Since a number of approaches are present that can be used by the qualitative researcher, the question comes up of which approach is the most suitable to the given problem being explored. All approaches that are built on German philosophy, that seek to understand the human experience and overall life, tend to have similar endpoints as they all lead to description (Todres and Wheeler, 2001; Hein and Austin, 2001).

Transcendental phenomenology and hermeneutic phenomenology are two major approaches that represent philosophical assumptions that link with experience and approaches for arranging and analyzing phenomenological data. The differing points of these two approaches include the historical advocates (Husserl or Heidegger), current proponents (Moustakas, 1994, for transcendental phenomenology Van Manen for Hermeneutic Phenomenology), and methodological procedures (Lavery, 2003).

Transcendental phenomenology of science presents a design through data capture that can be carried out of the human experience with meaning present at its core. Hermeneutics on the other hand focuses on the reflective interpretation of the text or study in history through which meaningful understanding can be gained (Moustakas, 1994). Literature is rich in social researches that have applied phenomenological research in a diverse manner. Milligan (2001) has applied the hermeneutical phenomenology in research for the concept of care in male nurses as whereas Shin (2002) has applied this in a study carried out to notice changes in women's bodies at menopause. On the other hand, Padilla (2003) carried out research aligned with the transcendental phenomenology to study women with a head injury, Wright (2003) for the exploration of spirituality among African American women that were in the recovery phase from drugs, Bondas et al, (2001) to explore the experiences of pregnancy among women, and by Kluge (2002) to understand the essence of physically active women that are aged at 65 and older.

Although these researchers show the practical use of these research approaches, a need is present for carrying out further studies through which the procedures can be better understood and organized in a sound process that can be used in further researches. Moustakas (1994) has pointed out that phenomenological analysis tends to use a more structured approach compared to what is used by the hermeneutical writers. He has embraced the standard features of research in human sciences which include the value carried by qualitative research, the emphasis put on the wholeness of experience, and a search for the viewing experience, behavior, and essences of experiences as an integrated and inseparable relationship present between the subject and object.

The transcendental approach is seen to emphasize such features but tends to start off a phenomenological study by setting aside the prejudgements of the researcher to the fullest extent through which a more objective and systematic procedure can be used for analyzing data. The particular term that is used for this process is called “epoche” which is a Greek word that literally means refraining from judgment.

For this reason, the term transcendental has been assigned because the research sees the phenomenon freshly for the first time, making it open to totality. The process of analysing phenomenological data tends to follow a systematic procedure that is rigorous but still accessible to qualitative researchers. The inquirer describes their own experience followed by identifying significant statements from the database of participants to cluster them into units that have a similar meaning. The next step involves the synthesis of these themes into textual and structural descriptions of experience by the individuals followed by constructing a composite narrative that exposes the essences and meanings of the experience. This methodology follows a systematic process for which it has been selected for implementation in the current research of applying ERM across decision-making in the context of a specific country.

Moustakas (1994) has also shed light on the ideas of Husserl relating to transcendental phenomenology. It attempts to remove any such element in the research which would represent a presupposition or prejudgement. One needs to look at things openly without the interference of the habits of the natural world. The key challenge that is faced in this regard is to describe something in the natural setting by understanding the meanings and essence through self-reflection and intuition. Sense is effectively created when the object with our own perception mingles with nature. In the words of Moustakas (1994), “the thing that appears in consciousness is viewed as the absolute reality whereas what appears in the world is absolute learning”. Intentional relation is created between the object of consciousness and the act of consciousness. Intuition can be seen playing an important role in describing the findings. Husserl has given preference to intuition over deduction in his transcendental philosophy.

4.4.3 Strengths and drawbacks of transcendental phenomenology

Moustakas (1994) has provided a systematic approach in transcendental phenomenology through which one can analyze the lived experience of individuals. The Cartesian dualism seen to be present between objectivity and subjectivity is removed by allowing the researcher to develop objective “essence” through aggregating the subjective experience of individuals.

Having a phenomenon to follow and individuals to describe can significantly facilitate the researcher in the process. It creates a concrete framework in form of questions to be asked answers to be recorded.

Since the approach is focused on gaining insight into individual experiences, it will collect data from the voice of the participant rather than those from the researchers or those individuals that have added towards previous literature on that particular topic, an approach that has been consistent in human research. However, specific challenges are also present that need to be noted while adopting this particular methodology. The specific pattern should be present between the essence descriptions, significant statements, and meaning units while the researcher builds a composite explanation through which the general meaning can be better understood.

An illustration can be presented of a study which had a significant statement “whatever good you do to one person is carried out to several others, many more as you got out and get into new relationships” can be narrowed down to a particular theme which is “investing and reinvesting in others” which supports the particular essence of giving. The general perception of the analysis process is that it flows from the detailed to the more general, but there are no checks that can ensure that smooth flow occurs. Furthermore, one may never be able to exhaust all the essence of an experience. The essence statement is seen to be bound by a particular place, time, and experiences of the individuals that are interviewed. Such essence may become more challenging to develop when a heterogeneous group is being targeted through the research when all of them have experienced the phenomenon.

Their experience is seen to vary greatly due to the diversity present in cultural or historical background. This requires achieving the state of epoche, which is a pure state of being consciously present and undertaking a fresh experience, but it is at whole challenging to achieve (Moustakas, 1994). It may not be possible for the researcher to set aside all innate biases and assumptions while purely taking up the experiences of the participants.

A specific language of research needs to be adopted by the researcher in transcendental phenomenology through which the philosophical issue can be better understood and embraced (Husserl, 1931). The above discussion clearly shows how the phenomenological method requires a unique language that incorporates various elements such as horizontalization, intuitive integration, epoche, imaginative variation, structural descriptions, and textural descriptions.

One needs to apply an open approach to understand these terms followed by looking at the appropriate application in the context of the specific study. When applying the hermeneutical phenomenology, elements are removed to reflect the historical, social, and cultural elements in which individuals read and interpret the text present. It is unclear how these are negotiated in include while undertaking study in the phenomenological study (Moustakas, 1994). Reimen (1986) pointed out that other writers on phenomenology tend to have an array of texts in their data collection procedures such as poetry, arts, and music. Moustakas has not provided a clear understanding of how these can be used in addition to interviews or whether they should be used at all. Detailed analysis steps have been suggested by Moustakas along with good illustrations of the method. The approach of phenomenology holds appeal particularly for those individuals in psychology but it also offers an alternative hermeneutical phenomenology which is widely used in human and social sciences.

4.5 Research Design

A cross-sectional study involves the study of outcome and exposure of participants simultaneously. This is unlike cohort studies, in which the participants are selected based on exposure status, and case-control studies, in which participants are selected based on the outcome status. The participants of a cross-sectional study are selected on the basis of the inclusion and exclusion criteria that have been set out beforehand of the study (O'Sullivan, et al, 2010). This approach has been deemed suitable in the current research, given that a particular target population is to be reached out to which includes the board members of firms present in Laos.

Creswell (2003) stated that cross-sectional studies aim to collect data relating to the research problem at a specific point in time. Since most of the data collected refer to a particular point in time, it does not need a time dimension to be taken into account. After the selection of the participants of the study, the researcher will carry out the study to assess the exposure and outcomes through a thematic manner. Cross-sectional designs are mainly applied in population-based surveys through which one can evaluate the prevalence or determination of the trends present.

Curtis et al, (2011) have mentioned two benefits of such a research approach such as being inexpensive in nature and can be carried out with relative speed. Such features were also a strong motivation for adopting the cross-sectional design for understanding the trends of ERM in Laos. Certain variables have been selected for selecting participants. Cross-sectional studies have seen wide application in the case of developmental psychology, but the strong potential for application is also seen in other domains such as education and social science. An example can be taken of the researcher that is carrying out research in developmental psychology who may select a number of participant groups but investigate them at only one point. Using this approach the differences in age groups can be attributed to age differences rather than a difference in the time frame (Flick, 2014). Cross-sectional studies are seen to be observational in descriptive research rather than carrying relational or casual meaning.

O'Leary (2013) mentioned that the researcher collects the data but does not manipulate the variables present. Using this approach can make it easier to describe various characteristics of a community but would prove challenging to understand the cause-and-effect relationship between variables being explored. Such an approach is often applied for making inferences about possible relationships that exist or to collect information that will be used for further experimentation. This is among the main rationales for conducting research on the thesis which will be used for drawing inferences regarding the adoption of ERM as well as its impact.

Cross-sectional studies can be viewed as a snapshot of a certain group of individuals at a particular timeframe. The other type is longitudinal studies that explore a group of variables for an extended period across different points of time, whereas cross-sectional only looks at the present moment (Kumar, 2011). Wide application has been seen of this approach for determining the prevailing characteristics of a population at a certain point in time. An example can be taken off using a cross-sectional study for determining whether exposure to certain risk factors links with certain outcomes. Cross-sectional studies are further divided into two types which are known as descriptive or analytical.

This is an important feature based on which this design has been deemed as appropriate for the determination of ERM adoption trends and the impact that is being noted. The term 'prevalence study' is seen to be widely used when carrying out exploration on the prevalence of particular traits or diseases in a population. An example can be taken of the use of the term 'survey' often when carrying out exploration assessment of attitudes and opinions. Researchers may collect cross-sectional data on current lung cancer diagnosis or smoking habits, which may not help to prove cause-and-effect relation but still provide quick insight into cause-and-effect relation present.

Significant cost savings are also seen associated with the cross-sectional approach as the researcher can collect a large amount of information at a relatively quick pace. The collection of data usually takes place through self-report surveys for which the

researchers can collect a large amount of information from a pool of participants (Johnson and Christensen, 2017). The main difference that can be noted between such type of study with longitudinal studies is the time frame taken. Longitudinal studies are seen to collect data from multiple intervals across a period whereas cross-sectional explore only a single point in time. Since data collection takes place at a number of intervals, one can contemplate the time and resources that will go into this process.

Another major drawback that is seen to emerge while using the longitudinal approach is the phenomenon of selective attrition which refers to the chances of certain participants dropping out of the study which can potentially impact the validity. Maxwell et al, (2008) stated that the chances of participants dropping out is significantly reduced in cross-sectional studies as the data from participants is collected all at once.

4.6 Data Collection and Analysis Methods

4.6.1 Qualitative Method

According to Crotty (1998), methodology describes the plan or sequence of actions that are to be followed while using a particular method. The methodology provides answers to questions that link with what, when, how, and why the data is to be collected as well as analysed. The current section will describe the methodology to be adopted in our own research which explores the link of ERM in decision making in Laos. Methods are seen to define a particular technique or procedure that is to be used for the collection and analysis of data. The current study aims at the collection of data through a qualitative approach. All paradigms can use both qualitative as well as quantitative approaches for the collection of data. The basis of the research methods can be traced to epistemology, ontological position, and methodology.

One can engage in research without being showing explicit or implicit commitment to a particular ontological or epistemological position. Researchers that are seen to differentiate between epistemological and ontological approaches often direct towards differing research approaches that lead to the same phenomenon (Grix, 2004).

Gunzenhauser et al, (2006) mentioned that there is a significant difference between quantitative methodologies as compared to objective quantitative methodologies as they demand rigidity of data collected. Qualitative methodologies aim to portray such a world in which reality is seen to be complex, socially constructed, and versatile (Glesne, 1999).

For this reason, qualitative methodological approaches are seen to be more focused on recognizing the subjective, experiential life-world by providing a description of their own experiences in detail (Patton, 2002). Further looking at the practicality of applying the qualitative research approach, researchers in human sciences give greater emphasis on qualitative research due to its features of text as data and emphasis on drawing meanings and interpretation (Silverman, 1998).

The current study uses a qualitative research design which aims to collect qualitative data mainly through interviews carried out. The qualitative method is used throughout the research such as the use of semi-structured interviews for the collection of data along with applying qualitative content analysis as the main method for data analysis. Investigator triangulation strategy is used as the key strategy for the research. Qualitative research is used with the aim of better understanding the phenomenon by looking through the eyes of individuals that have actually experienced it.

The core advantage which this method holds as compared to qualitative analysis is the richness of data that would be obtained, which provides a clearer view of the world present around us. This would help gain richer data regarding the meanings of the board of directors of Laos regarding the implementation and use of ERM in the company, particularly for enhancing the decision-making process. Using the interpretive method helps to generate greater insight and understanding regarding the behavior and provide explanations for actions from the perspective of the participant. A range of methods can be used such as focus groups, open-ended interviews, open-ended questionnaires, open-ended observations, role-playing, and think-aloud protocol.

The application of these methods helps produce qualitative data which are further analysed through the interpretation of the researcher. The researcher needs to make a precise schedule to be followed along with a precise value system from the outset. Research can be regarded as suitable if it results in rich evidence along with justifiable accounts regarding its internal validity, can be replicated by other people and the research findings can be replicated in a dependable manner (Richie and Lewis, 2003). Certain critique has also been raised against the qualitative approach such as being overly descriptive, generating results that are not justifiable and lacking analytical rigor (George, et al, 2005). Despite these drawbacks, there are certain benefits that also need to be taken into account associated with qualitative research such as the transparency it provides regarding the research process and data analysis (Bryman, 2004). A certain level of flexibility can also be seen present in qualitative methods as they allow a greater level of spontaneity and adaption of interaction that takes between study participant and the researcher. It allows the participant to provide a rather precise answer in his own clear words.

The same level of freedom is not provided to the participant in quantitative research as they generally have to select from a number of fixed responses (Mack, et al, 2005). Both cross-sectional and cross-cultural qualitative research design has been included in the current research. Cross-sectional design refers to the collection of data from the subset of a population for a specific period (Bryman, 2004).

One major differing factor between the qualitative and quantitative research design is the chances present of bias from the researcher. The lack of flexibility and control makes it increasingly difficult for the researcher to evaluate the researcher's biases for qualitative studies. The study design considered can be labeled as appropriate in each of the paradigms for finding different things. Ranjit (2010) mentioned that qualitative research tends to be more suitable when one wishes to explore diversity and variation in any aspect of human life.

The qualitative method is the primary method that is used for exploratory research as it helps to attain understanding and knowledge regarding motivations, hidden causes and opinions present behind a particular process (Creswell, 2012). The researcher can also gain insight into the inside facts of a problem and help bring about the development of new ideas, concepts, or hypotheses which can be potentially researched in the future.

Since the objective being pursued by the researcher is to extract views and insight from experienced individuals that are working in academic institutions through which objectivity can be pursued, qualitative research would be able to play an effective role. Using this approach also allows the researcher to dive deeper into the issue and drive out key trends, opinions, and thought processes linking with the topic. Methodologies used in qualitative research tend to vary from unstructured to semi-structured forms. Some of the techniques that are used under this method include focus groups, participation, interviews, and observation. The current research requires one-on-one interaction of the researcher with the board of directors across the Laos companies.

Applying the qualitative research approach through interviews seems to be appropriate according to the needs of the current study. The sample size taken in such research is seen to be smaller and is selected by fulfilling a particular quota (Kumar, 2014). Qualitative research is seen to recognize the value present in the value, setting, and context in which the participants frame the scenario. The interaction present between the researcher and participant in the research field also tends to play an important role in influencing the research process as well as its outcomes.

Applying the qualitative approach in research tends to recognize the interplay present between multiple views and voices while attempting to study them. The mapping of reality and knowledge is also facilitated through this process. However, this knowledge cannot be properly understood without understanding the meaning that is assigned by individuals to the knowledge by taking into account their actions, feelings, beliefs, and thoughts (Illingworth, 2006). In the qualitative approach, the construction of knowledge relates to the philosophical underpinnings which have been selected by the researcher,

mainly relating to the selection of the on-site or online collection of data. A number of approaches are present which the researcher can select from for conducting the qualitative research, mainly aiming for getting richer and detailed data on a specific topic or problem.

4.6.2 Interviews

The interview can be defined as the conversation between the researcher and participant aimed at gaining a deeper understanding of the research topic. Several researchers have deemed qualitative research interviews as highly viable and often utilized data collection tools (Jamshed, 2014; DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2004). Although a range of interview formats are available for researchers today, the semi-structured interview format has become the most recognized approach which is becoming increasingly prevalent in medical education research.

It provides the researcher with the opportunity to explore the matter in-depth and take into account the unique experiences of the interviewees through which one can better understand how one perceives and experiences the different phenomenon of interest. In the relation existing between the participant and researcher in this approach, emphasis is always put on the exploration of the human phenomenon, and interviews have been seen to carry a strong link with qualitative research and the naturalistic paradigm (Halcomb and Davidson, 2006; Cote and Turgeon, 2005). The use of qualitative interviewing as a data collection tool has been seen in the methodology of a range of researches while aiming to gain answers for specific research questions.

The qualitative research interviews are deemed suitable in scenarios where the researcher wishes to gain insight into the subjective perspective which the participant carries relating to the particular phenomenon rather than gaining insight into the generalisable understanding of groups of people. An example can be taken of applying the qualitative interview approach in exploring the experience of an employee or

discrimination and gaining better insight into the environment that he has to face in the workplace (Rowley, 2012). Qualitative interviews can be more or less structured or open. Unstructured or semi-structured interview approaches are seen to carry only a few pre-determined questions which allow the interviewer to explore the issue in detail which has been brought forward by the interviewee. Laksoy et al, (2017) stated that it is necessary to align the methodological approach with the interview guide.

On the other hand, the structured interview approach is seen to carry a set of predetermined questions that are posed in the same manner to all participants which are being phrased in the same manner. In medical education, the application of semi-structured interviews has often been seen in the medical research field which includes several predetermined questions. However, the interviewer can still dig deep into the responses of the interviewee through follow-up questions (Lingard and Kennedy, 2010). The interview should generally start off with a few easy questions through which the overall mood of the interview can be set out by becoming comfortable with the subject. A few questions that can be asked for easing how the interview include: “how long have you been working here?”, “Why did one become involved in this particular field?” or “how has the workload been recently in the organization?”. These would be answered more considerately as compared to other questions that would link more directly with the research topic. Questions for ending the interview should also be selected carefully such as “is there anything more you would like to add.”

Nimmon et al, (2016) pointed out that carrying out an analysis of cultural and power dimensions at the start of the interview can play an important role. Such analysis would make it easier to understand the situation that a particular scenario affords as well as the potential barriers that may come up. The individuals are viewed as cultural beings and can have different expectations regarding the interview scenario (Rogoff, 2003). Some people might view the interview as an invasive or difficult situation, whereas others may require the presence of a third person such as interpreter or culturally sensitive individual to understand the position of the interviewee.

4.6.3 Sampling Approach

The purposive (non-probability) sampling approach will be used in this study. The reason behind using a purposive approach is that not all industries and companies are ready to use ERM in Laos or are not capable or required to use an ERM approach. Therefore, the purposive approach will allow the researcher to use specific pre-requisite criteria while selecting the sample size.

Two different industries have been targeted for this purpose that is performing well financially in Laos. Tourism and construction are the two industries that have been selected. Ten firms each from both sectors have been chosen which is reasonable given the time and resources available for completing this study. Since, Laos is not a big country and does not possess extensive number of companies operating in the tourism and construction industries due to which it was feasible to keep the sample size of the firms to 10 for each industry.

The purposive and non-probability sampling approach has allowed the researcher to include only those individuals who are board members in the companies that are operating in the tourism and construction industries across Laos. Moreover, no differentiation on the basis of gender, sexual orientation, religion and other such factors was carried out which means that for qualifying as a potential respondent, it was imperative to be a part of board of directors. In addition, the inclusion of respondents in the data collection process was purely based on the availability of the board members and access of the researcher because it was not pragmatically possible to access and communicate with all the board members. Logistically and resource wise it was not possible to include more number of respondents, also professional engagements and commitments of board members and few other factors indicated the access and availability challenges. Moreover, several companies already had a smaller board size which naturally gave less options in terms of the availability of potential respondents. These reasons are also the justification for including 10 companies from each sector instead of less number of companies.

Those firms performing well on financial grounds will be selected because these firms will require the use of ERM more than other firms, as good financial performance needs the support of effective strategies and decision making consistently. Such firms also face intense challenges internally and externally because their operations are expanded, and their scale of functions is larger than other firms. For these reasons, these firms are more vulnerable to risk, and most other companies see them as their competitors.

Semi-structured interviews have been used to collect data because they allow the collection of in-depth information. It enabled the researcher to socially construct the findings in light of the information supplied by respondents. The intention initially has been to include at least two respondents (board members/ directors) from every selected company in the data collection process, which can make total participants number 40.

As per literature review findings and observation of recently conducted qualitative studies, it was noticed that 25-30 is the average number of respondents used by researchers. Therefore, the intention later on was to collect at least 25 interviews. Personal contacts will be used as gatekeepers, i.e., for arranging interview time/meetings with relevant respondents. However, during the process of data collection some major challenges were being faced and COVID-19 being the most prominent challenge in this regard which restricted the total number of respondents 20 from whom complete interviews were conducted. The physical or online availability of potential respondents was another major challenge due to their busy and hectic schedule. Moreover, it also happened that some board members were not willing or comfortable towards engaging in data collection process in the form of interviews. Given the constraints posed by COVID-19, it appears that the collection of 20 responses is a positive effort towards data analysis and findings of this study.

4.6.4 Data Analysis

ensure there are clear links to the sources informing the approach undertaken by referencing accurately to defend the design.

The analysis of qualitative research notes begins in the field, at the time of observation, interviewing, or both, as the researcher identifies problems and concepts that appear likely to help understand the situation (Miles and Huberman, 2012). Reading the notes or transcripts is an essential step in the analytic process because it gives an real time insight into the subjective opinion and perception expressed by the respondents. The cross-sectional nature of the design requires the use of audio or textual recording of the responses being given by the respondents (Willig, 2011).

The data collection process from qualitative study mostly involves writing down during an interview or in the field from feelings, comments, and observations that are reconstructed or text is transcribed from audiotapes. Researchers can make notes during the interview or audio record the interview with the permission of the respondents as an initial step towards conducting qualitative data analysis. Notes taking is considered important even if audio recording is being used because using this method the element of observation can be addressed which is a useful aspect of cross-sectional design (Guest et al, 2013).

In the words of Diamond (1993), "The basic data are these observations and conversations, the actual words of people reproduced to the best of the ability from the field notes". Documentation can be labeled as the first step of the analysis. Range of data relating to participants can be recorded such as the written documents, interviews, various contacts, and other information which is saved in the form of a list. The process of documentation holds significant value in qualitative researchers such as keeping track of the rapidly growing volume of information and providing a way for developing an outline for the analytical process. This further encourages the process of strategizing and conceptualizing the text present. This process of documentation can ensure that the researcher is not influencing the variables identified during the interview process and therefore keeping the analysis of variables relevant and to the point (Miles et al, 2013).

Thematic analysis method has been adopted in this study. The descriptive nature of the qualitative approach tends to allow the researcher to build a complex, holistic picture in a natural setting, and thematic analysis can help in doing so. To increase the consistency of the coding process, multiple coders should be used (Miles and Huberman, 2000). Therefore, this study will intend to use multiple codes in line with the nature of the results gathered. Having such a measure in place for quality assurance ensured that interpretations and coding schemes clearly represent the data. The keywords used by the respondents will be included in this process for determining the themes i.e., conserving the actual subjective responses of the respondents in the analysis process.

Identifying and defining these themes will lead to interpretations that will be analyzed in the light of theoretical framework and literature review findings. It is advisable to take the appropriate time when coding, for it is foundational to the data analysis process and should not be rushed. Therefore, the thematic coding will be undertaken gradually in line with the results gathered and the literature review presented.

The researcher has ensured that the process being adopted is transparent, i.e., by setting out the clear process to be followed (credibility), sharing optimum detail regarding the content through which readers can determine the generalisability (transferability), indicating the presence of consistency in research to show repeatability (dependability), and ensure that results presented are free from the biases of the researcher (confirmability). Aligning the data collection methods with the research questions and objectives established earlier is necessary in order to obtain results that correlate with findings that have been previously published in literature.

4.7 Ethical Considerations

For adhering to the ethical considerations, this study will follow the standard academic research practices such as data privacy, anonymity, data security and voluntary participation of the respondents. Guidelines of the University's ethics committee will be

adhered to and understood. A formal consent form will be used for taking the approval of each participant to be involved in the data collection process. The identity and names of respondents will not be revealed. Ethics can be understood simply as morals or rules of conduct.

Certain core elements are seen shared by various policies and legislation which relate with research ethics and greater human rights which include autonomy, safety, dignity, protection, maximization of benefits and minimization of harm (Bloor and Wood, 2008). A range of ethical concerns can be raised due to the relationship and intimacy that exists between the researcher and participant in qualitative research.

The qualitative researcher also faced the dilemma of maintaining the privacy of participants, establishing open and honest interactions, and do not take part in intentional misrepresentation.

Ethical considerations have a special place in research today. The current section looks at various ethical implications that may be raised in the current study. Creswell (2012) has stated that the research scholar needs to endorse and obey the goals set out for the research, providing genuine information with certainty that does not hold any inaccuracy. Taking into account the ethical considerations also allow the research also allow collaborative working with peers, mentors, and other sponsors of the study. The study also requires mutual respect, trust, fairness, and responsibility with all the people that are involved in the study (Bless and Higson-Smith, 2011). Likewise, appropriate use of public reserves as well as the acquisition of general provisions is also significant.

4.7.1 Informed consent

The concept of informed consent mentions that the participants of the research should be able to make a knowledgeable decision regarding their participation in research. Achieving consent may be desirable but may not always be necessary for all scenarios. An example can be taken of covert researches in which participants do not know that they are being studied, or the process of observing behavior in the public domain may

also be carried out without taking prior consent (British Psychological Society, 1993). The justification that can be presented for this exception is ensuring that the behavior of the participants is to be studied in the natural context without the interference of aims and objectives set out by the researcher. Most social science and health researchers are seen to demand informed consent from the participants.

The process of obtaining consent may involve the researcher going to communities and sharing the details of the researcher or individually providing participants with the information sheet as well as the consent form to be signed.

Egdorf and Raho (1994) obtained research from their computer-mediated communication groups before research the publicly available archives and lists. Using such material without taking proper consent from the authors could have proved to be damaging to the research process, especially when group members come to know that their research has been used without prior knowledge or proper consent. Important recognition has been gained by informed consent in the different fields of research. It is of utmost importance for qualitative researchers to specify the nature of data to be collected along with how it will be used. The principle of informed consent emphasizes the responsibility of the researcher to inform participants regarding different aspects of the research language which may usually be incomprehensible. Clarifications should be provided on: potential role of participants, financing body, identity of the researcher, role of participants and method of publishing the results (Hedgecoe, 2008).

4.8 Chapter Summary

This chapter was dedicated to identifying the devised research strategy for the current study. The researcher has presented the paradigm that is required to be followed as interpretivism. The researcher aims to use qualitative research due to its convenience and relevance with the aims and objectives of the study. The interviews will be conducted with two respondents (board members/ directors) from every selected company included in the data collection process, making total participants number 20. Ethical aspects of the study have been presented and addressed by the researcher.

5 Chapter5 Results, Discussions and Interpretations

The results have been obtained by interviewing a total of 20 participants who are working in construction and tourism firms across Laos. The firms that have been selected in this regard are based on multiple ownership due to more than one broad member. The transcript of the participants is provided in the appendices. The results have been gathered in the form of transcripts, and the transcripts are then reduced into meaningful themes and keywords. Various keywords are representing one sub-themes, and various sub-themes are presenting a major theme. A total of six major themes have been derived from the transcripts and responses given by the participants. The discussion below shows the keywords and themes extracted from the interview is also presented in appendices. The sector-wise analysis has been presented in the results.

5.1 Themes form Construction

Key words	Sub-themes	Major Themes
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It is always the best for the business to be aware of the risk when they run the business. 2. Traditional way is used to identify their risk, so they would look at the market, look at the consumptions, and trends. 3. Risk is not contextualized accurately. 4. Joint plan model has become more. 5. ERM process of making Plan, or response to the risk rationally, in order to avoid losing profit and facing bankrupt. 	Traditional Risk Management Plan Contextualization of Risk Adaption	Risk Planning

<p>6. ERM helps in being prepared for low season or natural attack, for instance covid-19 or natural disaster.</p> <p>7. To ensure efficient ERM and therefore also being more accountable towards donors and the parliaments ERM approaches of all donors need to be harmonised, so following a parliament ERM rather than ERMs of each donor.</p>		
<p>8. During covid-19 crisis, they cannot handle the change, so they have to get out of the market.</p> <p>9. Assess and predict the risk that would affect their business</p> <p>10. Advocate the tiff of practical of risk management plan</p> <p>11. EMR is necessary for every company that have more than 50-100 employers- Risks are unavoidable but we can make preparation plan to be ready for the.</p> <p>12. You may have risk analyse and you may come out with the plan to manage properly, and you need to prevent and avoiding unpredict risk.</p>	<p>Formal procedures</p> <p>Informal procedures</p> <p>Financial Risk</p> <p>Performance Risk</p> <p>Risk related decision making</p>	<p>Risk Identification</p>
<p>13. The market size in Laos and the fact that they cannot export to oversee that much.</p> <p>14. I think for those small and medium firm when we talk about enterprise risk management it sounds unfamiliar to them.</p> <p>15. Many enterprises show extremely low</p>	<p>Funds</p> <p>Infrastructure</p> <p>Skills</p> <p>Knowledge, Understanding</p> <p>Exposure</p>	<p>Resources and Capabilities</p>

<p>willingness to embrace ERM due to cost.</p> <p>16. SMEs do not have resources, by resources I mean financial and Human resources.</p> <p>17. Sometimes legal compliance should be the risk for them that they could be ordered to shut down the business.</p> <p>18. Firms just identify it, but they do not have plan to deal with it in term of managing the risk.</p> <p>19. the people of the country need to assess risks on a regular basis, continuously and on different levels: political risks, structural risks, management risks.</p> <p>20. Using donor funds needs a strict ERM to be highly transparent towards the entity itself (using and spending the funds), the respective donor and the 'taxpayers' of the respective country, donor funds come from.</p>		
<p>21. Leadership play a brutal part and I think it also depends on the culture perspective.</p> <p>22. Who are not oversea educated they would think let's play it by ears and handle things when it comes?</p> <p>23. Leadership is more well prepare for any risk that might harm or effect business operation.</p> <p>24. The owners do not really understand the concept of Risk Management or ERM</p>	<p>Risk aversion</p> <p>Risk taking</p> <p>Leadership Bias and Background</p> <p>Past experiences</p> <p>Subjectivity</p> <p>Scope of ERM</p>	<p>Leadership Style</p>

<p>25. Leaders do not analyse the situation and that lead to mitigation plan is not really practical.</p> <p>26. Leadership helps in making big projects decision, the head of each department are invited to the meeting and will be using majority voices to write proposal.</p> <p>27. The proposal will be sent to the owner, then the owner will decide the suitable solution.</p> <p>28. We can use every single suggestion to criticize than compare the suitable idea.</p>		
<p>29. you may have risk analyse and you may come out with the plan to manage properly and you need to prevent and avoiding unpredict risk.</p> <p>30. they mainly look at the financial perspective for example: the flow of the funds, the funds could undermine their business for instance if they cannot get the loan from the bank.</p> <p>31. Supply chain could come into play when they run the business for example the international companies.</p> <p>32. When it comes to enterprise risk management it's very problematic and they don't take it seriously due to the resources, the capacities of our own employee.</p> <p>33. The lockdown of the Laos PDR from the 29 March 2020 (Prime Ministers Decree</p>	<p>Risk analysis Financial aspects Challenges Impact of COVID</p>	<p>Benefits of ERM</p>

<p>No 06, 29 March 2020) on due to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic was an unforeseen risk threaten the implementation of NA/PPA – donor support.</p> <p>34.It is quite hard to make decision on an unclear project</p> <p>35.There might be a special agreement between employer and employees to decrease working hours and wages in order for company to survive.</p> <p>36.Covid-19 may have direct affect to goods and supplies; hence risks are miscalculated</p>		
<p>37.Firms are not familiar with ERM</p> <p>38.ERM seems to complicate the operations in small firms</p>	<p>Behaviours Challenges</p>	<p>Organization al Culture</p>

5.2 Themes form Tourism

Key words	Sub-themes	Major Themes
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Companies may have plan for risk aversion without ERM at small level. 2. Traditional way is used to identify their risk, so they would look at the market, look at the consumptions, and trends. 3. Follow the trend rather than forward thinking or planning ahead. 4. Risk is not contextualized accurately. 	<p>Traditional Risk Management Plan</p> <p>Contextualization of Risk</p> <p>Adaption</p>	<p>Risk Planning</p>

<p>5. Adopt Risk Management because things are changing in Laos, the Covid-19</p> <p>6. Joint plan model has become more.</p> <p>7. Our company was not well-prepared for the virus attack, so we received announcement from Government and have to arrange the urgent meeting to discuss.</p>		
<p>8. Big firms have very good business plan; they have their own risk assessment and Risk mitigation plan in place.</p> <p>9. SMEs they usually use the financial pressure to define the risk and to make decision what should come next.</p> <p>10. EMR is necessary for every company that have more than 50-100 employers- Risks are unavoidable but we can make preparation plan to be ready for the.</p> <p>11. Every project can be risky, but the decision will be considered upon environment that impacts incomes.</p>	<p>Formal procedures</p> <p>Informal procedures</p> <p>Financial Risk</p> <p>Performance Risk</p> <p>Risk related decision making</p>	<p>Risk Identification</p>
<p>12. Many enterprises show very low willingness to embrace ERM due to cost</p> <p>13. During COVID-19 crisis they don't know how to deal with this situation because they don't have any risk mitigation strategy like they don't calculate what is the worst case.</p> <p>14. Try to contextualise ERM to make it suitable for SMEs.</p> <p>15. The government should raise the</p>	<p>Funds</p> <p>Infrastructure</p> <p>Skills</p> <p>Knowledge,</p> <p>Understanding</p> <p>Exposure</p>	<p>Resources and Capabilities</p>

<p>awareness of Risk management for those SMEs</p> <p>16.SMEs do not have resources, by resources I mean financial and Human resources.</p> <p>17.Sometimes legal compliance should be the risk for them that they could be ordered to shut down the business.</p> <p>18.The detailed policy for risk management at programme and project level is currently under development.</p>		
<p>19.Leadership play a brutal part and I think it also depends on the culture perspective</p> <p>20.Who are not oversea educated they would think let's play it by ears and handle things when it comes</p> <p>21.Leadership is more well prepare for any risk that might harm or effect business operation.</p> <p>22.The owners do not really understand the concept of Risk Management or ERM</p>	<p>Risk aversion Risk taking Leadership Bias and Background Past experiences Subjectivity Scope of ERM</p>	<p>Leadership Style</p>
<p>23.Supply chain could come into play when they run the business for example the international companies.</p> <p>24.When it comes to enterprise risk management it's very problematic and they don't take it seriously due to the resources, the capacities of our own employee.</p> <p>25.It is necessary to use the concept of ERM in some certain situation, but our company</p>	<p>Risk analysis Financial aspects Challenges Impact of COVID</p>	<p>Benefits of ERM</p>

<p>didn't implement it in an appropriate way</p> <p>26.The Laos company is still depending heavily of donor support.</p> <p>27.Donors themselves need to follow a strict ERM. So, the 'implementer or beneficiary' (of donor support) and the donor itself need to assess 'possible' risks</p> <p>28.It is quite hard to make decision on an unclear project</p> <p>29.Even if company have plan for the effects, there would still be advantages and disadvantages, mostly disadvantages- Due to lockdown and closed borders,</p> <p>30.Covid-19 has negative effect to our business.</p> <p>31.There might be a special agreement between employer and employees to decrease working hours and wages in order for company to survive.</p> <p>32.Covid-19 may have direct affect to goods and supplies; hence risks are miscalculated</p>		
<p>33.ERM seems to complicate the operations in small firms</p> <p>34.Leaders have adopted risk or the business models or even ERM into the organisational culture</p> <p>35.Adopt the Enterprise Risk management step by step in culture</p>	<p>Behaviours</p> <p>Expectations</p> <p>Decisions</p> <p>Challenges</p>	<p>Organization al Culture</p>

Risk Planning is a theme developed in this chapter for which keywords are presented in the table earlier, however this theme is supported by academic literature as well i.e., Mishra et al, (2019) and Buczkowski, (2021) have mentioned about the importance of this theme in their respective studies. Moreover, another theme 'ERM Benefits' has been supported by Buczkowski, (2021) by stating that ERM creates enhanced value for the organizations operating in different industries. Mishra et al, (2019) mentioned that risk identification is an ongoing process and the proposed framework allows organizations to handle increasing complex risks and/or identifying them based on how the organizational resources may be exposed over time.

Risk Identification is another theme developed in this chapter as presented in the table earlier and this theme holds the support not only from interview responses but also from literature sources. For example, the studies conducted by Dittfeld et al, (2021) and Moorhead et al, (2021) found that the design stage of standard operation procedures of organizations requires risk identification and for providing the organization with a chance of developing feasible structure and risk treatment tool towards the emerging risks. They also mentioned about the use of advanced IT systems and information systems in the organization for keeping a close eye on different risk sources which provides support for the 'resources and capabilities' theme as well which is also supported by Dellana et al, (2022) as they mentioned about allocating significant funds for possessing required resources for effective risk management.

Mishra et al, (2019) argued that risk identification is an ongoing process and relevant risk management framework allows organizations to handle increasingly complex risks and/or identifying them based on how the organizational resources may be exposed over time. Managers could use a form of risk control analytics (monitoring dashboard of all identified risks under each interaction sets on a regular basis) to become more proactive in managing risk or exploiting opportunities across enterprise. Hunziker and Durrer, (2021) along with Abu Afifa and Saleh, (2021) have stressed on the availability of the resources and capabilities for pursuing risk management formally, strategically and systematically. Their findings support the identification of this theme in the study in line with interview results as the key terms/quotes are presented in the table earlier.

Young, (2022), Grieser and Pedell, (2021) and Avery et al, (2021) have argued about the use of strong leadership styles and have indicated that board leaders have to be prepared for different risk situations and they need to exhibit relevant leadership skills and styles for managing risks effectively. Their studies have assisted and validated the establishment of 'Leadership role' theme in this study.

Bento et al, (2018) stressed that internal control aspects of ERM plays a central role in making ERM activities effective in relation with risk treatment and prevention. Therefore, it is imperative for organizations for develop ERM culture which is also open towards challenging discussions related to risk and then possesses the information system support for adequate functioning. This notion is also supported by Crovini et al, (2021) and they added one more perspective by stating that a supportive culture towards ERM is important for reaching high compliance towards diverse type of risks.

Maffei and Spanò, (2021) and Crovini et al, (2021) have stressed on the support of middle and top management for implementing risk management systems in the organizations by indicating that decision making from management can instil a sense of ownership and direction across employees for driving risk management systems. Tan and Lee, (2022) have further added to this perspective by concluding that specific risk management teams are vital to be allocated by top management for encouraging a supportive culture of risk management which will enable the optimal use of ERM. Hassan et al, (2022) stated that corporate managers and policymakers must get the required support and encouragement for taking decisions in the favor of systematic risk management implementation. Moreover, they stated that risk culture needs to be promoted by policymakers especially by developing supportive strategies. These perspectives of contemporary literature have helped in developing most of the themes in this study that are presented in the table earlier by aligning them with responses of the interview respondents.

5.3 Themes Extracted from Construction Sector

Risk Planning

From the identified themes, it can be said that the participants have highlighted various elements pertaining to the use of risk management systems in a firm. From the findings, it is presented that the first theme is Risk Planning, which is presented by the sub-themes “Traditional Risk Management Plan”, “Contextualisation of Risk”, and “Adoption”. From these subthemes, it is presented that the firms are required to reduce the risk of traditional risk management systems.

Participant 2 from Galliford Try mentioned that:

“ERM helps in being prepared for the low season or natural attack, for instance, covid-19 or natural disaster”. Considering their discussion, it is evidence that the firms in Laos are unable to deal with the threats and understand why they need ERM to be implemented in their firm. This indicated that the usability of ERM is still not common in Laos, and there is a need to implement it. A quotation from his interview is pasted below.

“A business can face certain risks including financial, transportation-related threats, risks of not meeting goals, and risks related to sales targets. In my company, I will prefer to reduce possible risks through different policies.”

The last subtheme in this regard is risk adoption. The participants presented that there is a need for the firm to be more adaptive with the risks, as the covid-19 is negatively impacting businesses. In this regard, participants from Barratt and Interserve mentioned that “it’s always the best for the business to be aware of the risk when they run the business.”

Participants from construction businesses i.e., Interserve and Kier presented that “Companies may have a plan for risk aversion without ERM at small level”. This mentions that being adapted with the use of ERM is imperative because the firms are not adapted with ERM, the implementation may not help the firm.

Moreover, participant from Kier mentioned that “To ensure efficient ERM and therefore also to be more accountable towards donors and the parliaments” and “ERM

approaches of all donors need to be harmonised, so following a parliament ERM rather than ERMs of each donor”. From this, it is evident that the use of ERM can help the stakeholders to understand how risks can be mitigated, which may prove to be beneficial for the firm.

Risk Identification

The second major theme that was identified from the interviews was “Risk Identification”, which was based on five sub-themes. The first sub-theme was “Formal Procedures”, which are carried out while implementing ERM in a firm. The participants presented that firms may have “formal business plans” that help the firms in the mitigation of risk. The participants also presented those informal procedures also facilitate the firm in mitigating risk, as they present the practices of SMEs by “they usually use the financial pressure to define the risk and to make a decision what should come”, which means that ERM is also facilitated by informal procedures of a firm. Participant from Kier presented that “covid-19 crisis, they can’t handle the change, so they have to get out of the market”, and seven presented that “Assess and predict the risk that would affect their business”. This means that during covid-19, the risks have been increased, but informal methods have helped the firms in Laos to be more receptive to risks and able to identify them. Moreover, the companies also identify risks with the help of financial risk assessment. Participants presented that with the help of finances, the SMEs “Assess and predict the risk that would affect their business”.

A quotation from the interview of participant from Barratt is given below illustrating the importance of theme.

“In the recent annual meeting, we divided our goals into short and long-term goals. This method assists us in implementing strategies and accomplishing our main objective efficiently. It also plays a vital role in reducing and preventing the risks involved. I can provide an example of it. Presently our target is to accomplish 30% of the annual sale goal by the end of the first quarter.”

One participant from Balfour Beatty mentioned that “Advocate the tiff of practical of risk management plan”. This means that ERM helps in financial risk management for the firm. Another participant presented that “ERM is necessary for every company that have more than 50-100 employers- Risks are unavoidable, but we can make preparation plan to be ready for the”. This presents that ERM also helps in the identification of performance risk, which is the 4th theme of the major theme.

Resources and Capabilities

The next major theme is “Resources and Capabilities”, which is based on “Funds Infrastructure”, “Skills”, “Knowledge”, “Understanding”, and “Exposure”. It has been presented in this theme that ERM helps in improving various capabilities in a firm by helping them in managing resources in a better way. ERM facilitates in managing the way finances work in an organisation, employees’ skills management, their knowledge up-gradation and understanding towards how different functions of business work. It also helps in providing them with exposure to the way ERM works in various SMEs and other firms in Laos.

On the other hand, the participants have also presented mixed views on the knowledge and understanding as a resource improved by ERM in the firms of Laos. One participant has mentioned that try to contextualise “ERM to make it suitable for SMEs”. Whereas the other participants presented that “The government should raise the awareness of Risk management for those SMEs”. All these responses refer to the fact that ERM helps in improving the overall knowledge in the firm and suggested that more awareness related to risk management should be presented. Participant from Galliford Try presented that “the people of the country need to assess risks regularly, continuously and on different levels: political risks, structural risks, management risks.” And “Using donor funds needs a strict ERM to be highly transparent towards the entity itself (using and spending the funds), the respective donor and the ‘taxpayers’ of the respective country, donor funds come from”.

These responses pertain to the fact that understanding and exposure of ERM help the firms in Laos to improve transparency and manage structural risks, which will improve the overall understanding of how risk can be managed with ERM in the Laos firms. Lastly, on the exposure, participants from Galliford Try, Balfour Beatty and Interserve presented that:

“The detailed policy for risk management at programme and project level is currently under development”, “Sometimes legal compliance should be the risk for them that they could be ordered to shut down the business” and “Firms just identify it, but they don’t have the plan to deal with it in term of managing the risk”. Considering such responses of respondents, it can be said that ERM helps the employees and firms in Laos in having exposure to how planning can be done to manage risks. Further, a quotation from interview of participant from Interserve is given below:

“As I mentioned, compliance and policy will help our company to reduce and prevent all those risk that we might facing. For instance, compliance and policy will mention all those rules, roles and job description (JD), what is the CEO, CFO role and power, what are our missions and visions, so all those things are the key tools to minimise and prevent risks in order to help company performance and gain advantage foe stakeholders.”

Leadership Style

Leadership style is presented as a critical element in the implementation of ERM for the firms of Laos. The sub-themes for this major theme are “Risk aversion”, “Risk-taking”, “Leadership Bias and Background”, “Past experiences”, “Subjectivity”, and “Scope of ERM”. From all these themes, it can be presented that leadership played a critical role in the process of implementation of ERM. Participants have given various responses towards these themes, that range forms the positive role of leadership towards a more

subjective stance that leadership has been using for implementation of ERM and effective risk management.

Participant from Balfour Beatty mentioned that “Leadership play a brutal part, and I think it also depends on the culture perspective”, which presents that leadership act in line with the culture of the firm for risk management. Participant from Galliford Try mentions that “Who are not overseas educated they would think let’s play it by ears and handle things when it comes”, whereas Barratt and Interserve presented that leadership is more well prepared for any risk that might harm or affect business operation” and “The owners don’t understand the concept of Risk Management or ERM”. This means that the leadership’s knowledge regarding risk management is still limited in Laos, due to which they are unable to implement it properly, and negatively impacting the process.

Further, participant from Kier presented that “Leaders do not analyse the situation and that leads to mitigation plan is not practical” and participant from Barratt mentioned that “Leadership helps in making big projects decision, the head of each department is invited to the meeting and will be using majority voices to write a proposal.” From these responses, it has been presented in the case of firms working in Laos that leadership style has been critical in the implementation of ERM. The leadership has not been able to take risks and also to present biased behaviour towards ERM. The leadership is unable to understand the scope of ERM due to limited knowledge on the topic, due to which they are impacting the entire process negatively in the firms of Laos. This highlights the need for change in the behaviour presented by the leadership.

Benefits of ERM

The next theme that has been derived out of the responses given by participants is the benefits of ERM. The participants have presented various benefits of using ERM that involve “Risk analysis”, “Financial aspects”, “Challenges” and “Impact of COVID”. Participant 1 has mentioned that “you may have risk analyse and you may come out

with the plan to manage properly”, participant from Barratt presented that “Supply chain could come into play when they run the business, for example, the international companies” and participant from Galliford Try presented that “It is necessary to use the concept of ERM in some certain situation”.

Organizational Culture

These responses present that ERM can help in dealing with risk effectively, and firms must use risk management tools. Participants from Interserve and Kier presented that “implementer or beneficiary’ (of donor support) and the donor itself need to assess ‘possible’ risks with ERM”, which presents that it is not just beneficial for firms in Laos but also suitable for stakeholders. Participant from Kier mentioned that “Even if the company have a plan for the effects, there would still be advantages and disadvantages,” which means that ERM may have a few disadvantages, even if the risk has been evaluated properly. Similarly, participant from Balfour Beatty presented challenges of ERM as “It is quite hard to decide on an unclear project mostly disadvantages”, which means that ERM may not prove to be helpful in unclear projects. Lastly, participant from Barratt presented that “Covid-19 may have a direct effect to goods and supplies; hence risks are miscalculated”, which means that COVID-19 have also impacted the calculations of risk management, due to which ERM may not prove to be as helpful in the firms of Laos.

5.4 Themes Extracted from Tourism

Risk Planning, Risk Identification and Leadership Style

The participants presented that in Laos, traditional risk management systems are still being used, but their usability is questioned due to their incapability of assessing risk. Participant 1 from Collette presented those traditional methods “Follow the trend rather than forward-thinking or planning”, participant 2 from Trafalgar presented that “Companies may have a plan for risk aversion without ERM at small level”, which makes traditional methods less fruitful. Concerning the “contextualisation of risk”, the participant highlighted that “Risk is not contextualised accurately”. Another participant presented that “Adopt Risk Management because things are changing in Laos, the Covid-19”. This means that due to external forces, such as COVID-19, the risks are not being contextualised in the firms in Laos, which may be a cause due to which the use of modern ERM is critical for the firm.

Similarly, participants 4 and 5 presented that the “Joint venture model has become more common” and “ERM process of making Plan, or response to the risk rationally, to avoid losing profit and facing bankrupt”. Participant 1 mentioned that “You may have risk analyse and you may come out with the plan to manage properly”, which means that unpredicted risks can also be managed in SMEs with the help of ERMs. The last subtheme of this major theme is risk-related decision making, which presents that risk-related decisions can be made with the help of ERM. One participant presented that “decision will be considered upon the environment that impacts incomes”, which means that decisions are made according to the risk, while the other participant mentioned that “Every project can be risky”. This highlights the significance of using ERM for risk identification in the firms of Laos. Further, a quotation from interview of participant from Globus Travels is given below:

“So, the ‘implementer or beneficiary’ (of donor support) and the donor itself need to assess ‘possible’ risks. Designing a support project to the parliaments here in Laos PDR requires project documents, developed by the donor organization/country and the beneficiary. Designing these project documents always include a so called “Risk Log”, where all the ‘possible risks are listed.”

Resources and Capabilities

For the fund's infrastructure, the participants have given various responses in its favour and against as well. For instance, participant 1 mentioned that "Many enterprises show very low willingness to embrace ERM due to cost", whereas participant from Trafalgar presented that "SMEs do not have resources, by resources I mean financial and Human resources". This means that fund infrastructure can be improved with the help of ERM, yet, due to COVID-19, firms in Laos have limited resources. On the other hand, the participant two participants presented that:

"I think for those small and medium firm when we talk about enterprise risk management it sounds unfamiliar to them", and "During COVID-19 crisis, they do not know how to deal with this situation because they do not have any risk mitigation strategy like they do not calculate what the worst-case", which presents that infrastructure cannot bear the burden of further changes due to covid-19 is. Hence, covid-19 can also be seen as a major threat to firms in Laos. Further, a quotation from the interview of respondent from Expat Explore Travel is given below:

"I would say it is, because when we are able to understand and perceive the risk earlier, it makes it easy for us to manage with the challenges and foresee them. However, we do not have the resources that it takes to be mindful of risks."

Organizational Culture

The last theme extracted from the responses of participants is based on organisational culture. The sub-themes of this section are "Behaviours", "Expectations", "Decisions", and "Challenges". The participants have presented that ERM is critically based on how organisational culture is working. The participants have presented as "Adopt the Enterprise Risk management step by step in culture", which means that there is a need to carry out a stepwise approach to implement ERM in firms, as there have been some challenges identified in implementing ERM in the firms of Laos.

These respective themes are in line with the need of undertaking rational decision making by the board members of selected Laos organizations. For example, the rational model of decision-making exhibits that decision analysis methods are utilised to add utilities and numerical values to every alternative while making choices in perfect or classical rationality. However, alternatives having high value are chosen. When the rational model is being employed in this manner, this is assumed that organisational managers i.e., know of all possible alternatives; know the consequences of implementing each alternative; have a well-organised set of preferences for these consequences; and have the computational ability to compare consequences and to determine which is preferred."

For being able to put rational model of decision making into practice, it is therefore important for board members of the respective Laos firms to appreciate and ensure the adequate presence of all these above presented themes. Furthermore, for executing ERM smoothly, the rational model of decision making can be a support as after problem identification, it is time to create alternative solutions. Then evaluating alternatives and implementing the best one. After a specific time, options are considered to measure their effectiveness. Recycling can be affected by the problem at any step of the process (Fred, 2010). Therefore, decision making is a process of performing activities in a logical sequence. Such as problem identification must be done before creating solutions. By ensuring this sequence of activities, the rational model of decision making can assist in addressing the challenges and then achieving systematic risk management with the effective implementation of ERM. Therefore, these themes have a major role to play for making sure that board decision making is being positively improved.

5.5 Points Observed from Results

It has been presented from previous findings that industries have been confronting various challenges and risks while implementing the scope for operational, geographical

and cultural diversity. There have been various theories in this regard that present the belief that high risk facing firms may get benefits by adapting and implementing enterprise risk management systems. This study has helped in understanding how enterprises can seek benefits from risk management in order to improve financial performance and diversity. The study has helped in understanding the ERM can improve the performance measure in the industry of Laos. The evidence from the study has presented that ERM can prove to be helpful in improving the board decisions regarding the firm and help them in making effective decisions for using available resources in the Construction and tourism industry of Laos. It has been presented in the study that ERM is known to support internal structure, improve risk response, event identifications, and align the risk in an objective setting, which may prove to have a positive impact on the firm performance in the construction and tourism sector of Laos. The monitoring function of ERM is also known to have a critical impact on the performance of a firm. Nevertheless, it is presented that negative impact can be presented of ERM in the Laos firms regarding the utilisation of resources, as it can prove to be expensive. It can prove to be not as cost-effective in the case of Laos because the top management and leadership are not meaningfully familiar with how a decision can be made to improve performance. The major challenges for ERM in Laos are that the negative impact may be attributed due to a surge in the cost of monitoring the activities of the firm to identify risks.

The occurrence of COVID-19 crisis has a lot to with the already existing challenges of ERM adoption and implementation i.e., it has added strength to the challenges and has exposed the weaknesses or gaps prevalent across business firms especially across the underdeveloped countries such as Laos. For examples, after the occurrence of 2008 financial crisis, number of organizations gradually improved their ERM adoption and most recently by aligning it with the updated version of COSO framework 2017 (EandY, 2020). Some organizations were intending to progress ERM to a new level of value-added capability, however by not allocating the required resources and due to competing priorities, this progress remained halted. Some organizations showed reliance on annual risk assessment method which uses a check-the-box approach and

named it as ERM because it undertook passive heat map risk reporting. In addition, some organizations shifted their attention towards the process of Internal Audit risk assessment and gave it the name of ERM process and yet they restrained themselves within the risk assessment phase.

The percentage of organizations that improved their risk planning and risk responses by taking ERM more forward-looking has not been encouraging. Therefore, a significant percentage of organizations that undertook insufficient enhancements to their ERM approach have been caught by the unpredictable effects portrayed by the COVID-19 crisis on the way they do business (Eandy, 2020). It can be understood from this discussion that there is a genuine need and gap existing about the adoption of ERM for improving board decision making which this study has attempted to address.

It has been presented by the empirical evidence that the implementation of ERM and its monitoring does not have a significant impact on the performance of the firm. The findings of the study may seem to be contradicting with the theoretical findings that identified the positive impact of ERM on firm performance for the case of Laos. This requires a need for in-depth study while using the dummy variables as the main variables in future studies.

Financial performance is known to play a critical role in the business success of a firm. This can be presented that risk management may play an imperative role in improving the financial performance of the firms in Laos. It has been presented that risk management may play a critical role in businesses, especially if the broad decision-making is to be improved. ERM is known to be highly effective in the successful decision making of the board and helping them in establishing long-term decisions that are fruitful for the firm. As ERM is responsible for foreseeing the risks that might be confronted by a firm, it helps the leadership and board members to have a vision while making decisions. These findings can be consistent with some responses presented by the participants in the case of the Construction and tourism company of Laos. However,

as the broad members in the construction and tourism sector of Laos are not familiar with ERM, they may not get fruitful outcomes from using ERM. This can also negatively impact the outcomes of the decisions made by the firm.

Although from the findings, it can be seen that there are various ambiguities while discussing the implementation of ERM in the board decision making for the construction and tourism sector of Laos, it can be said that ERM may have a positive impact on seeking advantage, managing risk, and develop a strategic response to a challenge. However, these findings are presented in the global context, and there is a lack of research on the Construction and tourism sector of Laos. Such elements can make the ERM view as an artefact, which means that ERM is developed and implemented for a certain aim in the firm, and it can only be valued if it serves the purpose for which it is developed. This means that ERM will only benefit the Construction and tourism sector of Laos if it helps the board in making effective decisions. As the artefacts take place close to the human beings along with social elements, this creates a link between technological and human elements. This can be seen as a socio-technical system, which can prove to be helpful for ERM. This makes ERM a practical system that can help the board members in the construction and tourism sector of Laos to improve problem-solving and take critical decisions for the firm.

However, a consistent gap can be seen in the expected state and actual state of the business when ERM is implemented, which is an imperative challenge of implementing ERM in the construction and tourism sector of Laos. This can be seen as a significant socio-technical challenge of using ERM. In the case of the construction and tourism industry, it is expected that ERM should help in the integration of work in the firm by synthesising knowledge and expertise in different areas of the construction and tourism sector.

The integration of work in the construction and tourism sector of Laos may involve the combination of methods, ideas and management with risk assessment and evaluation in a way that can be suitable for the structure of the firm and satisfies the need for

functional units. This cohesiveness in the structure of the construction sector of Laos will facilitate the business and hinder any form of difficulties pertaining to the resources and people management.

This will improve the decision making of the board members in the construction sector of Laos, yet it can be seen as a two-way element. However, the implementation of ERM may improve the cohesiveness in business functions.

Despite this, the argument is made that the participation and involvement of top management are affected by the provision of conditions and terms that may involve collaboration norms, information flow and processes, and trust. Hence, this can prove to be helpful in the case of Laos. Moreover, the flow of information is improved due to the cohesiveness in the structure of the firm; the collaborations in social structure may need a surge in work created. Hence, as ERM may support the collaboration, it may facilitate the understanding of ideas and flow of new information in the firms, which will, in turn, support the decision making of the board members in the construction sector of Laos. This will help in a way that the top management and board will be able to be creative with the decisions and ideas, which will facilitate the resource usage in the construction sector of Laos as well.

A similar approach will prevent the top management from holding their position as the only information holder and improve the flow of information in the construction sector of Laos. The development and implementation of ERM are two distinct stages in adapting the ERM in firm structure. Hence, it is believed by the individuals that one process may guarantee success in the other stage. However, this may not be the truth, as the implementation of ERM is not possible without a proper infrastructure that is done in the development stage. If the development stage is not followed thoroughly, it will impact the overall working of ERM in the firm. It can be seen in the case of the construction industry in Laos that management and board members are not familiar with ERM and how it can be made useful, which means that the development of ERM is poor in the firms. This presents a need to highlight the development stage and its errors in the case

of the construction industry in Laos and provide various recommendations to deal with them.

The link between the two stages of ERM and their constraints may not depend on a stepwise relation, where ERM is not implemented until it is developed. Instead, the overlapping in the implantation and developments needs to be predicted at earlier stages, which may improve the chances that the risk management will be implemented in a successful way for the construction sector of Laos. With regard to completing further studies, it is expected that the research studies conducted in the future will help in determining the interdependence of these stages and what will be the impact on the outcomes of stages on the decision making for the construction sector of Laos. Moreover, the academic and research studies will focus on the existence of these stages in the absence of others and what challenges the construction sector of Laos may face when the first stage is not implemented.

As this is a hybrid approach, the arguments are based on the idea that due in some instances, there is a need for top management to involve a manager broker. Initially, the refinement and implementation of ideas, procedures and methods may be based on the link in different areas of knowledge for the construction sector of Laos. The broad members and managers in the construction sector of Laos may involve in scanning progress reports, providing needed resources, contributing ideas and supporting the employees. This will improve the organisational morale and encourage them to be creative so that the decision-making process for the broad members can be improved. Moreover, a cohesion of ideas in the tourism sector, considering its situation due to covid-19, will help in improving the management of risks and help the members to understand how risks can be evaded with the help of their ideas in the case of the construction sector of Laos. In all this scenario, if a broker is involved by the management, they will act as a bridge between the challenges and solutions, which will support the firm performance in general.

Overall, it has been observed that a specific focus needs to be developed by the boards of organizations i.e., instead of documenting and searching the list of all the potential risks that the firm might face, developing strategies that will deal with uncertain and unexpected situations and risks should be the priority.

Because of this, an advanced version of the ERM process based on a resource-based view should be adopted as per the review of Barney and colleagues (Barney et al., 2011). They can also be combined to form one effective theoretical strategy. This perspective fills the blind spots of the ERM process to make it a theory (Dubin, 1976). Scholars and practitioners are still looking for a strategy that will help them discover possible risks, handling them, managing unexpected circumstances, and predicting hazardous effects of the risks. Even though every organisation's theory has its own risk management procedure which can be partially correct, the real meaning remains the same. The respondent board members need to be aware and up-to-date about the contemporary developments of ERM for embracing it optimally and for addressing the challenges associated with its adoption.

5.5.1 Factors Imperative for ERM implementation across Laos

In the case of the sectors, no matter how much knowledge and resources related to ERM are collected, they are useless if a suitable individual to manage all operations is not available (Balogun, Agumba and Renault, 2016; Low, Hwang and Zhao, 2015). Many studies have suggested that low availability of internal information is an unwanted risk (46.7%). For instance, as the flow of information is impacted in the tourism sector, it can act as an additional risk, for which the workforce is not yet ready. Whereas in the case of the constructions sector, the follow of information is a less major threat, due to which the cost in tourism sector may increase for dealing with this threat.

In an ideal situation, the integration of risk culture with ERM enhances the monitoring responsibility, responsiveness and ability and adopts a top-down strategy (Roeschmann, 2014). Many employees agree that sharing information helps them a lot. Therefore, information sharing is similar to knowledge management, where individuals,

processes and technologies are involved (Edwards and Rodriguez, 2010). In the case of the ERM in the construction sector of Laos, it can be seen that the flow of information is suitable for the firm due to the implementation of ERM, but the extent is low. Due to this low extent, the challenges pertaining to ERM is low.

Yet, it cannot be said that information system has been developed successfully. Whereas, in the case of the tourism sector in Laos, the information management and sharing are poor, to an extent where the communication is also weak. This view also proves that the workers' point of view is the most significant. This high percentage proves that workers understand the importance of effective communication and sharing of information between groups. Information sharing is an aspect of ERM which provides a complete strategy against risks (Arnold et al., 2014).

It also enhances cooperation and builds trust among peers, which can facilitate the growth of information management in the tourism sector of Laos. Moreover, having a risk mindset means considering the complete situation regarding the situation and accepting all its opportunities and risks (Rochette, 2019). ERM makes sure to analyse all the situations and adopts a strategic risk mindset. Analyzation of such situations helps managers be prepared for all kinds of situations and understand potential risks and advantages. This means that if the managers in the construction and tourism sector are able to understand the situation and develop a risk mindset, they will be able to implement ERM in an effective way. From the results, it can be seen that this element is lacking in both sectors of Laos, which highlights the need for changes. Predicting outcomes helps the firms be better prepared for future events and decrease losses, which promotes resilience practices (Simkins, Fraser and Fraser, 2010). One of the main principles of ERM integration is risk mindset support which promotes effective ERM practices (Ansell and Agarwal, 2016). Hence, the sectors in Laos are believed to develop this mindset so that the effectiveness of ERM could be improved with reduced resources.

Many studies have explained the risk accountability in terms of ownership (Rochette, 2019). Previous studies have divided accountability into two types: organisational

accountability and personal accountability. The first case deals with the processes and outcomes related to achieving the organisational goals. The second case deals with personal tasks and risks resulted from them.

An example would be that COSO (2015, p. 3) have given many arguments related to the COSO Internal Control, 2013 Integrated Framework, which approves the key values of control environment since they 1) implement accountability; 2) proves loyalty to competency; 3) enforces responsibility, authority and framework; 4) assigns monitoring responsibilities; 5) enforces the importance of ethics and values. Still, the risk accountability is dealt with at the organisational level, where the responsibilities are divided among different sectors. Because of this, the risk culture manages people and processes and defines the relationship between goals and applications. If the risk culture is implemented in the construction and tourism sector of Laos, it is believed that the processes will improve with the passage of time.

Hence, it can prove to be beneficial for both of the sectors in Laos. The outcomes of these studies influence the managerial responsibilities of the ERM processes. Employers in both sectors of Laos are united under the fact that risk accountability enforces the risk culture and is a good practice in the organisation. They also state that accountability for outcomes and progress ensures high responsiveness. Accountability can be measured through evaluations, performance audits or other methods. Effective communication in an organisation is suggested by the COSO Framework 2004 (COSO, 2004). The 6th internal part of the COSO framework defines the importance of communication.

COSO gives great significance to the timely flow and sharing of information across the firm. Studies proved that employees understood the importance of effective communication and transparency for high performance. As the COSO framework has been the core of the current research, it is expected for both the tourism and construction sector of Laos to be mindful that the flow of information should be efficient, and the operations need to be highly transparent. These findings are similar to Arena et

al.'s (2010), who suggests that communication is an integral process that amplifies risk integration. The internal communication in the ERM process enables it to properly monitor and report activities to the top management.

It also makes sure that information is properly shared with business departments which support cooperation and solves misunderstandings. The result of this study proves that there is a good relationship between ERM and good communication.

5.5.2 ERM framework implementation

Many employees understand the fact the ERM supporting technologies and tools are important parts of the ERM process. The main aim of ERM tools is to effectively implement ERM and support its functionalities for a long time. The use of ERM technologies and tools atomises the risk practices and develops a strong framework that manages risks properly (Paladino and Francis, 2008).

A policy is defined as a statement that describes responsibilities and ensures reliable practices (ISSA, 2004). A policy should also contain the philosophy, control, attitude and assessment activities of the organisation that are necessary to achieve its objectives and goals (CESG, 2012). The control activities have two parts, framework and policy, that ensure that the organisations are handling risks efficiently (COSO, 2004). The policy is responsible for declaring the scope, goals and future of ERM, while the framework implements the policy by following proper procedures (Chapman, 2011). The policy also has details regarding the working and implementation of risks and what tasks should be performed (Chapman, 2011). Some studies have asserted that the employees recognise the importance of risk management framework and policies to make a strong organisation (Young, 2022; Lima and Verbano, 2019).

Considering the case of the tourism and construction sector of Laos, it is expected that the policies will be presented for the business sector so that a better outcome of the implementation of ERM can be expected, and the decision making of broad members can be improved. The outcomes of recent studies made a considerable percentage of

the employers aware of the importance of data related to understanding the potential risks.

Moody's Analytics (2014) puts great focus on the importance of having raw information, tools to manage them, transformational data and business strategies that will benefit from them later in the future.

Any negligence in this will badly affect the ERM implementation, and because of this, proper and effective sharing of correct information within all departments of the organisation is important (Moody's, 2014). For instance, in the case of the business sector of Laos, it is presented that the negligence in using data and tools may negatively impact the firms rather than providing beneficial results. This presents the need to hire an expert while working on the firms of Laos for ERM.

Even though some organisations have difficulty managing this in the case of Laos, aggregation of information allows firms to create proper practices, increase reliability, enhance the flow of information and also integrate stronger ERM abilities which allow the sharing of accurate and precise information (Bank for International Settlements, 2013). The risk monitoring framework plays a major role in the alignment of practices, functions and communications, which connects with the goals of the firm (Simkins and Fraser, 2010).

This presents a need to use a risk management framework in the business sector of Laos because the respondents presented a need for it. It also denies the parts of ERM which are responsible for enhancing the strategic association of framework, responsibilities and practices (Lundqvist and Andren, 2017). Some studies proved that there is a great relationship between ERM procedure and oversight framework according to the workers (Lundqvist and Adren, 2017; Mishra et al, 2019). This proves the ERM implementation was critical for almost 40% of the workers. The studies also declare that risk monitoring, risk control (reporting) and oversight framework (deciding responsibilities) are the main components of the ERM process (Lundqvist and Andren, 2017; COSO, 2017). In the light of this discussion and the direction showed by the

results it is evident that value-based ERM approach is imperative for improving the board decision making because value based ERM metrics fully endorses the decision-making.

This aspect quantifies all kinds of risks comprising insurance, financial, operational and strategic, which permits it to support all decisions. Therefore, it can be stated here that for comprehensive risk management in Laos organizations, integrating value based ERM and its essence can prove helpful because it supports systematic decision making. This also wholly captures the influence different internal and external risks can have as it is utilising the value metric of the company that involves all future consequences, whether it's the balance sheet, income statement or capital cost. Lastly, this shows the impact of any decision on the equation of risk-return (Segal, 2016).

Lastly, COVID-19 crisis is also pivotal to be considered here because it has exhibited some implications on the mindset and approach of the respondents who are part of business firms in Laos. from the perspective of COVID-19 crisis new dimensions has been surged i.e., by evaluating the data results in the light of COVID-19 crisis, the importance and effective implementation of ERM has been reaffirmed as the pandemic implications have made it clear that organizations are not integrating and organizing the ERM in an effective manner and it needs to be improved for the benefit of the businesses. After the financial crisis the value of ERM was being questioned back in 2008 as it wreaked havoc throughout the global business world being the most significant financial event and it negatively affected businesses operating with different geographies, industries and sizes. The business organizations started to question themselves shortly after 2008 crisis regarding how they can prepare themselves in a better way if such crisis occurs again in the future. Since the ERM was reactive, flat-footed and focused on highly likely risks only.

This criticism is appearing to be prevailing again in the midst of COVID-19 crisis which means that ERM is still not being adopted and implemented in the best possible manner. ERM has the potential and should have prepared organizations in a better way

for such crisis or events and this aspect is exhibiting the value of ERM is not being extracted properly.

This occurrence of COVID-19 crisis has also indicated that the adoption and implementation of ERM can face various unique and unpredictable challenges, however at the same time, organizations need to be proactive about their risk management strategies and they need to put conscious efforts for improving their board decision making. Merely setting expectations from ERM will not serve benefits, instead its integration within the culture and ensuring its implications on board decision making is imperative.

5.6 Chapter Summary

The chapter presented that the results are obtained from the interviews of board members working in different tourism and construction companies of Laos. It has been observed in line with the answers given by respondents that the construction and tourism sector in Laos are facing challenges in administrating ERM due to financial constraints and related challenges. The responses of respondents from both industries have indicated that companies operating in these industries have been confronting various challenges and risks while implementing the ERM and formal risk management system i.e., lack of willingness of board members, lack fo resources, requirement of infrastructure and advance information systems. Six themes have been identified in this chapter in line with the results gathered with the help of interviews i.e., risk planning, organizational culture, risk identification, resources & capabilities, leadership styles and benefits of ERM. The themes and sub-themes identified in this chapter are closely aligned with the literature review findings which signifies the reliability of the results. Two respondents from construction industry and 3 respondents from tourism industry mentioned that their understanding based on past experience does not allow them to adopt risk management as systematic process.

Themes presented in this chapter have been reaffirmed by literature findings and are closely aligned with the contemporary literature paradigm of ERM. Risk planning and risk identification has been cited as key initiating aspects which have been referred as imperative for managing risks systematically (Purdy, 2010; Hopkins, 2015). Assertions exhibited by theory of risk management as stated by Tippett and Carbone, (2004) has been found as complementary with the sub-themes identified in this chapter i.e., importance of risk planning and strategic nature of risk management. Therefore, an alignment of the results with the theory has been established in this chapter. COSO, (2017); Bento et al, (2018) mentioned about the benefits of ERM and the role of directors towards ensuring the execution of ERM has been validated by the themes identified in this chapter i.e., 'Leadership Style' and 'ERM Benefits'. Young, (2022) endorsed the crucial role of leadership and their respective style in ERM implementation which signifies the theme presented in this chapter. Results of this study have further elaborated that how the identified themes can be classified into sub-themes adequately e.g. Pagach et al, (2015) stressed about the strategic role of ERM and presence of efficient information system for making risk management work as a system and these aspects have been indicated by the responses of board members as well.

6. Chapter6 Conclusion

It can be concluded that this study has attempted to address and achieve its earlier established research objectives and questions in a logical and aligned manner which may have gone to a significant extent. In this study, board decision-making has been seen as an integral part of the functioning of business organisations, and this decision-making needs to be systematic for managing risks effectively. The importance of ERM for organizational decision making has been observed evidently in this study i.e., in the literature review and data results, ERM has been found as a critical element of general corporate governance and risk management culture of business firms (Ali and Khan, 2017; Tse and Krause, 2016). It has provided several instructions, principles, and values for business firms that effectively identify and mitigate risks. This has been evident from the responses given by the respondents during primary qualitative data collection, such as most of the respondents acknowledged the importance and relevance of different factors of ERM for their board decision making. In this study, it has been observed during the literature review section that enterprise risk management (ERM) can potentially provide organisational boards with value and advantage while making their decisions, especially when identifying and managing risks (Leoni and Florio, 2017). COSO framework formed the basis of this study's theoretical framework because the primary purpose behind the proposition and development of the COSO framework has been the identification and management of risks for adding value to organisational performance.

A key objective was to examine the challenges faced by organisations in implementing ERM in the specific context of Laos. Some important challenges have been identified that are in tandem across literature and interview results, such as the absence of top management support and risk management culture (Pierce and Goldstein, 2018; Saeidi et al, 2020). Some aspects of ERM are being implemented by the tourism and

construction sector boards in Laos without knowing and formally identifying them as part of the ERM process.

It has been concluded that awareness about ERM benefits and scope is insufficient across respective corporate boards in Laos. They are yet to achieve formal establishment and functioning of ERM enabled risk management culture.

Another research objective of this study was to propose a strategy for adequately adopting or implementing the ERM concept across the Laos tourism and construction industries. This objective has been achieved as a conceptual framework has been proposed in this chapter under the section of recommendations which can potentially assist Laos firms in effectively integrating ERM for improving their board decision making. This proposed framework has stemmed from literature review findings, COSO system, theoretical framework and thematic analysis of the results presented earlier.

It has been concluded that a concrete understanding of the usability and implementation of ERM is imperative today especially for top companies operating in the construction and tourism industry as reflected from the results and findings of this study, especially regarding integrating systematic risk management culture and approach (Bromiley et al., 2015; Rau and Bromiley, 2016). This has been achieved in a precise context so that organisational boards of tourism and construction firms in Laos can make decisions that are effective in managing risks. It has been noted in this study that the occurrence of risk has become inevitable for business firms, especially in the case of Laos business environment, which is a less developing country context. The recent event of COVID-19 has made the situation uncertain and prone to risks. Some specific challenges identified in this study are lack of resources, lack of awareness, lack of training, leadership willingness, and lack of formal risk management culture (Grieser and Pedell, 2021; Hassan et al, 2022).

Proper training about handling and managing risks should also be given to the Board members, and they should be taught about countermeasures that should be applied if any risk is faced at any time. They should mention the contingency plans of the organisation in regard to the challenges faced due to ERM implementation.

An underlying aim of the study was to expand knowledge, understanding and awareness about the usability of enterprise risk management for corporate boards of Laos construction and tourism companies about their decision making. This has been achieved by reviewing the broader academic literature and drawing key arguments from journal articles and textbooks. Moreover, by completing the interviews with relevant respondents, an attempt has been made to address this research aim. This study has identified a literature gap regarding the use of enterprise risk management approach across corporate boards of tourism and construction sector firms in Laos. A key objective was to evaluate the importance of ERM for organisational decision making, which has been made evident in the literature review and theoretical framework sections. For example, the link between ERM and strategy, the functioning of ERM as a framework and the development of a formal risk management culture are some factors that have indicated the importance of ERM for organisational decision making. Moreover, the respondents of this study have shown visible agreement that ERM can improve board decision-making i.e., multiple respondents from construction and tourism companies indicated this while answering question number three.

Better decision making ERM is required and is essential because no single accepted definition exists about ERM. The emerging consensus states that managing a firm is more critical than components and not only traditional risks, includes strategic risks and competitor actions which require decision making to be risk-averse and informed (Harwood, 2016). The research aim is also potentially achieved by reflecting on several theories such as the contingency theory, resource-based view, and risk management theory. It has been concluded that the COSO framework is still providing the basis of the contemporary ERM framework, which improves the understanding of risk management across business organisations.

The literature review has presented theories that can help improve the ERM integration across Laos firms such as, resource-based view and risk management theory (Schmit and Gatzert, 2016; Hiebl and Falkner, 2015). These theories have reaffirmed the

importance of relying on internal resources and systematic dealing of risks, indicating the need to embrace ERM.

It has been concluded that the application of resource-based view is relevant and beneficial for the Laos business firms intending to adopt and integrate ERM driven risk management culture. This is so because the resource-based view provides methods that can be used to prioritise tasks in the firm (Bromiley et al., 2015). The results of this study are sufficient to develop and suggest an ERM framework that can be used for successfully initiating and sustaining ERM culture so that board decision making can become more flexible, well-directed and well-informed. This study has concluded that resource allocation, strategic planning, and top leadership role are imperative factors that can drive the implementation of ERM-driven risk management culture across Laos firms i.e., based on the responses of question number five and six, theoretical framework and identified themes.

ERM infrastructure, characteristics of leadership, allocation of funds, support of leadership, information sharing, training of directors and traditional risk management culture are some notable factors (Beasley et al., 2018; Teoh et al, 2017; Viscelli et al, 2016). These are imperative factors to be part of the ERM framework for extracting optimal board decision-making results. It has been concluded that the kind of challenges and crisis business world is prone to, makes it essential to give more time and energy towards understanding and implementing ERM, more so because the way ERM is organized across businesses of different industries is not as meaningful as it should be.

The ERM shortfalls have become evident in this study which are embedded in the themes and sub-themes ultimately pointing to the imperative route and steps that organizations in Laos needs to undertake for transforming the risk management culture and programs being run within construction and tourism companies. For example, a renewed focus on delivering the strategic goals of the company is required guided by the systematic approach towards risk management i.e., adopting ERM frameworks for positively driving board decision making.

6.1 Research Limitations

This research has multiple limitations in line with its unique context and research method were chosen. The first challenge was faced during identifying the firms that have been implementing ERM in the business sector of Laos or possess some knowledge about it. During COVID-19, it was exceedingly difficult to meet people related to the Laos business environment and inquire about the ERM concept as COVID-19 impacted time and resource factors. Therefore, there are chances that the researcher might have missed some organisations in the construction and tourism sectors of Laos that are operating with the ERM framework already. The responses given by the participants in this study are based on solely their subjective experiences, and since the respondents are board members due to which their experiences are likely to vary significantly because every board member has their unique background and career path. Therefore, this might limit the generalizability of the findings.

Another limitation faced was the willingness of the potential respondents to be a part of the data collection process because not all likely respondents showed agreement to participate and were reluctant due to various reasons. This might have restricted the diversity and quality of data being collected in this study. Moreover, due to the COVID-19 factor, it was not possible to include many respondents in the data collection process because of a significant amount of time loss. This limitation might have affected the depth and reliability of the findings produced after the data collection process. These limitations are worthy of mentioning here because the ultimate objective was to search and include respondents who have prior knowledge and practical understanding (if possible) of ERM as a risk management framework. Another limitation can be the researcher's understanding of the construction of interview questions for extracting highly relevant information/ data from respondents. This limitation might have affected

the quality, relevance and value of interview questions that were asked to the respondents for addressing the research aim and objectives of this study.

6.2 Research Contribution

Since this study has investigated the research area of enterprise risk management in the specific context of Laos, it has some contributions to offer for the body of knowledge and literature, which will be presented in this section. Moreover, this study has potentially contributed to the broader academic literature and body of knowledge by reaffirming some points. For example, reaffirming specific theoretical perspectives such as the risk management culture, resource-based view, and risk management theory is relevant and meaningful in the less developed countries' context such as Laos (Bone, 2020). This is so because these theories are potentially implicating and have a significant role in Laos construction and tourism firms when pursuing ERM adoption, as observed in this study's findings i.e., as indicated by the experiences shared by the respondents during interviews. For example, the respondents have reflected the need of developing a formal risk management culture and those risks should be dealt with systematically, which is the fundamental assertion of risk management theory (Holzhauer et al., 2016; Wagner and Kinatendar, 2014).

Moreover, it has been observed from the responses of respondents that boards of selected Laos firms need to change their priorities about risk management and follow what Harrington et al. said. Harrington et al. (2002) have mentioned in the literature that the risks can be structured and prioritised by dealing with them systematically instead of approaching them individually. In addition, one of the most significant theories of strategic management is a resource-based theory, and its relevance has been identified in the Laos context in the light of data collected and findings. For example, selected Laos firms do not have strategic planning to embrace or integrate ERM, indicating that a resource-based view (RBV) needs to be implemented in these organisations (Responses to question number four, five and eight are reflecting it). RBV states that an unequal distribution of resources between organisations and organisations can gain

competitive advantages over the others because of this (Barney, 1991; Barney, 2001).

Another research contribution of this study is the alignment of findings obtained from the Laos context with the original COSO framework indicating that the COSO framework has considerable relevance and application in the less developed countries context. This can be a contribution because not sufficient evidence is available in the literature regarding the applicability and usability of the COSO framework in Laos regarding influencing or improving board decision making. For example, systematic use of risk management practices and culture is not prevalent across selected Laos firms, as affirmed in the light of responses given by the respondents i.e., answers to interview question number four to question nine are reflecting this.

Board members of selected Laos firms mainly possess awareness about ERM. However, due to certain constraints, they have not attempted to integrate it in their organisations even though the kind of risks they face and the kind of resources they have made it feasible COSO framework.

In literature, no significant study has been found supporting the fact that COSO framework variables are suitable for the Laos business context because this area of research did not attained interest of scholars and researchers. Therefore, a unique contribution of this study is the identification of COSO framework relevance for risk management across Laos business firms (COSO, 2011). Another essential contribution of this study is the determining relevance and importance of leadership theories/styles for effective integration of ERM in an organisational context, as mentioned in this study's findings. For example, top leadership support has been identified as a critical factor that can facilitate the integration of ERM driven risk management culture across particular Laos firms (Vij, 2019). Moreover, the need and relevance of situational leadership and transformational leadership have been identified. The role of leadership and top management has been highlighted as imperative for adopting and integrating

ERM across organisational boards for both developed and less developed countries context in the literature (Viscelli et al, 2016; Pederson, 2021) and this study's findings in response to the interview question number five, six and eight.

Apart from this unique contribution, this study has exhibited an essential contribution by indicating that decision making across organisational boards of less developed countries also needs the support of ERM as a mechanism for raising the chances of making it effective.

The COSO Enterprise Resource Management structure expresses that director of the organisations "support the entity's risk management philosophy, promote compliance with its risk appetite and manage risks within their respective spheres of responsibility consistent with risk tolerances" (COSO, 2017). Consequently, recognising pioneers all across the organisations and acquiring their help is fundamental to the fruitful execution of Enterprise Resource Management.

6.3 Theoretical and Practical Implications

As far as the literature of ERM is concerned, this study contains some positive implications because the prevalence and integration of ERM across less developing country's business contexts have not been significant in the recent past. For example, a favourable critical implication can highlight the importance and relevance of leadership styles and characteristics for integrating ERM across Laos business firms. The findings that leadership has a crucial role in ensuring effective ERM implementation and that there is a need for leadership development can positively implicate the business environment of Laos.

A shift in focus can happen by firms on their board members' personal and professional development as a result. This study has the potential to positively implicate the ERM literature by encouraging and giving a new direction to the researchers/ scholars for exploring the dynamics of ERM across less developing countries contexts. Therefore, it is expected that researchers might start to apply more already existing theories in Laos

and other less developed countries' contexts for determining their relevance and impact.

A potentially crucial implication of this study is the significant level of awareness that it can create across the research students and scholars who may want to conduct their research work across less developed countries. Since this topic area is of significant importance for business researchers at doctoral and master's levels and practitioners working in different industries, the chances are that this study might encourage them and enable them to think and undertake research investigations in less developed countries' contexts. This implication intends to be practical because the results and findings have shown a specific and clear trend which can make the researchers and readers understand adequately the use and importance of ERM for the board decision making across less developed countries' contexts.

Moreover, practitioners might start to trust and show willingness in the effectiveness of the ERM framework to enhance their risk management culture and board decision-making as most of the respondents in this study have acknowledged the need for a systematic risk management approach in the best interest of the organisation their business performances. Moreover, respondents have shown agreement on the application and relevance of ERM components/variables to improve risk management-related decision-making. The board of directors and business leaders needed clarity and understanding regarding the uses and scope of ERM that is explicit to Laos's construction industry and tourism industry, precisely because these two industries are high performing industries within Laos. This study has provided some clarity by highlighting pragmatic aspects, e.g., the balance in decision making instead of giving major shareholders the authority to make decisions.

Also, the understanding of roles in managing risk and systematic pursuit of risk management instead are some key areas that have provided clarity. This can significantly improve the risk related decision-making culture of the Laos boards

because it has shown a new paradigm of undertaking risk management which is currently not present in Laos firms.

Therefore, this study has the potential of shaping the observed work behaviours and problem-solving behaviour of organisational boards towards the risks that their respective firms face because a certain level of evidence has been exhibited by this study in favour of using ERM. For example, construction and tourism firms in Laos are not pursuing a risk management system, and at the same time, their board members acknowledge the benefits and needs of ERM. They have agreed that role of top leadership is decisive for making risk management effective. They have also indicated poor results that they experienced in the recent past regarding risk management due to a lack of formal risk management culture and system.

This study has attempted to effectively address this gap with a comprehensive ERM framework and by guiding the implementation process of the development industry and travel industry. The findings can be implemented, or Laos firms can draw inferences from this study's findings to develop an effective approach to improve organisational decision-making towards risk management, which means that this study can exhibit positive implications on pragmatic grounds. For example, Laos firms can ensure the availability and functioning of all the imperative variables mentioned in the conceptual framework and the suggested framework for achieving improved results. This can guide Laos firms and boards to draw meaningful insights using the proposed framework in their respective contexts.

The study's findings have presented that for improving the overall decision-making process, the firms and their board members in Laos need to make sure the availability of financial resources dedicated to ERM. Doing this will remove the financial restrictions from risk management practices and focus on a solution-based approach. Therefore, from a practical perspective, this can significantly change the way boards invest in the ERM. For example, most of the Laos firms are operating with a traditional risk

management plan which consumes fewer resources and finances, and they are focusing majorly on financial risks. They are not focusing on other types of risks.

This way, decision making related to risk management is not being proven effective for Laos firms. Moreover, limited or insufficient infrastructure and shortage of skills also need to be improved, which requires investment. If Laos firms intend to broaden their risk management focus, then they again need investment. Therefore, in light of this study's findings, the way Laos firms invest in their business and system will become well-directed and strategic, providing them with long-term benefits, i.e., in the form of a developed ERM system and culture.

One key implication is the affirmation of the contingency theory's validation in the less developed country context. The contingency theory by Lawrence and Lorsch (1967) explains that a firm's performance depends on several external and internal features such as technology, organisation culture, corporate framework, and environment. The findings of this study have made it clear that these features mentioned by contingency theory can be used positively for influencing ERM adoption across Laos business firms. For example, the organisational culture of Laos firms must embed ERM, the technology-driven infrastructure has to offer and make the desired system available for executing ERM, and Laos firms have to add ERM system in their corporate framework to improve their risk management decision making. Even though these factors are currently not in place across selected Laos firms, the understanding, awareness, and agreement shown by respondents have clarified that they need these factors to improve their risk management decision-making and ultimately can positively influence business performance.

Applying the resource-based view and its need across the selected Laos business firms is another theoretical implication that this study has exhibited. For example, the resource-based view provides methods that can be used to prioritise tasks in the firm. The respondents of this study have shown agreement that they need to prioritise establishing a systematic risk management culture that ERM offers comprehensively.

The resource-based view exhibits that firms possess resources, a subset of which enable them to achieve a competitive advantage and a subset of those that lead to superior long-term performance.

Resources that are valuable and rare can lead to the creation of a competitive advantage. Currently, selected Laos firms have not capitalised on their resources for competitive advantage and the conceptual framework. The suggested framework has highlighted the factors that can be utilised for developing an ERM-driven risk management culture as a source of competitive advantage.

As per the study findings and conclusions, it is clear that Laos business firms need to strictly follow a resource-based view if they are to extract optimal benefits out of ERM because the pre-requisites of ERM adoption cannot be achieved without the implementation of a resource-based view. Moreover, on theoretical grounds, this study can shape the type of leadership style and behaviours displayed by the board members of selected Laos business firms that are suitable for using ERM. The kind of behaviours that are important for leadership to demonstrate can be made clear as an implication of this study because currently, it is not identified or examined.

6.4 Future Research Directions

In Laos's business context, this study appears to be the first research undertaking this clear perspective that has discussed and evaluated the implementation of ERM to drive board decision-making. Therefore, a critical future direction of research that emerges here is the identification that Laos firms have the potential of integrating ERM in their risk management culture, and board decision making can reap benefits as a result of this integration. The optimistic and encouraging responses of respondents in this study are validating this contribution. More studies can be expected to investigate this area, especially which one of the factors or variables is effective or role player for improving ERM's integration across the risk management culture of Laos firms. This research direction has been derived because the findings have shown that multiple factors can

play their role in making ERM implementation smooth for board decision-making. Therefore, these factors can be narrowed down by conducting further research.

Value creation for business firms has been determined from the study findings as respondents indicated that company performance could improve by formally using ERM. This finding provides a future research direction of exploring the level and nature of value creation that ERM can facilitate in Laos. Since, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, this study is the first empirical qualitative study that has evaluated ERM's implementation with board decision making within Laos. Therefore, for further validating the factors identified in this study, additional research will be required for broadening the participants so that generalisation can be achieved. Importantly, it has been mentioned in the literature review that value-based ERM allows decision-making to be fully supported by value-based ERM metrics.

This quantifies all kinds of risks comprising insurance, financial, operational and strategic, which permits it to support all types of decisions, which indicates the relevance of this research contribution. Another critical future research direction can be exploring and examining the nature of decisions that exhibit significant influence from ERM, i.e., categorisation of the decisions boards has to make concerning ERM. In this study, decision-making has been considered in general. This will then assist in improving the effectiveness and direction of ERM while being integrated across Laos business firms. Another future research prospect that this study is encouraging can be the role of corporate governance. For example, how ERM can be used or contributes towards improving corporate governance of Laos business firms because this study has not dwelled into the governance aspect and has dealt with it briefly.

Some important future research directions can be drawn from this study's unique findings and conclusions. For example, it can be of significant interest for researchers and meaningful for the body of knowledge to investigate what employees and managerial level staff think about implementing ERM because the integration and adoption of ERM depend heavily on the risk management culture. In this study, the

focus remained on board level individuals and middle management, or other employee levels have been ignored, which makes this future research direction imperative for strengthening and comprehensively understanding the influence of ERM across Laos business firms.

Therefore, it gives a strong indication that a potential future research direction can be the undertaking of employees' and managerial perception about the uses and relevance of ERM for organisational decision making. This will examine the scope and applicability of ERM on different organisational decision-making levels, which can be a valuable addition and contribution to the body of knowledge. As mentioned in the literature, corporate leaders can use different decision-making styles in their respective situations (Ibneatheer et al, 2021; Onley, 2019). It has been identified in this study that the role of board members as organisational leaders is critical when it comes to the implementation of ERM, due to which their characteristics and professional development have become more acute. Importantly, leadership has been found a vital component of this study's COSO framework and conceptual framework.

The COSO Enterprise Resource Management structure expresses that director of the organisations "support the entity's risk management philosophy, promote compliance with its risk appetite and manage risks within their respective spheres of responsibility consistent with risk tolerances" (COSO, 2017).

Consequently, recognising pioneers all across the organisations and acquiring their help is fundamental to the fruitful execution of Enterprise Resource Management. Therefore, the literature and qualitative findings both have provided a future research direction. This direction can cover the investigation of developmental needs of the board of directors as business leaders across Laos business context, i.e., what characteristics, attributes and skills are essential for effectively integrating ERM in the decision-making process. Apart from this, another critical future research direction that can be potentially meaningful is the evaluation of external factors that exist in the business environment of Laos because external business environment factors can change the way a business

operates or behave. This is probable, especially in risk management culture and practices directed towards managing the risk while making board-level decisions.

A key reason behind this is that how external factors can shape or influence the ERM integration is not discussed in this study since this study did not consider the external environment factors, which leaves a visible room to work and improve. This aspect will enable the body of knowledge to clarify how Laos business firms can prepare themselves amid unique external factors.

6.5 Recommendations for Effective ERM Implementation

The framework suggested by the researcher is presented below, which has the fundamental purpose of providing a guideline for Laos construction and tourism sector firms for achieving an ERM driven culture of decision making. The variables have been extracted from the understanding developed by engaging in the literature review section, from the conceptual framework presented earlier and from the key findings of the data collected from specific respondents in the Laos context. Since the research aim of this study is about proposing an ERM framework for facilitating board decision-making. This framework has been developed after analysing and aligning the common links between literature review, conceptual framework, and qualitative data results. This proposed framework can be considered as the extended or modified form of the conceptual framework established earlier. The suggested ERM framework is presented below, which is expected to address and consider the internal business environment of selected Laos firms:

Figure 10: Modified conceptual framework

Sourc: Bikky,(2021)

This new framework is different from the previous framework in multiple ways. The clarity of role and process of ERM system was not available in the previous framework which made each factor appeared as independent of the other factor. However, in this new framework a clear interdependence can be observed. For example, the central point of focus in the new framework is the strengthening of business objectives from the support of ERM infrastructure and leadership characteristics.

Corporate governance can be seen as a distinct factor taking input from risk management culture and providing output strength to the business objectives and strategies in the new framework. Whereas, in the previous framework corporate governance was seen as part of the organizational strategy. This shows that corporate governance needs to be utilized as a source of competitive advantage and value for the business objectives which ultimately drives the board decision making. Therefore, the new framework is more logical and systematic in nature. The linking between board decision making, risk management culture and corporate governance is a strong aspect of the new framework which is indicating that how risk management culture can directly influence board decision making and how corporate governance can keep it independent in nature.

The new framework has also indicated the importance of leadership characteristics which were not given much importance in the previous framework. The new framework is more precise and concise as compared to the previous framework which not only is reflecting on the priorities and systematic linkages of the factors involved, but it is also making it more pragmatic. As a process and system, the new framework has more reliability because of the placement of each variable and because of linking each factor with another factor for creating value. The way organizational board was viewed and placed in the previous framework was less effective and logical as compared to its usage in the new framework. Below presented are some recommendation for Laos construction and tourism companies in the light of new framework, data results and literature review findings:

6.5.1 Need for top management support

This first recommendation is about the much needed and pragmatically required top management support for ensuring that ERM is being integrated effectively across the boards of Laos firms and is subsequently giving the formal opportunity to align the board decisions accordingly. This study has found that support from top management is currently not comprehensive and explicit towards the implementation of ERM across Laos boards due to lack of awareness, resources and competencies.

Therefore, the idea behind this recommendation is to create a support system at the top level that encourages board members to use ERM in their decision-making processes. Moreover, it generates support from other top management to establish a culture towards ERM-driven risk management. Moreover, there have been different validations observed across literature supported by conformational results, which shows that the help of the board is imperative for the implementation of the ERM framework (Viscelli et al, 2017). This gives a strong reason why top management support for ERM adoption is being recommended here. The focal point that restricts the establishment of ERM driven risk management culture across Laos boards is the lack of supportive executive strategy. As mentioned by the respondents, the board members overall cannot execute risk management effectively, regardless of whether they are friendly and jovial in their interaction. This potentially reduces the adequacy of ERM adoption and therefore makes it imperative to exhibit significant support by the board members and top administration.

Top management is recommended to remain proactive to ensure that the adoption and integration of ERM are consistent across boards of Laos firms. This ultimately and gradually can then assist in the decision-making of the board. Moreover, in Laos, the components that have been identified as missing across their organisational culture and risk management approach include risk tolerance, risk appetite, risk ownership and operational methodology. All these aspects require top management support and willingness for being functional in an effective way. This is another reason why consistent and positive top management support is being recommended. In most of Laos's construction sector business organisations, a top-bottom hierarchy is being followed, making it essential that these aspects are linked with each other.

A significant level of balance is existent for making sure that the top management decisions are made are not being affected. This also makes it essential to ensure involvement, willingness and presence of top management support for ERM has driven risk management culture. This can be quite challenging as every top management

individual possesses unique thinking, past experiences, and perception regarding risk management (Hunziker and Durrer, 2021).

Therefore, another associated recommendation here is to make sure that the mindset of top leadership is flexible and aware of the benefits that ERM can facilitate irrespective of the diverging nature of their perception and past experiences.

This will prepare and make top management capable of embracing ERM driven risk management culture. Fraser et al. (2018) have investigated the perception of top management about ERM as a critical driver for organisational performance across the construction sector. They found that risk management is ineffective when board members and top management are not supportive because it disturbs the decision-making process. Since a critical focus of this study has been onboard decision making, this particular recommendation becomes relevant and vital for Laos firms.

6.5.2 Availability of cost, time and resources

The findings of this study have also presented that a lack of resources is a significant challenge for the construction and tourism sector of Laos while implementing ERM within their risk management system. Based on this finding, it has been recommended that Laos firms strategically pursue the availability of time, cost, and resources to integrate ERM into their risk management culture. For companies working in a less developed country such as Laos, it can be challenging to invest and allocate resources for ERM integration because it requires specific pre-requisites for doing so, which includes willingness/ support of top leadership and deliberate policy changes by going through a formal process. This can require a formal change management process and an organisation-wide sense of urgency to carry out these changes for the long-term benefit of the organisation. Once this recommendation is achieved, the chances of positively influencing the board decision making in the best interest of the whole organisation will increase along with the achievement of a formal risk management culture driven by ERM. In addition, depending on the respective capacities,

competencies and funds, construction and tourism sector companies can opt for either in-house experts or outsourcing this change management process.

The ultimate objective should be to reduce the cost of implementing ERM across Laos firms for enabling boards to make decisions in an aligned manner. The implementation of this recommendation is linked with the implementation of previous recommendations. It depends on the extent to which organisational leadership is willing and ready to embrace ERM drive risk management culture. Another objective behind this recommendation is to enable and shift the attention of Laos firms towards developing and then sustaining ERM-driven risk management culture. Moreover, this is a fundamental component of ERM frameworks discussed in the literature review section and the ERM framework suggested by the researcher in this section.

This recommendation is expected to be meaningful for Laos's construction and tourism sector companies because it can attain a competitive advantage by optimising the resources. Given the current situation of Laos construction and tourism firms, as expressed by their board members (respondents), optimising resources and effective cost management is essential for them, which can be achieved by proper resource allocation.

This also indicates how interlinked the nature of risk management culture expects and requires different organisational organs to function optimally and support each other. When top management of Laos firms realise that with the application of ERM, they can reduce costs linked with risk and enhance risk management practices. The implementation of this recommendation will be smooth. It is essential to mention here that this and the previous recommendation are pragmatic because tourism and construction sector board members perceive ERM as a burden instead of something of significant value. This behaviour has been identified as one key reason why ERM is not being implemented or adopted properly across Laos firms. Therefore, a probable corrective measure in this regard is the application of this and the previous recommendation.

6.5.3 Developing ERM Culture (Risk Management and ERM implementation guidelines)

In line with the conclusion of this study and the findings of this study, a key recommendation is about the establishment of an ERM culture within the broader risk management culture. Importantly, it was indicated by the respondents that there is no formal and systematic risk management culture in place across selected Laos firms. This is important because construction and tourism firms in Laos are currently not operating with a formal culture of risk management that embeds ERM framework elements due to which their board decision-making is yet to be systemised, well-informed, and well-directed. It has been observed from the literature review section that the framework holds critical importance when it comes to guiding effective risk management across firms, especially the COSO framework discussion indicated this aspect.

Therefore, this gives another validation that the functioning of an ERM-driven risk management culture is vital for Laos firms to take risk-free decisions and take decisions by avoiding risks or identifying appropriate risks. Regardless of the specific industry, ERM-driven risk management culture is fundamental because it provides ease in terms of resource allocation and top management support while integrating ERM with the organisational strategy. ERM driven culture can absorb and disseminate information better and flow, which is the essence behind effective risk management practices and techniques (Beasley et al., 2017).

Currently, the organisational strategies of Laos firms are not integrated and aligned with risk management culture, which is posing a significant hurdle in the way of improving board decision making. Therefore, to enhance board decision-making towards risk management, a critical pre-requisite has been recommended for Laos construction and tourism companies to establish ERM-driven risk management culture. Thus, Laos firms can achieve twofold benefits by pursuing and achieving an ERM culture, allowing firms to improve strategic planning and risk insight.

For tourism and construction firms in Laos, resource allocation holds critical importance as most companies are operating with limited resources, which makes this recommendation even more vital because it will allow them to allocate resources systematically and optimally, ultimately benefiting the board's decision-making process. In addition, when it comes to the ERM process, culture has been cited as the most critical component that can protect the organisation's performance.

It is also recommended that business firms in Laos need to integrate the essence of value based ERM in their culture which will strengthen the overall risk management culture. As it has been mentioned by Segal, (2016) the value-based ERM model is designed explicitly for ERM and is optimally suitable for decision-making. This model is agile and practical, easy to modify and quick to calculate. Furthermore, this is dependent on the basic building blocks to which all individuals could relate, offering the transparency required for organisational management to depend on its decision-making support. This view is inclusive, adding a proper balance of input coming through business (required for credibility) and corporate units (needed for consistency). Furthermore, instead of demonstrating the downside risks only, this value-based ERM strategy could assist organisational initiatives by analysing the return and risk implications of the proposal (Segal, 2016). Therefore, with these characteristics one can understand the suitability and significance of value based ERM for strengthening the risk management culture of the companies.

6.6 Reflection on Research Journey

This section presents my learning and reflections on how I have gained experience and knowledge of findings facts by following stepwise approach. This study has helped me in improving my research skills, which will make my research more reliable. As I have collected qualitative data, I came across many hurdles and challenges because this experience was unusual for me. I had to face various dysconnectivity related challenges and problems due to COVID-19.

As people were self-isolating and maintaining social distance, I had to look for contacts for reaching out to the board members from tourism and construction sector by myself. It was challenging for me to pitch my idea because I was not able to see them face-to-face. However, I believed that going through this experience have made me more confident and in future I will be able to cater to such challenges in more effective manner.

To compile the results, I had to conduct thematic analysis for the content that I gathered. I was unsure about how I should start. I was late in my schedule, and for this reason I have seek help from my mentor and online resources. I went through various research papers to understand the process, and with the help of that I was able to code and compile themes. After going through this process, I believe that I am more confident, and I will be able to work more efficiently in the future on such studies. As I have neglected quantitative study at the time, I aim to focus more on quantitative studies in the future and work more efficiently in terms of collection and complication of the data.

The most challenging time was the COVID-19 period when it struck as a pandemic and disturbed the social lives of the people. I was trying to collect the primary data by physically visiting my home country and meeting the potential respondents and conducting interviews in person. However, due to the lockdowns in both countries, air travel restrictions and uncertainty, I was not able to visit my home country, and, in this chaos, I wasted valuable time which I could have utilized in improving my research work. Ultimately, I had to rely on using online platforms for reaching and communicating the potential respondents and collecting data from them. As the summer was ending, I decided to formally pursue online communication methods for reaching out to the board members of the relevant companies in Laos because the situation was the COVID-19 problem was not improving. With a disturbed and unclear mindset, I started to contact potential respondents on social media and other online platforms.

During this process, I used some agents as well for efficiently completing the data collection process. I used some people in my social circle who are working professionals as a gateway for reaching out with potential respondents.

This approach helped me significantly because it was becoming difficult to set up online meetings with potential respondents i.e., different time-zone, availability of board members, their willingness and continuity of communication were some challenges that were addressed by engaging agents as gateway in this process. Few times it happened that the meetings had to be cancelled due to the sudden unavailability of certain board members and few times it happened that board members were not comfortable in answering the questions.

Overall, it was a difficult, time-taking and challenging process which taught me to be more patient as things does not always go as planned. WhatsApp voice calls and video calls were the main communication method used along with some skype calls for those respondents who preferred this method.

Putting my reflection in the lense of Gibbs' model, I can reflect with more preciseness using five stages of the reflective cycle developed by Graham Gibbs in 1988.

Source: Gibbs, (1988)

The first stage is about description of the situation or event. I can reflect here that I did my role of researcher and doctoral level student with my best efforts and commitment despite of challenges. My supervisor and the respondents of data collection performed their roles and in the end I have been able to address the established research aim and objectives.

The second stage is about feelings i.e, what I was thinking during the course of this research experience and what I felt. I was certainly nervous and unsure about my ability to complete the research process in the form of my thesis and it appeared to me that I will get stuck at some stage of this research process. With doubts and low confidence level I started and continued my journey of completing this thesis until I reached the final stages of thesis. However, now I feel different about the situation i.e., I have improved confidence about engaging in research activities and I have awareness of my strengths and weaknesses in the context of research work.

Third stage is about evaluation i.e., I need to objectively look into the practices and approaches that worked well or in my favor during this experience and also approaches that did not worked in my favor. I would state here that COVID-19 was the major negative situation faced during the research process due to which data collection process was halted and disrupted. However, the constant support of my supervisor was a positive aspect that helped me in pushing myself to work harder.

Fourth stage is about drawing conclusions from the experience i.e., by using the information that was collected during the course of research process. I can reflect here that I have and I intend to further improve my IT skills which helped me a great deal during the course of this thesis especially when COVID-19 crisis occurred. Moreover, I have and I intend to further develop my reading habit which was a vital element behind completing this thesis successfully. Overall, I have understood that I need to be well-

prepared for different kind of problems and situations while engaging in research activities.

Fifth stage is about preparing an action plan for prioritizing, clearly determining and pragmatically achieving the goals that I need to achieve for preparing myself effectively for similar research activities in future. I am considering to participate in some kind of training and development using different platforms such as, specific skills related courses on Udemy.

6.6.1 Reflexivity

During the data collection process, reflexivity usually involves evaluation of researchers' own belief systems, practices and judgements (Braun and Clarke, 2019). The objective of adopting reflexivity is to determine such personal beliefs that incidentally may have affected the research process. One must be prepared during reflexivity to question his/her own assumptions and pre-conceived notions. An integral role is played by the researcher during data collection process, especially when qualitative research is being carried out. Under reflexivity, part focus is given to the researcher and part to the subjects. A general acceptance is required of the fact that researchers are integral components of qualitative research process, and influence the project outcomes actively (Wilkinson, 2015).

In terms of my background, I can reflect here that I had limited experience of conducting large scale research, however I do have the background of business and management areas which kept me aware through most of the phases of this study. Only some aspects were surprising for me and pushed me at the backfoot especially the research methodology chapter i.e., I took a major chunk of time for exploring, reading and understanding the epistemological, ontological, interpretivism, and cross-sectional aspects of methodology chapter. The problem that I faced during this chapter was my memory i.e., after few weeks of developing my understanding, I used to feel less confident about my conceptual clarity towards the ontological and epistemological

dimensions. I even used hand written notes and drawn some pictures for properly understanding the functioning and difference between these dimensions. I felt that due to my lack of prior experience and understanding about the methodological paradigm of research, I faced this problem of loosing my focus and understanding.

In terms of my relationship with the participants of the study, I had no direct formal or informal relationship with any of th respondents included in the data collection process. I felt that this aspect helped me in asking the questions more confidently and conducting the interview more professionally. The kind of culture I come from, if I had to interview someone I knew beforehand, it would have been difficult for me to maintain complete professionalism and formality. This way, I have observed that while interpreting and analysing the results of interviews, I was able to apply an enhanced objective lense and was able to apply best efforts towards understanding the context of respondnts and their answers.

In the context of personal reflexivity, I can state here that my own upbringing, eduction and work experience in my home country influenced my analysis and especially the entire conclusion chapter in a positive way. For example, I was able to comprehend and relate the responses of the respondents in the light of literature and theoretical perspectives because I could precisely understand the situation of respondents and sometimes I extracted unspoken words from them as well.

7. References

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8. Appendices

A. Transcripts

Interview from managers of Construction Companies

Participant 1:

Q: What is your understanding about the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: Going on tours is not easy as the environment is highly uncertain where unexpected change can take place in any point. Different types of risks that can come about in tours include natural disasters, manmade disasters, changes in costs, injury to tourists etc. Most of the tours are carried out without such kind of events but the underlying chance of such risks are only present for which they need to be taken into account. Some events cannot be avoided such as road blockage for which certain margin has to be kept in plans along with allocating adequate funds.

Q: When you say preventing, what are the business plans and business strategies does your company use?

A: All type of risks is not preventable as they are not under human control for which one can only apply action to reduce its impact. The risks for which prevention can be applied include transportation breakdown, hotel unavailability etc. Proper checking is carried out of vehicle condition before leaving. Advance payment is made for the hotel booking to confirm invitation.

Q: When you Plan and identify about Risk Management, how did you plan, did you plan project by project please explain.

A: Different types of tours and plans are created where the risk associated with each plan varies significantly. This means that risk management varies from one project to another. It requires taking into account the current conditions and forecast number of scenarios that can potentially emerge which may pose threat for the company. Once the potential risks associated have been identified, the next step involves creating potential counter measures.

Q: Do you think by implementing the concept of Enterprise Risk Management help you to driving your business and help you in decision making performance?

A: Risk management is an important practice that should be applied on everyday basis. Our business had to learn the importance of risk management in a hard way since we faced disruption on several events that led to confusion and mismanagement. Focus should generally be on end customers, which we failed to accommodate effectively due to lack of preparation for such events.

Q: In the board directors meeting room, what are the main arguments in decision-making and how did you deal with that?

A: Main decision made generally revolves around the facts placed and proposed action that is to be taken for it. This action or advice is then reviewed critically by different members present in the team following which it gains approval. Main head of the organization generally has veto power over decisions but faced little resistance as most people believed in his capabilities.

Q: Do think different leadership of board directors has any impact on decision-making?

A: Leadership holds significant importance in our company as senior employees are seen to play the role of guiding beacon. They are expected to play mentoring role in the organization and make effort for developing their skills. Significant decision-making power is delegated to lower employees which allows them to make better decision according to the present scenario.

Participant 2:

Q: What is your understanding of the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: Prevention of several possible risks faced by a business is managed under the concept of Enterprise Risk Management. A business can face certain risks including financial, transportation-related threats, risks of not meeting goals, and risks related to sales targets. In my company, I will prefer to reduce possible risks through different policies.

Q: When you say preventing, what are the business plans and business strategies does your company use?

A: In my opinion, the risk management team can play a vital role in risk prevention. Therefore, I will utilize the services of this team to prevent risks in the company. The team would perform its duties in two steps. Firstly, it will study risks and identify possible risks. Secondly, it will take assistance from situations faced in the past and develop plans to prevent identified risks.

In addition to it, the compliance and policy will also support us in preventing risks. It will be helpful because it will highlight laws, roles, and responsibilities and assist a business

in working effectively. Moreover, it will be of great advantage regarding business partnerships and developing other relations required for the success of a business.

Q: When you Plan and identify Risk Management, how did you plan, did you plan project by project please explain.

A: Planning is an important element required for the success of a business. In a recent meeting, we planned to accomplish our goals by dividing them into short and long-term targets. Being a public company, we plan things for a long period. We have decided to accomplish our yearly goals every quarter.

Q: Do you think implementing the concept of Enterprise Risk Management helps you to drive your business and help you in decision-making performance?

A: Yes, it helps us in risk prevention. It does so by forecasting the possible risks and implementing plans to avoid those risks. Moreover, the compliance and policy also assist in this regard by offering a clear understanding of the roles and goals of the business and employees associated with it.

Q: In the board directors' meeting room, what are the main arguments in decision-making and how did you deal with that?

A: In our company, the environment in the board of directors meeting room is usually quite realistic. Heads of departments take part in the decision-making process and present their suggestions and possible risks. Effective communication skills and leadership abilities enable us to listen to all the disagreements and finally make a decision regarding several issues. So it can be said that the decision-making process of the company is participatory and all of the leaders are offered an opportunity to take part in it.

Q: Do you think different leadership of board directors has any impact on decision-making?

A: Every authority has its requirements and potentials and I admit that being a member of the board of directors too has its potentials. But I think decision-making is usually

influenced by being a shareholder of the company. Member with major shares will be given more importance during the decision-making than the member with minor shares.

Participant 3:

Q: What is your understanding of the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: Enterprise Risk Management involves ways and approaches used to prevent risks faced by the business. Risks faced by the business include accidents, financial threats, and risks related to resource allocation. I will make sure to focus on minimizing risks in the company.

Q: When you say preventing, what are the business plans and business strategies does your company use?

A: In my company risks' prevention will be made sure by taking services and assistance from the risk management team. This team will first identify possible risks in the business and then will develop realistic plans to prevent these risks.

In my opinion, estimating possible risks is of prime importance when it comes to initiating a business. Moreover, we will make sure to keep in view compliance and policy. It means that we will consider constitutional laws and regulations while running

our company. One of the advantages of compliance and policy is that it helps a business in developing positive relationships with its partners and stakeholders.

Q: When you Plan and identify Risk Management, how did you plan, did you plan project by project please explain.

A: In the recent annual meeting, we divided our goals into short and long-term goals. This method assists us in implementing strategies and accomplishing our main objective efficiently. It also plays a vital role in reducing and preventing the risks involved. I can provide an example of it. Presently our target is to accomplish 30% of the annual sale goal by the end of the first quarter.

Q: Do you think implementing the concept of Enterprise Risk Management helps you to drive your business and help you in decision-making performance?

A: Yes, of course, implementing the Enterprise Risk Management approach assists our company in accomplishing its goals. Being a public company, we need to plan for a long period and therefore we plan for a year and divide our yearly goals into quarters for achieving them easily. Compliance and policy will be helpful for us in risk prevention because they will highlight all rules and job descriptions. A clear understanding of these roles and rules will help in preventing possible risks to a greater extent and in improving the productivity of our company.

Q: In the board directors' meeting room, what are the main arguments in decision-making and how did you deal with that?

A: During meetings, we have different points of view and opinions. For instance, the director wants to increase yearly sales target, but the head of sales department think it is difficult as it would need investment in marketing. Accounts and finance department suggests that reducing or saving cost is important for long-term productivity of the company. It means to say that all of the departments are involved in the decision-making process. We keep in view disagreements of leaders and then plan possible ways to resolve issues. Communication helps us in understanding issues highlighted by heads of departments and in the decision-making process.

Q: Do think different leadership of board directors has any impact on decision-making?

A: In my opinion, the decision-making doesn't depend strongly on being a member of the board of directors. Instead, it depends on the share of the company. The shareholder with more shares will have a strong position during the decision-making process. However, being a major shareholder and member of the board of directors have certain requirement potentials and I think their decision-making is mostly dependant on profits enjoyed by them.

Participant 4:

Q: What is your understanding about the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: In every business there are always facing all types of Risks, from my perspective Enterprise Risk Management is all about how to prevent all those Risks such as unexpected threats, accidents in workplace or transportation and set all Goals. In my company we will focus preventing rather than Solving the issues, let say more than 80% is focusing on preventing.

Q: When you say preventing, what are the business plans and business strategies does your company use?

A: To prevent and avoid all those risks we need to plan, which we use Risk Management team, first of all Risk management team will analyse and identify what kind of risks will be faced. Secondly, Observation and examine from the past experiences and make adaptation in the current situation, all those risks that we might facing need to verify urgently and frequency.

I think to start every business, first we need to estimate what are risks that we might facing when we launch the business, our company has turned to public company, so we need to set formality rules like compliance and policy. When we mention compliance, it means all those rules have been already settled. For instance, we have followed the law, constitution, and polity, all those things will allow the company to dominate and control our employees. Basically, I think compliance and policy is helping company to

avoid arguments with our partnerships and to gain both side advantages. I will attach the company briefly road map, it will you to understand our enterprise 's implication like who are connect to our enterprise such as partnerships, stakeholders, board of directors, employees, customers and clients, and Government.

Q: When you Plan and identify about Risk Management, how did you plan, did you plan project by project please explain.

A: As our company is public company, in annual meeting we have settled long term and short time goals. For example, I'm the director of petrol department, our department will set the long-term vision and mission then broke it down in details then apply strategies to achieve all those goals efficiently to reducing and preventing risks by risk assessment, let say our aim is to achieve at less 30% of the annual sell goal by the first quarter.

Q: Do you think by implementing the concept of Enterprise Risk Management help you to driving your business and help you in decision making performance?

A: Obviously, adopting the concept of Enterprise Risk Management allow our company to achieve company's goals, as I mentioned earlier our company is Public company, we need to plan ahead we can't just only plan for tomorrow or the day after tomorrow, if we compare to Small and Medium Enterprise, they might only plan for the next month but our company have settled 1 year plan and broke it down in quarter goals. As I mentioned, compliance and policy will help our company to reduce and prevent all those risk that we might facing. For instance, compliance and policy will mention all those rules, roles, and job description (JD), what is the CEO, CFO role and power, what are our missions and visions, so all those things are the key tools to minimise and prevent risks in order to help company performance and gain advantage foe stakeholders.

Q: In the board directors meeting room, what are the main arguments in decision-making and how did you deal with that?

A: In every meeting environments, obviously we all have different opinions and perspective so quite often that we disagreed let say director wants to increase the sell

from last year 20% but sell department think we could reach that target but we need to invest on advertise but the accountant and financial department want to save cost and reduce some capital, so every department are involve when it comes to decision-making, we need to compromise and come up with the solutions which refer to our business plan and risk assessment plan. Let say our aim of this year we need to make profit 10 million USD just from petrol department but after first 2 quarters director want to increase the profit from 10M to 15M that could be our business arguments and again every disagreement that might occur we need to refer to our business plan and risk assessment plan.

Q: Do think different leadership of board directors has any impact on decision-making?

A: I think to become the member of board directors you need to have requirement potentials, but obviously different people have different working style and leadership style, but in the decision-making, we need to base on the share of the company the major shareholder will have more power in decision-making, but as I mentioned major shareholder and other member of board directors they have requirement potentials, I think they know what they are doing and I think mostly are based on their benefits and profit.

Participant 5:

Q: What is your understanding about the concept of ERM?

A: ERM do you mean enterprise risk management isn't it, I think it means you got to identify the risk, you may have risk analyse and you may come out with the plan to manage properly, and you need to prevent and avoiding unpredict risk.

Q: Do you think your firm adopt and implement ERM concept?

A: I think most of the companies what I have worked with they have risk management plan or their own strategies but when it comes to enterprise risk management it's very problematic and they don't take it seriously due to the resources, the capacities of our own employee.

I think the way they identify the risk is very simple, just based on their experience if the financial performance is right then they think they company have done well.

Q: since you said most of the firms in Laos they don't adopt and implement the concept of ERM properly, how do the board director manage to make good decision-making progress?

A: As I said early, mainly based on my working experience, when they talk about risk management and the way they identify the risks they mainly look at the financial perspective for example: the flow of the funds, the funds could undermine their business for instance if they can't get the loan from the bank.

Because many businesses here can't run really well, they can't make a lot of profit, it risky if the bank will give them loans. So, they are usually based in financial perspective into account when they access the risk.

Large size enterprises they also take into account, the chains in businesses for example the supply chain could come into play when they run the business for example the international companies.

Q: Do you mean it depends of the size of the firm, let say small and medium enterprises they don't really adopt ERM but when it comes to large size firms do you think they doing better in term of implementing ERM?

A: Yes exactly, that what I'm trying to explain, the large size of businesses is usually own by foreigners the big shareholders are foreigners. So, it's critical because the western business models have adopted. Beer Laos is very good example I think, they have very good system in place, they have very good business plan, they have their own risk assessment and Risk mitigation plan in place.

Q: Since small and medium enterprises didn't adopt the ERM concept, what the outcome of decision making, does it only base in financial performance?

A: As I explain earlier, for SMEs they usually use the financial pressure to define the risk and to make decision what should come next. if they can't make profit or they can't generate revenue from their business activities it just means they didn't manage it

properly and many enterprises have been pushed away from the market particularly most recently during covid-19 crisis, they can't handle the change, so they have to get out of the market.

Q: Apart from financial performance what are other factors that impact or influence their decision-making?

A: Well, I think consumption plays a very big role in decision-making for example as you know many enterprises in Laos are small and medium sizes, so if the consumption is getting low it's very likely that they will decide to close down the business. So, the market size in Laos and the fact that they can't export to overseas that much.

Q: Do you think most of the firms know what is Enterprise Risk Management is?

A: No, I don't think so, I think only few companies, as I said earlier only big firms those own by foreigner or have international shareholders, only those firms that they are implementing ERM plan.

I think for those small and medium firm when we talk about enterprise risk management it sounds unfamiliar to them, but you would see in their business plan they do have the similar thing like risk management plan.

Q: Do you know COSO framework?

A: what does that mean, I don't know that, but I know something else which call business risk mitigation strategy (BRMS).

Q: In the future, do you think implementing/adopting ERM framework will help driving your company performance or not?

A: well, yes and no... yes I think it's always the best for the business to be aware of the risk when they run the business. But at the same time, it also depends on the context and the size of the enterprise for instance, for sure ERM or RM is something they need to invest and adopt it in practical way not just leave it as papers. Based on my experience ERM seems to complicate, they want to keep it simple, as I said earlier it does not mean the company does not have any plan regarding the risk assessment.

Q: Do you the way they run the business and risk assessment/analyse in traditional way? No proper framework?

A: Yeah, they use traditional way to identify their risk, so they would look at the market, look at the consumptions, the trends. For example: for the IT industry they know that digitalisation trend is coming, risk for them they can't just realise in the physical things. So, I think they just follow the trend rather than forward thinking or planning ahead like in next 5 years or 10 years what would come next.

Q: Since the firm doesn't adopt and doesn't want to invest in ERM, do you think leadership style has an impact for decision making?

A: definitely, leadership style of direct or the CEO of the company play a brutal part and I think it also depends on the culture perspective as well like those CEO who are local, whose not oversea educated they would think let's play it by ears and handle things when it comes. That quite a big different for those companies which run by the foreigners or the shareholders(Ltd or public) or Laos people but graduated from oversea they would have adopted risk or the business models or even ERM into the organisational culture, they are more well prepare for any risk that might harm or effect business operation.

Q: Would you recommend those companies to adopt ERM framework?

A: Yes, because my main role is to identify their business plans, risk management plan, we call it really simple Risk assessment and copping plan it's the part of busines plan. I usually encourage them to assess and predict the risk that would affect their business. But again, it's required investment, many enterprises show very low willingness to embrace, they just think small, they think they don't need to invest too much in preparing for any risk instead of that they just focus on the number how to generate the revenue.

For instance, during this Covid crisis they don't know how to deal with this situation because they don't have any risk mitigation strategy like they don't calculate what is the worst case.

Q: In your opinion, what is the best step to help them to improve the decision-making process if they don't adopt ERM framework?

A: I think we should not be giving up pushing them to implement any kind of risk mitigation or risk assessment or risk management but what we need to do is to localise it, try to contextualise to make it suitable for SMEs. I don't even think we should enterprise Risk Management just call it very simple like business Risk management.

Q: yeah but those have similar meaning.

A: When they make their business plan, it's always the section that talk about risk analysis or risk assessment. They usually come up with coping measurement or machinating. They usually identify the Risk as Low, Medium or High they do have that process in their business plan. But the way they set it; they conceptualise it not really practical. They just create it for the sake of habit, they just to make it look good for the loan sometime. It's also important to advocate the tiff of practical of risk management plan with the people of the Ministry of Industry and Commerce because these people who are the one who look at the plan, they should be the one who verify and validate their plan.

The government should raise the awareness of Risk management for those SMEs because before they start running their business, they need to get the license, they will get all that guidance from those people in ministry.

Q: Since you said the analyse the risk by the level like Low, Medium and High, Do you actually breakdown risk in detail?

A: Yes, but the problem is the people, the people who own the company, they don't really understand the concept of Risk Management or ERM, they don't understand how to analyse or classify the risk, they kind of mess up sometimes, that lead to mitigation plan is not really practical and again we will just go back to the points that I mentioned

earlier they just want their business plan to be approved and get business certificate from ministry of industry and commerce.

Also, they don't have resources, by resources I mean financial and Human resources, for instance, if some enterprise identifies legal compliance as a risk, because they are new they don't know about the law, so legal compliance should be the risk for them that they could be ordered to shut down the business but the point is that they don't have the expertise who knows about the law in the company. That is why I keep saying they are concern about invest in the area that they consider or identify as a risk. It is not only about now I know what the Risk is are, it's also about how you will deal with those risks.

Q: The concept of ERM is not only about identify the risk but also about prevent the risk and unexpected threat and setting future goals as well, I think really think they understand the concept of Risk management or BRMS that you mentioned earlier.

A: Exactly, I think the term of management is also unfamiliar to them, because mostly they can identify the risk although sometime is not really practical. But the main problem is how to manage the risk because you identify it and you get the plan and you get prepare for your resources to deal with the risk when it comes. Of course, the risk is something that can happen in the future, many enterprises they don't really care about the future especially SMEs, they problem is they just identify it but they don't have plan to deal with it in term of managing the risk.

Q: In your perspective, in the nearly future will they adopt or implement the concept of Enterprise Risk management?

A: I think it possible they will adopt Risk Management because things are changing in Laos, the Covid-19 is lesson learned for them, for many businesses they have to be forward thinking and taking the Risk into account seriously and the fact that they have to be competitive in the market as well.

The joint plan model has become more popular in our country for example the estate business they have to do the joint plan with foreign investors, so I think to that mechanism or business pattern I think they will need to Adopt the Enterprise Risk management step by step. They will be influenced from their business partner and also the market as well. for example, the handicraft products they export to Japan, when the

covid starts the market they can't export to Japan so they will reverse back to the people in Laos why you don't find another way to ship.

I think there is a law about bankruptcy to assess if the business is about to go bankrupt, so the Government, particularly the Ministry of Planning and Investment, and Ministry of Industry and Commerce they will monitor the business performance of the firms, I have seen many business declare themselves as bankrupt and the government also ordered some businesses to close down because their poor business performance so that also link to Risk management, or Risk mitigation plan.

So, I think the government also monitor risk management plan more closely, the light of adopting ERM in your sense is possible. One day we will get there with the help of government.

Participant 6:

Q: What is your understanding of the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: Ans Every business faces a number of risks and implementing effective policies to decline these risks is called Enterprise Risk Management. These risks involve financial constraints, uncertainty regarding achievement of sales targets, discrimination in cost, transportation challenges, influence of political factors on the performance of the firm, and others. I think the role of leadership is of great importance in Enterprise Risk Management as decision making process of businesses mainly involve leaders or managers.

Q: When you say preventing, what are the business plans and business strategies does your company use?

A: Risks faced by a business couldn't be eliminated completely however they can be minimized. My company would use data to develop plans and strategies for risk minimization. I would make sure to monitor situations keenly so that risks such as transportation breakdown could be prevented. I would also make sure to develop budget plans using advance software and services of experts to prevent financial risk. Moreover I would declare job roles to employees so that maximum productivity could be attained and organizational goals could be met.

Q: When you Plan and identify Risk Management, how did you plan, did you plan project by project please explain.

A: We believe that planning is crucial for success of a business. The planning approaches we use vary based on situations and resources available. However, we mostly divide our annual targets in four parts and attain each goal in the duration of 4 months. For instance, this year we divided our sales target in four parts and successfully attained goal for this quarter. It is important to note that we keep our planning flexible so that possible or sudden risks do not impact organizational goals significantly.

Q: Do you think implementing the concept of Enterprise Risk Management helps you to drive your business and help you in decision-making performance?

A: Yes, I think it is a great concept and helps my business attain goals by improving the decision-making process. It helps managers in knowing about possible threats and being prepared for what is about to come. Our Enterprise Risk Management strategy helped us in maintaining our performance during the pandemic and assisted us in attaining sales target. Moreover, saving costs through this approach assist us in ensuring sustainable growth of the firm.

Q: In the board directors' meeting room, what are the main arguments in decision-making and how did you deal with that?

A: Difference in opinions is a major challenge that I face during the board of directors' meetings. Usually, the difference in opinions is related to policies we develop for the firm. For instance, directors usually focus on increasing sales target but when sales manager insist on the need of investment for this purpose finance manager discusses importance of saving cost for sustainable growth. It makes decision-making process complicated and sometimes impacts major organizational goals. I utilize informal communication skills to resolve such issues and involve everyone in the decision-making process by collecting feedback from them.

Q: Do think different leadership of board directors has any impact on decision-making?

A: Board directors strongly impact the decision-making process of the firm, but I think they don't have equal say in organizational matters. It is because more authority is given to members with greater shares of the business.

Participant 7:

Q: What is your understanding of the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: Enterprise Risk Management involves all approaches that could be utilized to protect a business from possible risks or that could decline risk factor for the firm and help it in experiencing growth and success. Risks faced by a business include failure to optimally utilize resources, financial constraints, and infrastructure development. Risk management requires experts to develop a plan and implement policies in the organization. Therefore, it cannot be achieved without the interest of employees and leadership.

Q: When you say preventing, what are the business plans and business strategies does your company use?

A: Increase in the trend of latest technologies in organizational cultures has made it possible for the leadership to prevent a business from possible risks. To ensure prevention in my company I would hire risk management experts and focus on promoting planning and cooperative working in the organizational culture. This would help me in increasing productivity of the firm and preparing the workforce to face challenges. I would also focus on utilizing cost saving approaches.

Q: When you Plan and identify Risk Management, how did you plan, did you plan project by project please explain.

A: In my opinion stepwise planning ensures stable growth of a business and help leaders to prevent risks. Therefore, I usually practice project by project planning. It helps me in focusing on short-run targets or goals and doesn't expose all of the available resources to possible threats or risks. It is also advantageous as it helps me in ensuring cooperative participation of the workforce and doesn't increase their workload.

Q: Do you think implementing the concept of Enterprise Risk Management helps you to drive your business and help you in decision-making performance?

A: Decision-making process is all about developing policies for the business. In my opinion risk management positively impacts the decision-making process of a firm as it provides clear picture of events and improve foresight skills of the leadership. It is crucially important for development and implementation of effective policies. I think leaders should focus on it for policy-making purposes.

Q: In the board directors' meeting room, what are the main arguments in decision-making and how did you deal with that?

A: The meeting consists of different members from different departments and all of them have their own opinions. Owners of the company are usually interested in increasing growth of the firm and suggest increasing targets. But managers of respective departments have their own view about things and are aware of challenges. This discussion sometimes rises conflicts and disputes. However, I always try my best to not create tension in the meeting room and respect everyone's opinion as it listening to every member makes it easy for me and board members to decide about targets.

Q: Do think different leadership of board directors has any impact on decision-making?

A: Board of directors are valuable members of the business, and their opinions are respected by everyone. However, as far as their influence on the decision-making is concerned, I think it depends on number of shares they have.

Participant 8:

Q: What is your understanding of the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: The enterprise risk management is a concept that is used to minimize risk factor for the business by implementing different approaches. Risk factor for business depends on the nature of business, political situations, and the industry it is operating in. For a construction business the following elements could be risks. Unavailability of sufficient financial resources, infrastructure development, government policies, and transport related issues.

Q: When you say preventing, what are the business plans and business strategies does your company use?

A: Every business struggle to prevent itself from risks at the decline business productivity and raise a question on its sustainable growth. To prevent my company

from risks I would hire expert staff. I would practice effective communication skills to convey objectives of the business efficiently to the workforce minimize issues faced by them. I would promote use of advanced tools in the organizational culture to access the risk factor and control it.

Q: When you Plan and identify Risk Management, how did you plan, did you plan project by project please explain.

A: I prefer practicing long-run planning. Though I divide organizational targets in parts long-run planning helps me in knowing about the availability of resources and provide the clear picture of a yearly plan. It also makes it easy for the workforce to understand the objective of the year and motivate them to slowly work for that.

Q: Do you think implementing the concept of Enterprise Risk Management helps you to drive your business and help you in decision-making performance?

A: Decision-making process decides the fate of a business. While developing policy that is important for leaders you have complete knowledge about situations faced by the business. This knowledge is provided by enterprise risk management. Therefore, I think that it plays great role in the decision-making process and help leadership in running business.

Q: In the board directors' meeting room, what are the main arguments in decision-making and how did you deal with that?

A: Conflicts are a part of every business. Where there are more than one owner, there are conflicts. During meeting, I have observed that business owners focus on increased revenue generation. While managers of departments insist on ensuring sustainable growth as it is the only thing that helps a business to gather market power and stay active in the industry. I use my communication skills to prevent the tension in the meeting room.

Q: Do think different leadership of board directors has any impact on decision-making?

A: I think this depends on shares directors have.

Interview from board members of Tourism Industry companies

Participant 1:

Q: what is your understanding of the concept of Enterprise Risk management?

A: Based on my past experiences, Enterprise Risk management is the core value need to contribute to the business. So, I understand that every business has its risk but it depends on the owner of the company how they monitor. For my company, risk depends on many factors, for instance, Risk on people, Risk on financial circumstance, Risk on decision. So, in general every decision has risk but it how we optimise the Risk.

Q: Do you think your firm adopt or implement the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: I would say all the Risk depends on decision making whether or not you will go further, my enterprise I would say we have Risk Parameter that has been set. Many of the firms have certain level of Risk parameter for example my company when I think about Risk, the first thing that comes to my mind is financial risk as you see the

pandemic some of the firms they are slowing down and many of the firm are facing bankrupt. But how I manage my financial circumstance is I reserve 3 types of funds. First is emergency fund, every earning I reserve 10% and another 10% is reserve for maintenance and the other 10% is the net profit need to pay back to individual staff, I mean everyone who contributes on sale but the concept of Risk management on people my only concern is the internal confidential information before we recruited people, we have contract to sign I am not quite sure if this is the answer that you are looking for but this is what my perspective is. The contract to sign we will share some information with only executive management comity and who will not. We find the talent on themselves; we will have 3 months' probation. So, 3 months' probation is time for testing our Risk, we will give them a big job challenging job and will see how they will manage, if they don't pass, I will only offer normal executive position rather than senior position.

Q: What are the factors that help you in decision making in each project?

A: first I need to plan further, look into tiny details, I would say every point that I need to have a look, my people need to be ready, once my people ready and the plan is ready it means the project is ready to start. I mean practical project.

Q: As you mention your people, how do share your data base with your employees?

A: I will select based on their expertise, who will become our senior leadership management comity based on their pass experience, I will ask them or evaluate them to see what the company reason and mission statement is. What we are going to be in the next 5 or 10 years, if they are understanding of the context that I have demonstrate and release some of the project for them to manage. Once they can manage, I will be more than welcome and delight them and welcome them on board senior leadership management comity.

Q: Do you think leadership style has the impact on how you manage people?

A: indeed, I can say I'm not bossy style, I think boss and leader are totally different every cooperate strategy that I have in my mind, what I have planned, I allow everyone

in my company to contribute what do they think, what can they imagine the firm that they currently worked with, what they really want our firm in the future. Would they want to see the firm getting bigger, and they get higher position, I think I'm quite adapting on against methodology if you aware of this.

I think everyone works under the same team not each department, because all of them is vehicle to drive company ahead.

Q: Do you think you employees understand the concept of Enterprise Risk Management or not?

A: I think they aware of it because every time I plan on something, I will tell to think 380 degree more than 360 degree, what is the potential, what is the impact, what if it impact our branding, because we are not doing only for money, we are doing and creating something for customers to see our value we give that is our core value preposition, focusing on the value for our customers not commercially I would say.

To answer in the right direction about the risk in my company is to share what they thought and allow them what we can drive, and they will think about the risk later when I ask them questions.

Q: Do you think enterprise risk management helps you to minimise the risk in your company or not?

A: I would say it is, because as I mention before management style in each firm it's really different, if we going to make our firm to meet international standardisation I think it's they key value that you start thinking about the impact that make our brand reputation and go way around that may impact on our financial position as well as investing in people because they company growing people the core value, if we invest and they are staying with us that is my risk.

Q: Since most 80% of the firms in Laos they don't aware of Enterprise Risk management, do you think in the future will those firm invest their money in human resources in particular to raise the awareness of enterprise risk management?

A: Hmm, I think if the company want to grow Rapido developing themselves, risk mitigation or even the concept of Risk management it's really important because you are the reputation today is your income tomorrow. They should think around not risking around.

Q: have you heard about COSO framework before?

A: I'm afraid not would you mind explaining more.

Q: It's the organisation who invented and developing the Risk framework, the framework itself explain how you identify the risk, preventing, deal with unexpected threat, find the alternative solution for the risk and even setting future goals.

A: I see how to access the risk and monitoring

Q: How you deal with it basically.

A: I think it depends on company size, and how they are ready to get more market share, I would say in Laos when they think about the risk, I would say it challenging to drive company in the certain level but Risk is the good thing because it allow us to take a chance and make sure our plan is ready before we hit the market.

It's all about internal communication isn't it. You will sit in the meeting room discuss about your confidential information, if our information leaks, I think it incidentally this also call risk.

Q: In your opinion, what step or action are essential for improving decision making process in general don't need to be only on financial performance.

A: Well, decision making is depending on what kind of project that we are handle, if it quiet challenging I would do my research as much as I can, check the data adapt to my planning and then I start to send those information to relevant department to start the project.

Q: Since most of the company they don't know the concept of enterprise risk management, do you think the government should promote the awareness of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: yeah, I think it's quite important for government to emphasis because it's internal management if the information is leaking the competitor can take advantage from that. I think ERM is all about how we manage our plan and how we control the environment that we design to release our plan, if you can trust the person, they can keep it confidential I think it should be fine, I would say every country has been aware about this, but it depends on personal characterise in the certain people as well.

Participant 2:

Q: What do you understand about the concept of enterprise risk management (ERM) in the light of your experience in your organization?

A: The Laos PDR, a LDC country (additional LLDC Landlocked Least Developed Country) is still depending heavily on donor support. The national and provincial parliaments as highest body of a country/provinces overseeing the executive, shaping and promulgating legislation and being the elected representatives of the people of the country need to assess risks on a regular basis, continuously and on different levels: political risks, structural risks, management risks.

Q: Do you think that your company needs to implement ERM. If yes, then what are the reasons behind it?

A: Since the National Assembly (8th Legislature) and the People's Provincial Assemblies (1st Legislature, established in 2016) are young parliaments capacities of parliamentarians and staff still need to be built and developed. In this regard the country is still depending on technical and financial donor support. Using donor funds needs a strict ERM to be highly transparent towards the entity itself (using and spending the funds), the respective donor and the 'taxpayers' of the respective country, donor funds come from. Donors themselves need to follow a strict ERM.

The ERM is regularly assessed. Every donor has its own ERM in the project, UNDP e.g. assess risks of project implementation at least every quarter per annum. Other donor access risks in the beginning and mid-term of the project. Most of the donors identify the risks annually, others even identify risks per activity – describing which risks can hinder the successful implementation of an activity/training etc. (e.g., the German Rosa

Luxemburg Foundation, which is supporting the National Assembly, access each activity to be implemented on risks).

Q: Can you share an experience of the board room which you think is best exhibition of the decision-making process and nature of decision making prevalent in the board?

A: ERM according to the COSO (Committee of Sponsoring Organisation of the Treadway Commission) approach is in fact the basis for the mandate and functioning of this internal structure, which in this sense also functioning as an anti-corruption structure. This ICPMS function a coordination mechanism but first and foremost as a control structure, overseeing donor funds and the 'correct' use of this funds so in the end overseeing 'potential' risks with the goal of minimizing any risk.

Q: Can you explain an incident when board engaged in risk management and its identification/ measurement?

A: The ICPMS immediately responded to all donors on the lockdown where all activities were suspended for an uncertain time-period. The ICPMS monitored the development of the pandemic carefully and identified at early-stage scenarios after the pandemic all the time in close coordination with the respective donors. This enabled donors to provide unused funds to other projects in case they were able to operate. Once the lockdown was released, the ICPMS were able to immediately implement activities in the NA and PPAs which lowered the risk to not being able to fulfil the planned workplan in 2020. So, the risk was due to good monitoring and coordination of the ICPMS minimized extremely.

Q: What was the result and outcome of the risk management practice that your board conducted in terms of its impact on firm performance consistent?

A: Slow decision-making by the NA is often experienced. Diverging views between the Executive and the Legislature regarding the changes of the respective roles and responsibilities of the Institutions. Weaknesses in stakeholder coordination leading to overlapping initiatives and gaps in development assistance. Also, the lack of financial resources etc can be seen as a major challenge.

The ICPMS follows this regular risk management practice for all projects as one of its main mandates.

Q: Can you explain an event or incident which reflected the adoption of COSO framework in the board room decision making and risk management practices?

A: In fact, the National Assembly ICPMS includes ERM on the basis of implementation of projects since they sign responsible for the proper use of funds and timely implementation of agreed activities. (see samples attached to this questionnaire).

Q: What you felt and learnt from the exhibition of different leadership styles in terms of suitability for board decision effectiveness?

A: The decision was made by the National Assembly in August 2013 by an NA decree to establish the ICPMS mandated with strict monitoring, coordinating and ERM on 'external' support to the parliament. With the establishment of Provincial Peoples Assemblies (PPAs) and support has been extended to all 18 PPAs, the ICPMS covers them too.

Participant 3:

Q: What do you understand about the concept of enterprise risk management (ERM) in the light of your experience in your organization?

A: Here in the Laos PDR are facing: the 'risk' of spending donor funds ('taxpayers' money) properly along the financial requirements and guidelines of the parliament and the requirements and guidelines of the respective donor on the other side, since these parliaments here are still receiving donor support.

Q: Do you think that your company needs to implement ERM. If yes, then what are the reasons behind it?

A: So, the 'implementer or beneficiary' (of donor support) and the donor itself need to assess 'possible' risks. Designing a support project to the parliaments here in Laos PDR requires project documents, developed by the donor organization/country and the beneficiary. Designing these project documents always include a so called "Risk Log", where all the 'possible risks are listed. Often donors also identify the risks in numbers (1 low/5 high). Risks can change within the duration of projects depending to its political, economic, social, and other environments the project is embedded into.

E.g. risk management by UNDP, oner donor to the parliaments in Laos PDR:

“Risk and uncertainty are inherent in many of UNDP’s activities. Achieving its mission of eradicating poverty and reducing inequalities and exclusion requires the organization to take risks. UNDP has an elaborated Enterprise Risk Management framework (ERM)[1] embedded in its Programme and Operations Policies and Procedures (POPP). The steps of the risk management process are as follows:

- Establishing the context
- Risk assessment
- Risk treatment
- Monitoring and review; and
- Communication and consultation

The detailed policy for risk management at programme and project level is currently under development. At the project level, UNDP currently applies adaptation of PRINCE2 project management method. A Risk Log of each project is available online in Atlas (UNDP’s ERP) as part of each project’s documentation.

Q: Can you share an experience of the board room which you think is best exhibition of the decision-making process and nature of decision making prevalent in the board?

A: To respond to these ERM requirements and in terms of an efficient, transparent, accountable, and sustainable donor project implementation, the National Assembly established an entity, the ICPMS: The International Cooperation and Project Management Secretariat (ICPMS). This is an NA structure as long as the Laos parliaments receive external support. This entity is: (1) A ‘one-point entry of external support to the parliaments; (2) Proactively communicate NA program strategies, priorities and projects to development partners; (3) Oversee the use of donor funds within the NA (ERM); Identify and connect donors with relevant partners within the NA; Ensure transparency between donor projects (ERM); (4) Protect against repetitive reporting on donor-funded projects and activities; (5) Improve communication and synergies between the NA committees and donor-funded projects.

Q: Can you explain an incident when board engaged in risk management and its identification/ measurement?

A: Once donors are engaged with a project in the Laos parliaments for a certain time, parliaments develop along these projects annual and quarterly workplans and set deadlines for implementation of specific identified activities. A risk for all projects supporting the National Assembly and Provincial People’s Assemblies is not being able to implement activities in time and according to implementation deadlines. So, the lockdown of the Laos PDR from the 29 March 2020 (Prime Ministers Decree No 06, 29 March 2020) on due to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic was an unforeseen risk threaten the implementation of NA/PPA – donor support.

Q: What was the result and outcome of the risk management practice that your board conducted in terms of its impact on firm performance consistent?

A: Due to the existence of this ICPMS which regular monitors all ‘possible’ risks carefully, we were able to minimize risks in implementation of donor support. The team of the ICPMS is monitoring all projects on an almost daily basis to manage the risks might occur. Risks identified by the ICPMS e.g.:

- Insubstantial ownership to implement some activities
- Over-expectations from the NA and PPA Members and staffers about the scope of the new project
- Expectations from the public about what the National Assembly and Provincial People’s Assemblies are able to deliver
- Citizens’ reluctance to express their opinions or viewpoints in public meetings with or communications to parliamentarians
- Unwillingness of parliamentarians to “listen” to citizen “voice” and to reflect citizen viewpoints in the NA and PPAs
- Absorptive capacity of the NA and PPAs may not meet expectations
- Project activities are not fully implemented due to lack of resources, including human resources

Q: Can you explain an event or incident which reflected the adoption of COSO framework in the board room decision making and risk management practices?

A: In fact, the National Assembly ICPMS includes ERM on the basis of implementation of projects since they sign responsible for the proper use of funds and timely implementation of agreed activities. (see samples attached to this questionnaire).

Q: What you felt and learnt from the exhibition of different leadership styles in terms of suitability for board decision effectiveness?

A: The National Assembly followed different management schemes for implementing programmes and projects funded by donors with different and no success. Only the establishment of an entity, which is entirely mandated to include strict monitoring, coordinating and ERM on 'external' support to the parliaments in the end worked to accomplish the accountability, trust and transparency needed if working with 'taxpayers' money.

Q: What steps you think your company board needs to take for effectively using ERM. Explain with suitable examples.

A: The ICPMS needs to harmonise ERM for all incoming projects. At present the different donors to the national and provincial parliaments follow different ERM schemes determined by their entity. To ensure efficient ERM and therefore also being more accountable towards donors and the parliaments ERM approaches of all donors need to be harmonised, so following an parliament ERM rather than ERMs of each donor.

Participant 4:

Q: what is your understanding of the concept of Enterprise Risk management?

A: In view of my knowledge about ERM, Enterprise Risk management is the basic belief need to contribute to the business. Thus, I comprehend that each business has it own risks however it relies upon the proprietor of the organization how they observe that risk. For my organization, risk relies upon numerous variables, for example, Risk on individuals, Risk on monetary situation, Risk on choice. Thus, as a rule each choice has risk however it how we work along the Risk.

Q: Do you think your firm adopt or implement the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: I would say all the Risk relies upon dynamics of whether you will go further, or not. I would say we have Risk Parameter that has been set. A significant number of the organizations have certain degree of Risk boundary for instance my organization when I consider Risk, the main thing that goes to my mine is monetary risk as you see the pandemic a portion of the organizations they are easing back down and a considerable lot of the firm are confronting bankrupt. Yet, how I deal with my monetary condition develop the way through which Risk management is decided. The agreement to sign we will impart some data to just leader the board comity and who won't. We discover the ability on themselves; we will have 3 months' probation to deal with the risk and mitigate it. Thus, 3 months' probation is the ideal opportunity for testing our Risk, we will give them a difficult task testing position and will perceive how they will oversee, in the event that they don't pass, I will just offer ordinary leader position as opposed to senior position.

Q: What are the factors that help you in decision making in each project?

A: first I need to design further, investigate minuscule subtleties, I would say each point that I need to see, my kin should be prepared, when my kin prepared, and the arrangement is prepared it mean the plan is prepared to begin. I mean functional plan.

Q: As you mention your people, how do share your data base with your employees?

A: I will choose to be dependent on their aptitude, who will turn into our senior management and the executive's committee into resourceful elements. I will ask them or assess them to perceive what the organization's aim and statement of purpose is. What we will be in the following 5 or 10 years, on the off chance that they have the knowledge of the setting that I have shown and delivered them a portion of the task for them to oversee. When they can oversee, I will greet and welcome them on board senior authority the executive's comity.

Q: Do you think leadership style has the impact on how you manage people?

A: in reality, I can say I'm not bossy style, I think leaders may have varying method to coordinate that I permit everybody in my organization to contribute what do they figure out about managing risk, what would they be able to envision from the firm and right now worked with, what they truly need in our firm later on. I think everybody works under a similar group in every office, since every one of them have a vehicle to drive organization ahead.

Q: Do you think you employees understand the concept of Enterprise Risk Management or not?

A: I believe that the employees are capable to take decisions for their own. Yet, they need guidance on risk management. Even if they are familiar with the notion of risk management, they need to be mindful on how things work. To reply to the correct way about the risk in my organization is to share their opinion, about the risk later when I ask them regarding it.

Q: Do you think enterprise risk management helps you to minimise the risk in your company or not?

A: I would say it is, because when we are able to understand and perceive the risk earlier, it makes it easy for us to manage with the challenges and foresee them. However, we do not have the resources that it takes to be mindful of risks.

Q: Since most 80% of the firms in Laos they don't aware of Enterprise Risk management, do you think in the future will those firm invest their money in human resources in particular to raise the awareness of enterprise risk management?

A: Well, I think if the organization need to develop Rapido creating themselves, risk moderation or even the idea of Risk the executives it's truly significant on the grounds that you are the standing today is your tomorrow. They should think around without gambling around.

Q: have you heard about COSO framework before?

A: I'm afraid not would you mind explaining more.

Q: It's the organisation who invented and developing the Risk framework, the framework itself explain how you identify the risk, preventing, deal with unexpected threat, find the alternative solution for the risk and even setting future goals.

A: I see how to access the risk and monitoring

Q: How you deal with it basically.

A: I think it relies upon organization size, and how they are prepared to get more piece of the overall industry, I would say in Laos when they consider the risk I would say it trying to drive organization in the specific level however Risk is the beneficial thing since it permit us to take a risk and ensure our arrangement is prepared before we hit the market.

It's about inner correspondence isn't it.. you will sit in the gathering room examine about your private data, if our data spills, I think it by chance this additionally call risk.

Q: In your opinion, what step or action are essential for improving decision making process in general don't need to be only on financial performance.

A: All things considered, dynamic is relying upon what sort of plan that we are handle, on the off chance that it calm testing I would do my examination however much I can, check the information adjust to my arranging and afterward I begin to send those data to pertinent office to begin the task.

Q: Since most of the company they don't know the concept of enterprise risk management, do you think the government should promote the awareness of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: better believe it I believe it's very significant for government to accentuation since it's inner management if the data is releasing the contender can exploit from that. I think ERM is about how we deal with our arrangement and how we control the climate that we configuration to deliver our arrangement, on the off chance that you can believe the individual they can keep it secret I figure it ought to be fine, I would say each nation has known about this, yet it relies upon individual describe in the specific individuals also.

Participant 5:

Q: What is your understanding about the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: Going on risk management isn't simple as the climate is profoundly dubious where startling change can occur in any point. Various sorts of risk that can come to completion in risk management incorporate catastrophic events, obstacles, changes in costs, injury to travelers and so forth. The greater part of the risk management are completed without such sort of occasions yet the fundamental possibility of such risk are just present for which they should be considered. A few occasions can't be covered in managing risk, for example, street blockage for which certain edge must be kept in plans alongside dispensing sufficient assets.

Q: When you say preventing, what are the business plans and business strategies does your company use?

A: All sort of risk are not preventable as they are not under human control for which one can just apply activity to diminish its effect. The risk for which anticipation can be applied incorporate transportation breakdown, inn inaccessibility and so on. Appropriate looking at is conveyed of vehicle condition prior to leaving. Advance installment is made for the lodging booking to affirm greeting.

Q: When you Plan and identify about Risk Management, how did you plan, did you plan project by project please explain.

A: Various kinds of risk management and plans are made where the risk related with each arrangement shifts altogether. This implies that risk the executives differs starting with one plan then onto the next. It requires considering the current conditions and estimate number of situations that can possibly arise which may present risk for the organization. When the potential risk have been distinguished, the subsequent stage may develop counter measures.

Q: Do you think by implementing the concept of Enterprise Risk Management help you to driving your business and help you in decision making performance?

A: Risking the board is a significant practice that ought to be applied on premise. Our business needed to gain proficiency with the significance of risk the board in a hard manner since we confronted interruption on a few occasions that prompted disarray and

botch. Zero in ought to for the most part be on end clients, which we neglected to oblige viably because of absence of groundwork for such occasions.

Q: In the board directors meeting room, what are the main arguments in decision-making and how did you deal with that?

A: Major choice made by and large rotates around proposed activity that will be taken for it. The discussion usually revolves around the risk management, yet actions are rarely taken in this regard. This activity is then checked on basically by various individuals present in the group following which it acquires endorsement. Fundamental top of the association by and large has blackball control over choices however confronted little opposition as a great many people had confidence in his capacities.

Q: Do think different leadership of board directors has any impact on decision-making?

A: Leadership may play a critical role in the decision making for board, because the board always have to look forward to the leaders for finalizing the decisions. In this case, the board members are liable to the leadership.

Participant 6:

Q: What is your understanding of the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: In my opinion, the ERM is the most important element that contributes to the business success. It consists of processes that are used by managers to evaluate and reduce risks involved in the business. In tourism sector the possible risks include unavailability of hotels, infrastructure development and lack of financial resources.

Q: When you say preventing, what are the business plans and business strategies does your company use?

A: My company has a risk parameter through which we monitor possible challenges for the growth of the firm. Our decision-making process also depends on this risk parameter and it really helps us in ensuring stable business growth. The first thing that we focus on while monitoring risk is the financial risk. It is because financial risk influences every project strongly and ensuring the availability of financial resources for investment is our main aim. The pandemic has also explained the importance of

managing financial risk as companies having lack of financial assets faced serious challenges during the lockdown.

Q: When you Plan and identify Risk Management, how did you plan, did you plan project by project please explain.

A: My planning focuses on involvement on the workforce and therefore I plan in a way that doesn't put burden on employees and decrease their job satisfaction. I prefer to develop policies and strategies for every project separately. This helps me in engaging workforce in organizational activities and also assists me in allocating financial resources effectively. In my opinion, employees get motivated when a flexible working environment is provided to them.

Q: Do you think implementing the concept of Enterprise Risk Management helps you to drive your business and help you in decision-making performance?

A: Decision-making is a complicated process that involves a number of steps. The effective decision-making uses planning, monitoring, feedback, and previous record of the firm. I use my critical thinking skills and feedback from employees and other managers to develop policies for the firm. The feedback from the workforce helps me in understanding about possible risks involved in the business. Also, our Enterprise Risk Management strategy helped us in maintaining our performance during the pandemic

Q: In the board directors' meeting room, what are the main arguments in decision-making and how did you deal with that?

A: The main arguments in the decision-making in the board of directors' meetings are related to balancing risks and opportunities. For instance, directors want to generate more profit, but lack of financial resources comes up as an important challenge faced by the business in this regard. To overcome these issues, I focus on implementing several strategies such as involving managers in the decision-making process as they are more aware of the company's position, understanding the agenda role, exploring both short and long-term goals in the meeting so that everyone could understand the objectives and position of the business. I also encourage managers in the meeting to present performance of the company so that the decision-making process could be facilitated.

Q: Do think different leadership of board directors has any impact on decision-making?

A: Being a director means that you have a say in decision-making process of the business. But I think it mostly depends on shares a director has.

Participant 7:

Q: What is your understanding of the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: The trend of enterprise risk management is increasing over time in the world's business sector because of its ability to enhance firm's productivity. Managers use it to evaluate possible challenges faced by the firm and plan accordingly. The risk faced by a business depends on its objectives and the industry it is functioning in. They involve lack of financial resources, challenges involved in infrastructure development, lack of skilled employees and others.

Q: When you say preventing, what are the business plans and business strategies does your company use?

A: Completely preventing the business from risk factor is impossible. However, it is possible from managers to minimize the risk factors faced by the business. For this purpose, proper planning and information of right policies is required. In my company, I would make sure to hire risk management experts so that managers could have a clear picture of risks involved. Also, I would focus on keeping a record of the firm so that new policies could be developed based on experiences in the past.

Q: When you Plan and identify Risk Management, how did you plan, did you plan project by project please explain.

A: Planning is an important factor that contributes to the success of a business. There are different types of planning such as long-run planning and short-run planning. In my company, I prefer practicing long-run planning as it enables me to convey the annual goals and objectives to the workforce. This helps them in getting mentally prepared for goals to be achieved.

Q: Do you think implementing the concept of Enterprise Risk Management helps you to drive your business and help you in decision-making performance?

A: The information provided by enterprise risk management is of crucial importance for the decision-making process of a business. I use this information for developing effective policies. Therefore, it can be said that ERM helps in facilitating the decision-making process of my company. For instance, ERM helped me in understanding the importance of saving cost for sustainable growth of the business.

Q: In the board directors' meeting room, what are the main arguments in decision-making and how did you deal with that?

A: During such meetings, main challenge that I face is of bringing directors and managers on same page. However, to resolve touch issues I try to maintain the environment of meeting calm and friendly. I also encourage managers to present performance of the company so that directors could easily understand space for growth of the business.

Q: Do think different leadership of board directors has any impact on decision-making?

A: In my opinion every director has his own importance but as far as influence on decision making process is concerned number of shares matter a lot.

Participant 8:

Q: What is your understanding of the concept of Enterprise Risk Management?

A: Enterprise risk management is particularly important for sustainable growth of a business as it helps managers and the top-management of the business to identify the risk factors and prevent the business from them. Possible risks a business could face include insufficient financial resources, lack of technology in the organizational culture, decline in job satisfaction of employees, challenges related to transport and infrastructure etc.

Q: When you say preventing, what are the business plans and business strategies does your company use?

A: One of the objectives of my leadership is to prevent the company from risk factors as much as possible. I would use to do so. I would encourage managers to provide feedback on performance of the company and challenges faced by it. Moreover, I would also promote teamwork in the organizational culture as it would minimize the chances of risks. To prevent the company from financial risk factor I would develop a proper annual budget plan for the company. This would help me in planning and allocating resources optimally.

Q: When you Plan and identify Risk Management, how did you plan, did you plan project by project please explain.

A: Usually risk factors faced by a business are unpredictable. Therefore, in my opinion, long-run planning is more effective. It not only improves productivity of the workforce but also enhances chances of sustainable growth of a business.

Q: Do you think implementing the concept of Enterprise Risk Management helps you to drive your business and help you in decision-making performance?

A: Yes, enterprise risk management improves the decision-making process. It is because it provides information required for the decision-making process. For instance, managers get to know about the right time for further investment through ERM. So, it can be said it facilitates the decision-making process.

Q: In the board directors' meeting room, what are the main arguments in decision-making and how did you deal with that?

A: I don't face such issues because in our company's board of directors meeting, we discuss the company's performance and key performance indicators in detail. However, I use my good communication skills to avoid conflicts and confusion during the meeting. Our managers are very cooperative and professional, so it is usually easy to bring directors and managers on the same page.

Q: Do think different leadership of board directors has any impact on decision-making?

A: I think this depends on shares directors have.

